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SOSYAL BİLİMLER ENSTİTÜSÜ
SOSYOLOJİ ANABİLİM DALI
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**FROM COSMETICS TO BANKS:
AN IN-DEPTH LOOK AT PORTRAYALS OF FEMALE POWER IN ADVERTISING**

Yüksek Lisans Tezi

MERVE NUR UĞURLU

İSTANBUL, 2025

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ÖZET

Kozmetikten Bankalara:

Reklamcılıkta Kadın Gücünün Tasvirlerine Derinlemesine Bir Bakış

Kadınları güçlendirme söyleminin, çağdaş reklamcılığın görsel ve söylemsel dünyasında nasıl temsil edildiği ve yeniden kurgulandığı sorusu, son yıllarda femvertising kavramı etrafında yoğunlaşan eleştirel tartışmaların merkezine yerleşmiştir. Bu tez, söz konusu tartışmalara Türkiye bağlamında katkı sunmayı hedeflemekte; “güçlü kadın” imgesinin farklı sektörlerde ne tür anlatı biçimleriyle temsil edildiğini ve bu temsillerin toplumsal cinsiyet normlarıyla nasıl kesiştiğini sorgulamaktadır. Araştırmanın kuramsal temeli; toplumsal cinsiyetin performatifliği kuramı, feminist medya kuramı ve sosyal inşacılık yaklaşımı üzerine inşa edilmiştir. Çalışma kapsamında, YouTube’da “güçlü kadın reklam” anahtar sözcükleriyle ulaşılan, yalnızca özel sektör markalarına ait ve Türkçe yayımlanmış 51 reklam arasından amaçlı örnekleme yöntemiyle seçilen 19 reklam incelenmiştir. Veriler, nitel içerik analizi yöntemiyle değerlendirilmiş; her bir reklam görsel ve işitsel katmanlarıyla birlikte, kuramsal kodlara dayalı bir analiz sürecine tabi tutulmuştur. Elde edilen bulgular, güçlü kadın temsillerinin sektörlere göre belirgin biçimde çeşitlendiğini göstermektedir. Sonuç olarak bu çalışma, femvertising’in yalnızca ticari bir pazarlama stratejisi değil; aynı zamanda toplumsal cinsiyetin, kültürel kodların ve sektörel temsiliyet dinamiklerinin bir aynası olduğunu ortaya koymaktadır. Sektörel bağlamın, kadın imgelerini hangi biçimlerde dönüştürdüğünü sorgulayan bu çalışma, reklamcılığa eleştirel ve çok katmanlı bir medya okuması sunmaktadır.

Anahtar kelimeler: Kadın, Güç, Güçlü, Reklam, Cinsiyet

ABSTRACT

From Cosmetics to Banks: An In-Depth Look at Portrayals of Female Power in Advertising

The question of how the discourse of women’s empowerment is represented and reconstructed within the visual and discursive landscape of contemporary advertising has become central to recent critical debates, particularly those surrounding the concept of femvertising. This thesis aims to contribute to these discussions in the context of Türkiye by examining how the image of the “strong woman” is constructed through various narrative forms across different sectors, and how these representations intersect with gender norms. The theoretical framework of the research is grounded in gender performativity theory, feminist media theory, and the social constructivist approach. The study focuses on 19 advertisements selected through purposive sampling from a pool of 51 commercials published in Turkish by private sector brands on YouTube, using the keywords “güçlü kadın reklam” (“strong woman commercial”). Data were analyzed using qualitative content analysis; each advertisement was examined in both its visual and auditory dimensions, guided by theory-based coding. The findings reveal that representations of strong women vary significantly across sectors. Ultimately, this study demonstrates that femvertising is not merely a commercial marketing strategy, but also a mirror reflecting gender, cultural codes, and sectoral dynamics of representation. By interrogating how sectoral contexts shape the image of women, this research offers a critical and multilayered media reading of advertising.

Keywords: Women, Power, Strong, Advertising, Gender

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This thesis is dedicated to all strong women and girls who have had to fight for space, for voice, for freedom. My fight will always be for us.

And finally, to everyone: friends, strangers, thinkers, artists, builders, rebels, who work every day to break the unjust cycles of this world, so that women can live stronger, fairer, freer lives, thank you.

Merve Nur Uğurlu, 2025

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INTRODUCTION

In contemporary societies saturated with images, narratives, and symbols, advertisements occupy a unique position as one of the most powerful tools of cultural transmission and symbolic construction. Beyond their immediate commercial objectives, advertisements function as potent vehicles through which identities, roles, values, and hierarchies are subtly yet systematically shaped. Far from being neutral or purely economic texts, advertisements are deeply embedded within the cultural codes of their time, acting as what may be termed “silent directors” of social norms. In particular, the representations of gender within these visual and verbal texts provide fertile ground for understanding how femininity is imagined, commodified, and at times, reconfigured.

Feminism has long positioned empowerment as a core goal, seeking to challenge structures that limit women’s agency and visibility. The increasing visibility of the “strong woman” figure in advertising is not merely a reflection of evolving gender norms but also a site of ideological negotiation. The repeated portrayal of women as assertive, resilient, and autonomous suggests a departure from traditional, domestic, and passive female stereotypes. This shift demands a deeper exploration into the symbolic and discursive mechanics through which advertising constructs and circulates gendered imagery. The growing social interest in feminist discourse, the global rise of women-led movements, and the wider visibility of women in leadership, sports, science, and activism have undoubtedly reshaped the expectations surrounding female representation in the media. Within this cultural climate, the phenomenon of femvertising (consisting of the words “feminism” and “advertising”) which is a marketing strategy that integrates feminist messages to promote products or brands—has gained traction. These campaigns often foreground themes such as empowerment, confidence, independence, and collective solidarity among women. However, their authenticity, consistency, and transformative capacity remain contested, especially when examined across different sectors, target audiences, and cultural contexts.

Research Context and Problematization

The growing visibility of strong female figures in advertising reflects a convergence of social, cultural, and commercial forces in recent years. The rise of fourth-wave feminism, driven by digital activism and global movements, has amplified public discourse around gender equality. In response, brands have adopted empowerment narratives not only to align with shifting consumer expectations, but also to benefit from the market appeal of socially responsible and progressive messaging. At that point, femvertising has emerged as an advertising strategy that promises a transformation in the representation of women while simultaneously constructing an increasingly complex relationship between feminism

and marketing. This approach enables brands to aestheticize feminist discourse and integrate it into consumer culture. Campaigns frequently emphasize notions such as “strength,” “self-confidence,” and “solidarity,” replacing traditional images of womanhood with increased visibility of women across diverse body types, ages, and lifestyles. However, this trend does not always produce a transformative effect; in some cases, strength is reduced to a visual stylization—a depoliticized value coded primarily through aesthetics. While this advertising shift marks a notable development in gendered representations, academic attention has primarily concentrated on specific portrayals rather than broader structural patterns. Studies have focused either on stereotypical portrayals (e.g., domestic roles, sexualization, objectification) or on single-sector case studies. Analyses have typically examined either the portrayal of women in specific industries (e.g., cosmetics, cleaning products) or the recurrence of gender norms across advertisements more generally. What remains underexplored is a comparative, sector-based analysis of how the “strong woman” figure is constructed, circulated, and differentiated in relation to the norms, values, and expectations specific to each industry. This gap is particularly significant in the context of Türkiye, where the intersection of modernity, tradition, conservatism, and feminism produces a unique media environment. While the global logic of femvertising permeates Turkish media, its articulation is deeply shaped by local dynamics. Cultural values, religious codes, gender roles, and political discourses influence how empowerment is defined, what kind of female figures are considered “acceptable,” and how strength is visualized and narrated. Consequently, the symbolic boundaries of femvertising in Türkiye differ considerably from those observed in Western campaigns, making local analysis not only relevant but essential.

Aim of the Research

The primary aim of this study is to investigate how “strong women” are represented in femvertising campaigns across different sectors in Türkiye and to determine whether these representations converge or diverge based on industry-specific expectations and aesthetic conventions. Rather than treating femvertising as a monolithic phenomenon, this study approaches it as a flexible, culturally-contingent discourse that adapts itself to the logics of various markets.

The following questions have served as conceptual anchors guiding the progression of this study and have been taken into consideration throughout the evaluation process. Questions reflect a conceptual curiosity aimed at understanding the sectoral, cultural, and visual diversity of strong woman representations in femvertising campaigns. In this regard, traces of these questions can be observed throughout the analysis and interpretation sections of the study, manifesting in various forms.

- How are strong women represented in femvertising campaigns across different commercial sectors?

- To what extent do the visual and verbal codes of femvertising operate as tools of transformation or repetition?
- How do Türkiye’s cultural, religious, and political dynamics influence the articulation of female strength in advertising?
- What symbolic tensions or contradictions emerge when strength is visualized through gendered imagery in different industry contexts?

Methodological Overview

This study employs a qualitative content analysis approach to examine how strong women are represented in femvertising campaigns across different commercial sectors in Türkiye. The study is based on a purposively selected sample of 19 advertisements, drawn from a larger dataset of 51 femvertising campaigns disseminated via YouTube. These advertisements were categorized into eight sectoral groups, including Beauty & Personal Care, Finance & Insurance, Food, Automotive & Mobility, Fashion, Technology & Telecommunications, Home & Domestic Industries, and Industrial & Agricultural Sectors. The sectors were grouped based on shared characteristics to observe potential intergroup differences. One advertisement was selected from each sector; in cases with multiple options, a random picker was used. The selection criteria for inclusion were clearly defined. Only Turkish-language advertisements that explicitly vocalize the concept of “güç” (power/strength) or “güçlü kadın” (strong woman), and that are created by commercial brands (not public institutions), were considered. Campaigns were excluded if they merely featured women without emphasizing empowerment, or if their portrayal of strength lacked coherence with the aims of femvertising. This methodological rigor ensures the consistency and focus of the analysis.

Contribution and Significance

This research offers a unique contribution to the fields of gender studies, media analysis, and advertising theory by focusing not merely on representations of women, but specifically on representations of “strong” women. Unlike existing literature that often isolates either gender roles or industry-specific analysis, this study brings the two dimensions together through a sector-based comparative study. This focus allows for the identification of patterns, ruptures, and contradictions within femvertising practices that may not be visible when analyzed within a single domain. Furthermore, by grounding the study in the local cultural context of Türkiye, this study adds a significant layer of nuance to the global conversation on femvertising. It interrogates how empowerment is articulated in a society where gender politics are shaped by a blend of secular modernism, religious conservatism, and global consumer capitalism. This setting introduces unique constraints and opportunities for advertisers who wish to engage with feminist messaging without alienating traditional audiences or breaching social taboos. The study also advances methodological innovation by integrating both visual and auditory elements of

advertisements into a unified coding scheme informed by theoretical frameworks. This holistic approach acknowledges that meaning in advertising is not solely communicated through language or imagery, but through their interplay—an interplay that is crucial for decoding the layered narratives of strength. Finally, this research challenges simplified binaries between authentic and inauthentic empowerment. Rather than dismissing femvertising as either genuine or exploitative, this study explores its internal heterogeneity, revealing how different sectors strategically frame strength in ways that reflect their market logic, cultural positioning, and intended audience. It also considers whether the recurrence of these portrayals can generate a cumulative effect capable of shifting public perceptions and normative expectations around women’s agency and potential.

Structure of the Study

This study is organized into four main chapters, each of which builds upon the preceding one to construct a comprehensive analysis of strong women representations in femvertising. Chapter One: Theoretical Framework discusses feminism waves, key concepts from feminist media theory, gender performativity, and social constructivism, providing the analytical lenses through which the advertisements are interpreted. Chapter Two: Conceptual Framework explores women in media, femvertising, its major dimensions (empowerment, representation, commercialization), and case studies from international and Turkish campaigns. Chapter Three: Methodology outlines the methodology used and path followed in the study. Chapter Four: Analysis and Findings presents the findings of the analysis, highlighting convergences and divergences in how strong women are portrayed across industries. Finally, Conclusion and Evaluation & Recommendations summarizes key insights, reflects on the limitations of the study, and proposes future directions for research and practical application. Emphasizes the role of media responsibility in shaping inclusive and empowering narratives.

With its multi-theoretical foundation, critical methodological design, and commitment to contextual specificity, this study seeks to contribute meaningfully to ongoing discussions about gender, media, and power. By focusing on the figure of the strong woman as a cultural battleground, it illuminates how advertising simultaneously mirrors, mediates, and modifies the evolving contours of femininity in Türkiye and beyond.

CHAPTER ONE: THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

FEMINISM & GENDER

The relationship between feminism and gender is shaped by the feminist emphasis on defining gender and resolving social inequalities (Butler, 1990). Gender is not merely a biological distinction between male and female but a socially constructed system that determines roles, norms, and expectations within society (Beauvoir, 1949; Butler, 1990). Feminist scholars have argued that gender is a historical and cultural product, shaped through discourse, social institutions, and power dynamics (Scott, 1986). This perspective challenges traditional binary understandings of gender and highlights how these constructs reinforce structural inequalities (Connell, 2002).

Feminist theories critique the way societal norms dictate gender roles and advocate for a more egalitarian social structure, where individuals are not confined to identities solely based on biological sex (Butler, 1990; Oakley, 1972). Simone de Beauvoir (1949) famously stated, “One is not born, but rather becomes, a woman,” emphasizing that femininity is imposed upon individuals through socialization. Similarly, Oakley (1972) argued that gender is a learned behavior reinforced by cultural expectations and institutionalized through education, family structures, and media. This feminist critique extends beyond individual experiences to analyze how gender functions within broader social structures (Lorber, 1994).

Feminist analyses of gender inequality not only reflect differences between women and men in the social structure but also reveal how these differences serve as tools of power on social, cultural, and economic levels (Fraser, 1997; Butler, 1990). Fraser (1997) highlights how gender operates within a dual system of oppression: the cultural devaluation of women’s contributions and the economic exploitation of gendered labor. It’s possible to say that gender’s impact extends beyond individual identities and plays a significant role in social structures as well (Butler, 1990). In this context, feminism challenges the legitimacy of patriarchal systems while advocating for the creation of a society where all genders live under more equal conditions (Friedan, 1963).

The development of feminist theory emerged as a response to the assumption that gender is a fixed and natural category (Butler, 1990). Early feminist movements focused on achieving legal and political rights, while later waves introduced more nuanced critiques of gender as a constructed identity (Tong, 2009). Butler’s *Gender Trouble* (1990) played a pivotal role in shifting feminist discourse by arguing that gender is performative—that is, individuals enact gender through repeated behaviors, which sustain its social reality. This idea builds on Foucault’s (1978) concept of discourse and power, showing how gender is continuously produced and regulated through societal norms.

Thus, feminism engages in a profound analysis of gender-based inequality and the systemic structures that create and sustain it (Fraser, 1997; Butler, 1990; Crenshaw, 1989). By questioning the legitimacy of patriarchal systems, feminism seeks to dismantle hierarchical structures and advocate for transformative change (hooks¹, 1984). The feminist movement is not monolithic but comprises diverse perspectives, from liberal feminism's emphasis on legal equality to radical feminism's critique of patriarchal power and socialist feminism's focus on economic structures (Tong, 2009). Despite these differences, a common goal unites feminists: the pursuit of a society in which gender does not determine one's opportunities, rights, or social status (Friedan, 1963).

1.1. Feminism: Waves

Feminism is both an ideology and a social movement that has evolved to challenge gender-based inequalities in political, economic, and cultural life (Beauvoir, 1949; hooks, 1984). Its roots date back to the late 18th century, when thinkers like Wollstonecraft began advocating for women's rights to education and citizenship (Wollstonecraft, 1792; Tong, 2009). Early feminism emerged in reaction to patriarchal systems that restricted women's autonomy and legal status (Delphy, 1984; Beauvoir, 1949). Over time, the movement expanded through successive waves, each shaped by distinct historical and theoretical contexts (Freedman, 2001; Evans, 1979). Despite internal differences, feminist thought consistently aims to achieve gender equality, empowerment, and the dismantling of systemic oppression (Butler, 1990; Crenshaw, 1991).

First-Wave Feminism

The first wave of feminism, which emerged in the late 19th and early 20th centuries, focused primarily on securing basic legal rights for women, particularly the right to vote, access to education, and property rights (Freedman, 2001; McMillen, 2008; Offen, 1988). It is possible to say that liberal feminism constituted the strongest theoretical basis of the first wave because one of the movement's key achievements was the fight for women's suffrage and legal equality. As an example, in the United States, key figures such as Susan B. Anthony and Elizabeth Cady Stanton led suffrage campaigns (McMillen, 2008). The struggle for women's suffrage highlighted the intersection between gender and democracy, and the right to vote was seen as essential for women's participation in shaping laws and policies that affected their lives (Fawcett, 1912). Furthermore, the early feminist agenda included access to higher education and ownership rights, as women sought to gain intellectual and economic autonomy. The first wave, although limited in scope, had a profound impact on the legal status of women and laid the foundation for later feminist activism by securing some of the most fundamental rights that women were historically denied (McMillen, 2008).

¹ bell hooks chose to write her name in lowercase as a rejection of individual glorification, emphasizing that ideas matter more than the person. This decision reflected both the collective spirit of the feminist movement and her respect for her maternal great-grandmother (hooks, interview by Lowens, 2018).

Second-Wave Feminism

The second wave of feminism, which began in the 1960s, marked a significant shift in the goals and methods of feminist activism. Although liberal feminism in the second wave still advocated for legal reforms on issues such as equal rights for women, labor equality and domestic violence, the second wave broadened its scope to address issues related to social and cultural inequality, including reproductive rights, workplace discrimination, and sexual liberation (Evans, 1979). A key distinction of the second wave was the emphasis on women's autonomy and the right to control their bodies, particularly through access to birth control and abortion services (Morgan, 1970). This period also saw the rise of consciousness-raising groups, where women shared their personal experiences and connected them to broader societal issues, highlighting the intersections between personal and political lives (hooks, 1984). It is possible to say that the footsteps of radical feminism were heard during this period because the second wave significantly expanded the feminist agenda by challenging deeply ingrained social norms and patriarchy, and questioning traditional gender roles, ultimately reshaping the public discourse around women's place in society. This period also bears traces of Marxist and socialist feminism, which emphasized the economic and class exploitation of women and defended the rights of women workers. Feminists of this period, such as Friedan (1963) and Gloria Steinem (2000) tackled issues like workplace inequality, reproductive rights, and gender-based violence, and their efforts culminated in landmark legislative reforms like the Equal Pay Act and Title IX in the United States (Friedan, 1963). The second wave also led to the establishment of feminist institutions and organizations that continue to influence women's rights advocacy, such as the National Organization for Women (NOW), founded in 1966 by Betty Friedan and others, and the Ms. Foundation for Women, co-founded in 1972 by Gloria Steinem to support grassroots feminist initiatives (Rosen, 2000; Ginsburg, 1990).

Third-Wave Feminism

The third wave of feminism emerged in the 1990s, building on the achievements of the second wave while introducing new perspectives on feminism's inclusivity, fluidity, and diversity (Baumgardner & Richards, 2000; Valenti, 2007). Postmodern feminist thinkers challenged universalist assumptions, emphasizing that women's experiences of oppression vary across intersections of race, class, sexuality, religion, and ability (Crenshaw, 1991; Baumgardner & Richards, 2000). Third-wave feminism rejected the idea of a singular feminist identity, promoting instead a pluralistic and individualized approach that embraced contradictions, multiplicity, and hybridity (Valenti, 2007).

This wave was also marked by critical theoretical contributions such as Judith Butler's theory of gender performativity, which questioned the binary and essentialist conceptions of gender (Butler, 1990), and Donna Haraway's cyborg feminism, which explored the intersection between gender, technology, and embodiment in postmodern society (Haraway, 1991). These frameworks allowed feminists to critique normative gender expectations and develop new languages for gender identity, including queer, trans, and nonbinary perspectives (Butler, 1990; Haraway, 1991).

Moreover, third-wave feminism embraced the use of digital media to amplify voices and foster activism (Munro, 2013). Blogs, forums, and later social media platforms enabled feminist engagement in decentralized, grassroots forms, transforming how movements were built and sustained (Munro, 2013). Feminist campaigns such as #YesAllWomen and #MeToo—though emerging in later years—were rooted in third-wave strategies of consciousness-raising and networked mobilization (Munro, 2013; Valenti, 2007).

Finally, third-wave feminists sought to reclaim femininity and beauty practices, arguing that choosing traditionally “feminine” aesthetics could coexist with feminist empowerment when exercised autonomously (Baumgardner & Richards, 2000). This marked a departure from the second wave’s more oppositional stance toward beauty culture (Baumgardner & Richards, 2000).

Fourth-Wave Feminism

The fourth wave of feminism, which began in the early 2010s, is characterized by its focus on digital activism and social media campaigns (Jackson et al., 2020; Banet-Weiser, 2018). Fourth-wave feminists have used platforms like Twitter, Facebook, and Instagram to mobilize around issues such as sexual harassment, gender-based violence, and gender inequality (Jackson et al., 2020). The #MeToo movement, which gained widespread attention in 2017, exemplifies the power of social media in mobilizing women’s voices and challenging systemic abuse and harassment (Adichie, 2014). The digital age has enabled women to amplify their voices and create communities of support, allowing for the rapid dissemination of feminist messages and the organization of protests and campaigns in real-time. Additionally, the fourth wave has emphasized the importance of sexual and reproductive rights, with activists advocating for policies that protect women’s autonomy over their bodies and access to healthcare (Fotopoulou, 2016). In this wave, feminist movements are not only concerned with legislative reforms but also with creating a cultural shift that challenges entrenched gender norms and promotes gender equality across all sectors of society. By leveraging digital technologies and global networks, fourth-wave feminists have advanced the conversation on gender justice in ways that previous waves could not have imagined (Jackson et al., 2020). Feminist scholars such as Sarah Banet-Weiser and Aristeia Fotopoulou have been especially influential in articulating how media, popular culture, and digital technologies shape contemporary feminist activism and public engagement (Banet-Weiser, 2018; Fotopoulou, 2016).

The fourth wave of feminism in Türkiye is increasingly shaped by digital activism, with campaigns like #sendeanlat, #BenimBedenimBenimKararım, and #İstanbulSözleşmesiYaşatır creating spaces for women to share personal experiences, claim bodily autonomy, and mobilize public discourse. These movements reflect a localized form of technofeminism that blends online advocacy with street protest (Dinçer, 2023; Özkazanç, 2018). The slogan “Benim Bedenim Benim Kararım” has become a central feminist demand, especially in debates around reproductive rights and state control over women’s bodies, resonating with global fourth-wave themes of consent and bodily integrity (Öztaş, 2020).

Scholars emphasize that Türkiye's digital feminism is not a mere imitation of Western models but a hybrid, context-specific activism that innovates new repertoires of resistance (Akşit & Akşit, 2021).

The different waves of feminism have shaped women's efforts to transform their social positions, while also contributing to the evolution of gender roles and stereotypes within society. These roles and stereotypes have been deeply intertwined with historical processes and have been shaped alongside social structures over time. Feminism argues that the confinement of women and men to specific roles perpetuates the inequalities within societal structures. Therefore, feminism not only critiques gender roles and stereotypes but also advocates for their transformation, aiming to achieve gender equality in society.

1.2. Gender: Lenses

The concepts of sex and gender are foundational to the study of social identity and human interaction. While sex refers to the biological attributes that differentiate male and female bodies- such as chromosomes, reproductive anatomy, and hormonal differences- gender encompasses the social, cultural, and psychological attributes associated with masculinity and femininity (Fausto-Sterling, 2000). West and Zimmerman (1987) introduced the concept of "doing gender", emphasizing that gender is not merely a static identity but an ongoing social performance shaped by interactions and expectations. This framework closely aligns with the theory of gender performativity developed by Butler (1990), who argued that gender is not a stable identity grounded in biological essence, but a stylized repetition of acts that produce the illusion of coherence. Crucially, Butler challenges the assumption that biological sex precedes gender, claiming that sex itself is discursively constructed and performative: "Sex is as culturally constructed as gender; indeed, perhaps it was always gender" (Butler, 1990). Simone de Beauvoir (1949) was among the first scholars to challenge biological determinism in gender identity. She famously asserted, "On ne naît pas femme: on le devient" (translated as "One is not born, but rather becomes, a woman") highlighting the role of socialization in shaping gender roles. Similarly, Ann Oakley (1972) argued that differences between men and women arise not from biological necessity but from social conditioning, reinforced by institutions such as family, education, and media.

The distinction between sex and gender is a relatively recent concept in sociological and feminist thought, gaining prominence in the mid-20th century. Oakley (1972) emphasized that while sex is a biological category, gender is shaped by societal expectations. This distinction was further elaborated by scholars like Nancy Chodorow (1978), who examined how early childhood socialization reinforces traditional gender roles. Butler's (1990) concept of gender performativity challenges the idea of gender as a stable identity. She argues that gender is enacted through repeated behaviors, which sustain societal expectations. This perspective contrasts with earlier views that saw gender as a fixed trait linked to biology (Fausto-Sterling, 2000). Connell (2005) extended these ideas by introducing the concept of "hegemonic masculinity", which explains how certain expressions of masculinity dominate while others

are marginalized. Together, these theoretical contributions illustrate how gender is not a passive reflection of biology, but an active, socially constructed process that maintains and legitimizes hierarchical structures within society.

Gender stereotypes are widely held, oversimplified beliefs about the characteristics and roles of men and women (Lorber, 1994). These stereotypes shape not only individual behavior but also institutional dynamics and cultural expectations (Bem, 1981). For instance, traditional norms associate women with nurturing and emotion, while men are expected to exhibit strength and rationality. Goffman (1979) illustrated how these dichotomies are visually encoded in advertising, where men often appear as dominant actors and women as passive figures. Expanding on this, Gill (2007) argued that postfeminist media culture constructs a contradictory image of women—simultaneously empowered and objectified—thus reinforcing neoliberal ideals under the guise of individual choice. In occupational contexts, Williams (1995) introduced the concept of the “glass escalator”, showing how men in female-dominated professions are subtly advantaged. These enduring stereotypes do more than reflect social norms; they actively sustain gender hierarchies, limit opportunities, and condition self-perceptions (Eagly & Karau, 2002). Deconstructing these patterns is essential not only for equity but for reshaping the cultural logic that legitimizes them.

Gender roles refer to the expectations and norms that societies assign to individuals based on their perceived gender. These roles dictate behaviors, responsibilities, and social interactions, shaping how individuals navigate their personal and professional lives (Lorber, 1994). Barrie Thorne (1993) studied how children are socialized into gender roles through play, demonstrating that boys and girls are often encouraged to engage in different types of activities that reinforce traditional expectations. Similarly, Chodorow (1978) argued that caregiving roles, particularly within families, contribute to the reproduction of gender norms. Sherry Ortner (1974) examined how societies often associate women with nature and men with culture, reinforcing ideas that position women as caregivers and men as leaders. This perspective highlights how gender roles are historically tied to broader cultural narratives. The transmission of gender roles is further reinforced by institutions such as media, education, and religion (Gill, 2007). For example, Joan Scott (1986) analyzed how historical discourse shapes gender expectations, demonstrating that gender roles are not static but evolve over time.

The formation of gender stereotypes and roles begins at an early age and is shaped by multiple socialization agents. Dorothy Dinnerstein (1976) argued that early childhood experiences, particularly interactions with primary caregivers, play a crucial role in reinforcing gender norms. This idea aligns with Chodorow’s (1978) theory that mother-child relationships contribute to the persistence of traditional gender roles. Connell (2005) explored how societal structures maintain and enforce gender roles, emphasizing the role of hegemonic masculinity in sustaining male dominance. Silvia Federici (2004) linked gender roles to capitalist economies, arguing that women’s unpaid labor within the

household sustains economic systems. Cynthia Enloe (2014) extended this discussion to global politics, demonstrating how gender roles influence international relations and labor markets; her work highlights the intersection between gender, economics, and power. The reinforcement of gender stereotypes occurs also through cultural narratives and institutional practices (Williams, 1995): Goffman's (1979) analysis of gender in advertising demonstrates how commercial representations contribute to societal expectations about femininity and masculinity. Taken all together, these perspectives demonstrate how stereotypes and roles are not only descriptive but actively constitutive of power, ideology, and social order—making their deconstruction essential to feminist praxis.

Gender roles have not only shaped individual identities but also influenced the organization of societies throughout history. These roles have evolved under the influence of shifting economic, political, and cultural conditions (Oakley, 1972; Scott, 1986; Connell, 2005). While certain expectations about masculinity and femininity have remained stable, historical events such as industrialization, global conflict, and feminist movements have redefined gender norms over time (Boserup, 1970; Hartmann, 1981; Goldin, 1990; Friedan, 1963). Boserup (1970) argues that the shift to agrarian economies intensified gender inequality because men's control over land and large-scale farming led to patriarchal social structures, where women's roles became primarily domestic. In many early civilizations—including Mesopotamia, Ancient Greece, and China—women were excluded from political power and formal education, reinforcing their secondary status in society (Ortner, 1974). In many traditional agrarian cultures, strict gender roles dictated women's responsibilities in domestic work, while men assumed public and economic authority (Oakley, 1972). These patterns were reinforced by religious and legal doctrines. For example, in many medieval European societies, laws restricted women's property rights and placed them under male guardianship (Scott, 1986). Dorothy Dinnerstein (1976) and Nancy Chodorow (1978) argue that maternal roles became central to women's identities in these societies, reinforcing the expectation that caregiving was an inherently female duty. These ideas persisted for centuries, influencing cultural perceptions of motherhood and domesticity.

The Industrial Revolution (18th–19th century) fundamentally altered gender roles by shifting economic activity from rural farms to urban factories. As industrialization expanded, men became the primary wage earners in manufacturing and trade (Hartmann, 2010). Working-class women participated in factory labor which was challenging traditional gender norms, yet they were still working often under harsh and exploitative conditions, paid less than men and often restricted to “feminine” jobs such as textile work or domestic service (Williams, 1995). During and after the World Wars, millions of women entered the workforce to fill roles left by men who were conscripted into military service (Goldin, 1990), causing a dramatic transformation in gender roles. These changes temporarily disrupted traditional gender norms, proving that women could perform jobs traditionally reserved for men. However, after the wars ended, societal pressure encouraged women to return to domestic roles. The 1950s “ideal

housewife” image reinforced traditional gender expectations (Williams, 1995). Yet, the mid-to-late 20th century witnessed a steady increase in women’s workforce participation, driven by economic necessity and changing social attitudes.

The Second-Wave Feminism movement (1960s–1980s) played a pivotal role in redefining gender roles, challenging traditional expectations of women. Friedan’s *The Feminine Mystique* (1963) exposed the widespread dissatisfaction among women confined to domestic roles, igniting a movement that led to significant legal reforms, such as the Equal Pay Act (1963) and Title IX (1972). Expanding the discourse, Butler (1990) and hooks (1984) critiqued feminism’s limitations, emphasizing the intersections of gender, race, and class. hooks, in particular, highlighted how mainstream feminism often marginalized women of color and working-class women, calling for a more inclusive approach.

The late 20th century saw increasing challenges to rigid gender roles, influenced by shifting social movements and academic discourse. Butler’s (1990) concept of gender performativity arguing that gender is not inherent but constructed through repeated behaviors shaped by societal expectations, reshaped perspectives and continues to influence contemporary discussions on identity and gender expression. As legal and social frameworks and facilities such as technology evolved, mainstream discourse increasingly questioned established gender norms, creating new spaces for gender activism, challenging traditional stereotypes and promoting diverse gender expressions (Gill, 2007). Even though postfeminist media culture presents contradictory messages -both empowering women and reinforcing beauty standards, female representation in media has improved, gendered expectations still persist (Gill, 2007).

Focusing on three pivotal gender theories -Social Constructivism (1966), Feminist Media Theory (1975), and Gender Performativity (1990)- these frameworks provide a robust analytical lens to examine the portrayal of strong women in advertisements across diverse sectors. By integrating these perspectives, the aim is to explore how advertisements construct, reinforce, or challenge gender norms and stereotypes, thereby contributing to the broader discourse on gender perceptions in contemporary advertising. Each theory serves as a distinct yet complementary tool, enabling a multi-layered analysis to address research questions concerning sectoral variations and their societal implications.

Social Constructivism Theory

Social Constructivism posits that social reality is not an inherent or objective phenomenon but is actively constructed through interactions among individuals and groups within a given society (Berger & Luckmann, 1966). In their seminal work, *The Social Construction of Reality: A Treatise in the Sociology of Knowledge*, Berger and Luckmann (1966) articulate that reality emerges through a triadic process: externalization, objectivation, and internalization. Externalization refers to the process through which

individuals project their subjective experiences, values, and social norms into the external world, embedding them within cultural artifacts such as language, traditions, and media representations (Berger & Luckmann, 1966). Objectivation occurs when these externalized meanings take on a seemingly objective existence, becoming collectively recognized as social “truths” that shape institutionalized norms (Berger & Luckmann, 1966). Internalization, in turn, describes the process by which individuals absorb and integrate these constructed realities into their consciousness, perceiving them as natural and self-evident components of social life (Berger & Luckmann, 1966). This iterative cycle ensures that social constructs not only reflect existing norms but also actively reinforce and reproduce them, making certain gendered meanings appear immutable over time.

Feminist scholars have extended this framework to highlight how gender, too, is a socially constructed institution rather than a biological given. Judith Lorber (1994) argues that gender is a social institution—a pervasive system that organizes work, family roles, sexual behavior, and symbolic interactions. Gender, according to Lorber, is constructed through ongoing social practices that reinforce its “naturalness.” Similarly, West and Zimmerman (1987) introduce the concept of “doing gender,” emphasizing that gender is a routine, methodical, and situated activity that individuals perform with each other in everyday life. This performance is governed by institutional and cultural expectations and often involves adhering to normative behaviors aligned with masculinity or femininity: “Gender is not a set of traits, nor a variable, nor a role, but the product of social doings of some sort.” (West and Zimmerman, 1987).

From a constructivist perspective, then, gender is not simply a reflection of internal identity or biological difference, but a cultural narrative that is stabilized through repetition and institutional reinforcement. These narratives are embedded in language, education systems, laws, religious codes, and media—each acting as a site where gendered meanings are constructed and circulated. Importantly, these constructed norms often carry exclusionary implications. Feminist critiques have shown how dominant constructions of gender tend to privilege whiteness, heterosexuality, middle-class status, and able-bodiedness, while marginalizing identities and expressions that fall outside of these frameworks (Lorber, 1994; Butler, 1990; Crenshaw, 1989).

By making the constructed nature of gender visible, social constructivist theory provides a powerful analytical lens for understanding how norms become naturalized and how they might be resisted. It invites scholars to question taken-for-granted realities and to examine the socio-historical processes that produce and legitimize specific understandings of gender.

Feminist Media Theory

Feminist Media Theory provides a critical framework for analyzing how media representations of gender, particularly women, are embedded within and reflective of patriarchal structures (Mulvey, 1975). Emerging from the second wave of feminism, this theory gained prominence with Laura Mulvey's groundbreaking article, "Visual Pleasure and Narrative Cinema," which introduced the concept of the male gaze (Mulvey, 1975). She argues that media constructs women as objects of visual pleasure for a presumed male audience, reinforcing gender hierarchies through both visual representation and narrative positioning. The male gaze not only objectifies women but also limits their agency by structuring their roles in ways that prioritize male pleasure and control. This is particularly relevant in advertising, where women are frequently depicted in ways that appeal to male spectatorship, even when presented as strong or independent figures. Subsequent scholars expanded this critique beyond film into advertising, demonstrating how commercials commodify women's bodies and reinforce restrictive gender roles. Van Zoonen (1994) argues that media functions both as a mirror and an agent of social change, meaning that advertisements both reflect and construct dominant gender ideologies. This extends to editorial choices, aesthetic conventions, and corporate marketing strategies that perpetuate patriarchal narratives while framing them as progressive representations of gender equality. Feminist Media Theory serves as a critical lens to scrutinize the portrayal of strong women in advertisements, assessing whether these depictions genuinely empower women or merely repackage patriarchal norms under the guise of progress (hooks, 1992). In the case of cosmetic advertisements, for instance, campaigns promoting "empowered beauty" often reinforce traditional beauty standards, aligning with Mulvey's male gaze rather than challenging systemic gender inequalities (Mulvey, 1975). Even when empowerment is invoked, it is frequently tied to self-objectification, positioning attractiveness as a prerequisite for female agency.

This study explores how feminist ideals intersect with commercial imperatives in constructing strong women's imagery. Furthermore, Tuchman's (1978) concept of "symbolic annihilation" will be employed to assess whether advertisements genuinely broaden representations of female strength or merely offer market-friendly iterations of empowerment that exclude more radical feminist perspectives.

Gender Performativity Theory

Judith Butler's Gender Performativity theory redefines gender as a dynamic, iterative process rather than a fixed essence, asserting that it is constituted through repeated performances shaped by societal norms (Butler, 1990). In "Gender Trouble: Feminism and the Subversion of Identity", Butler argues that gender is not something one "is" but something one "does," enacted through bodily gestures, behaviors, and discourses (Butler, 1990). These performative acts, repeated over time, create the illusion of a stable and natural gender identity. Judith Butler's writings on performativity, gender roles, and stereotypes are

intricately linked to Jacques Derrida's concept of deconstruction (Butler, 1990; Derrida, 1976). Butler builds on Derrida's perspective that meaning lacks fixity and is continuously deferred and transformed through *différance* (Derrida, 1976). This Derridean influence underscores Butler's contention that gender remains an inherently fluid and contested category, shaped by power structures and cultural expectations (Butler, 1993).

Building upon Simone de Beauvoir's assertion that "one is not born, but rather becomes, a woman" (Beauvoir, 1949), gender is considered not as a biological reality but a construct shaped by reiterated performances. Similarly, Foucault's concept of discourse (1978) also influences Butler's understanding of how power operates through language, institutions, and social norms to regulate gender performances. Through these frameworks, Butler challenges essentialist notions of gender identity, arguing that there is no inherent femininity or masculinity outside the repetitive acts that constitute them.

Advertising, as a site of both cultural production and ideological reinforcement, performs gender through visual and linguistic cues, embedding social expectations within the representations it constructs. Derrida's approach to uncovering internal contradictions within texts is evident in Butler's deconstruction of gender norms, demonstrating that stereotypes are not static but exist on an unstable foundation (Butler, 1990). Advertisements do not simply reflect gender norms but actively produce and normalize them. This study applies Gender Performativity to analyze the performative elements in advertisements -gestures, wardrobe choices, body language, and dialogues etc.- to assess how they construct female strength. These elements do not merely depict gender but actively bring it into being.

The social transformations that have unfolded across different waves of feminism, along with gender theories, provide a critical framework for understanding how gender perceptions are shaped. Women's roles in both public and private spheres are structured through various discourses and representational practices, which, in turn, directly influence societal perceptions of womanhood. Building upon this foundation, the next chapter focuses on exploring the manifestations of women's representations across various domains.

CHAPTER TWO: CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

WOMEN IN MEDIA

2.1. Gender Through Media

The Social Construction of Gender in Media

From the perspective of social constructivism, gender is not an innate, fixed reality but a concept shaped through social interactions, historical contexts, and cultural processes (Berger & Luckmann, 1966). Within this framework, media functions as a central institution that participates in the production and reproduction of gender norms. Media is not merely a reflection of social reality; it is an active producer of meaning. Through television, cinema, advertising, and social media, narratives about “femininity” and “masculinity” are created and circulated. These representations help establish normative structures that shape how individuals perceive and experience gender in everyday life.

Gaye Tuchman’s (1978) concept of “symbolic annihilation” is significant in this context. She argues that media marginalizes women either by rendering them invisible or by restricting them to narrow, stereotypical roles. This idea reveals how media does not merely mirror social hierarchies but constructs and legitimizes them through repetitive and selective portrayals. From a social constructivist viewpoint, media institutions operate within economic and political frameworks that influence the meanings they produce. Rosalind Gill (2007) explains that contemporary media functions within a neoliberal cultural logic, presenting gender as an individualized, depoliticized, and commodified identity. As such, gender is constructed not through personal autonomy but through ideologies shaped by market interests and consumer culture.

The production of gender in media also relies heavily on visual and narrative techniques. Elements such as lighting, camera work, color, narrative structure, and dialogue are culturally coded devices that create specific meanings. These tools work together to naturalize certain gender roles, embedding them in visual and storytelling norms that are consumed and internalized by audiences (Goffman, 1979). Mulvey’s (1975) influential concept of the “male gaze” further explains how classical cinematic techniques position viewers—regardless of their actual gender—as masculine subjects, inviting them to adopt a voyeuristic perspective on female bodies. A visual positioning which women are represented as passive objects of desire, framed through aesthetic conventions that emphasize their look, contributes to the reproduction of gendered power dynamics by normalizing a mode of looking that privileges male dominance and female objectification. While traditional mass media often worked to stabilize dominant gender ideologies, the rise of digital and participatory platforms offers the potential for more diverse

expressions (Abidin, 2016). However, even these platforms are shaped by structural forces such as capitalism, algorithms, and aesthetic norms, which can limit the scope of genuine diversity.

One of the most evident ways media constructs gender is through the repetition and reinforcement of normative femininity and masculinity. According to social constructivist thought, these norms are not biologically determined but are built over time through cultural transmission and symbolic practices. Femininity in media is often represented through ideals such as beauty, emotionality, care, fragility, and passivity. Naomi Wolf (1991), in “The Beauty Myth”, argues that modern media has created a dominant beauty ideology that links women’s value to their appearance, using this ideology as a form of control. Advertising plays a key role in reproducing and normalizing this ideal. These representations stylize the female body in ways that sexualize and aestheticize it, not only dictating how women should look but also how they should behave. bell hooks (1992) points out that these norms often center whiteness, youth, and heterosexuality, while marginalizing queer women, older women, and women of color, reinforcing a narrow, exclusionary femininity. Masculinity is also constructed in the media through hegemonic ideals. Raewyn Connell’s (2005) concept of “hegemonic masculinity” refers to a culturally dominant model of manhood defined by power, control, heterosexuality, and emotional restraint. This model is consistently reinforced in media through portrayals of strength, action, and rationality, particularly in advertisements and genres targeting male audiences. Gill (2008) notes that even seemingly alternative male figures such as emotionally expressive or metrosexual men, often remain within the bounds of commodified masculinity. These representations are not subversive but are simply market-adapted forms of dominant masculine norms.

Media representations of gender are frequently structured through binary oppositions: male/female, active/passive, rational/emotional (van Zoonen, 1994; Goffman, 1979). These binaries not as reflections of natural differences but as culturally produced constructs that gain authority through repetition (Berger & Luckmann, 1966). Even progressive-looking content may reproduce these binaries subtly. A strong female character may still be sexualized, or a sensitive male character may still be positioned as the decision-maker. These contradictions reveal how gendered meanings in media are layered, complex, and ideologically saturated, emphasizing the importance of critical analysis.

The literature on the social construction of gender in media explores how gender identities are produced, legitimized, and circulated through media systems, rather than simply represented. Social constructivist theory provides a robust framework for understanding how cultural norms become internalized and appear “natural.”

Gaye Tuchman (1978) laid the foundation for feminist critiques of media with her theory of symbolic annihilation, arguing that women are either erased from media or confined to restrictive roles. While groundbreaking, her framework has been critiqued for not fully addressing the diversity of contemporary media landscapes. Naomi Wolf (1991) critiques how the media uses beauty standards as a form of social

regulation. In her analysis, advertising becomes the site where a dominant femininity is produced and policed—aligning closely with constructivist views that such standards are culturally manufactured. Gillian Dyer (1982) emphasizes the myth-making function of advertising, noting that visual codes and narrative tropes work to make constructed gender norms appear natural and self-evident. Her work reveals how representation operates as a system of meaning-making, rather than a mirror of reality. Nancy Fraser (1995) offers a vital critique of constructivist approaches that ignore material and structural dimensions. She argues that analyses of gender construction must also account for the economic and institutional factors, such as class, race, and access to power, that shape identity and representation. Gill (2007) contributes significantly to this discourse by analyzing post-feminist media culture. She shows how media presents women as empowered, autonomous individuals, yet does so within consumerist frameworks that depoliticize and commodify this empowerment, a phenomenon she terms “commodified agency.” Angela McRobbie (2004) also critiques the post-feminist assumption that feminism’s goals have been achieved. She argues that narratives of personal choice and self-expression often mask ongoing structural inequalities, reconfiguring patriarchy in more subtle and insidious ways. Connell’s (2005) concept of hegemonic masculinity is central to understanding how dominant forms of manhood are constructed and maintained across various media. It highlights the cultural work that media performs in defining and legitimizing one form of masculinity while marginalizing others. Abidin (2016) explores how influencer culture on digital platforms allows for new forms of gender self-representation. However, she cautions that these representations are often shaped by platform economies, aesthetic standards, and algorithmic visibility, revealing that even participatory media spaces are not free from the logics of social construction.

In sum, the critical literature rooted in social constructivism shows that gender in media is not a fixed reality but a dynamic, culturally produced construct. These scholarly works illustrate how gender norms are shaped by historical processes, institutional structures, and symbolic systems of meaning. Understanding this foundation is crucial for analyzing the logic, limits, and contradictions of femvertising and similar commercialized gender discourses.

Gender Performativity and Visual Repetition

Judith Butler’s theory of gender performativity (1990) fundamentally challenged essentialist views of gender by suggesting that gender identity is not innate but is constituted through the stylized repetition of acts. Rather than reflecting a pre-existing identity, these acts collectively give the illusion of gender coherence. In contemporary digital media environments, especially in social platforms such as Instagram, TikTok, and YouTube, this process of reiteration is not only visible but also intensified and monetized. Digital platforms offer both the infrastructure and incentive for constant performance. The omnipresence of visual self-presentation, algorithm-driven engagement, and the demand for consistent content creation produces a cultural atmosphere in which identity is shaped by visibility. Gender, especially femininity, is performed in a loop of repetition, aestheticization, and commercialization

(Banet-Weiser, 2018). These repetitions often reproduce dominant visual codes associated with femininity: beauty, softness, sexual availability, and emotional expressiveness, thus stabilizing gender norms rather than disrupting them.

From a Butlerian perspective, the constant visual articulation of gendered identity on digital platforms does not merely express femininity; it constitutes it. Every filtered selfie, curated aesthetic, and carefully timed dance video contributes to the performative sedimentation of what is legible as “woman.” These acts are not freely chosen expressions but are structured within a matrix of social, cultural, and technological expectations. As Butler (1993) later elaborates, performativity always occurs within a regulatory framework, where deviations from the norm are sanctioned or erased. Moreover, the visual grammar of these platforms favors repetition in the algorithmic sense. Content that adheres to popular trends and formats is rewarded with visibility and engagement, while content that deviates risks marginalization. Thus, performative repetition in digital culture is not only discursively enforced but technologically encoded. The visual field becomes a regulatory regime, not unlike the heteronormative discourses Butler critiques. The rise of influencer culture provides a particularly fertile site for examining how femininity is performed and regulated in digital spaces. Influencers, particularly women, operate within a gendered economy where visual self-presentation becomes a form of labor. As Abidin (2016) explains, influencers engage in “calibrated amateurism,” crafting an image that appears spontaneous and authentic while being highly calculated. This balancing act between relatability and desirability is particularly gendered: femininity is expected to be emotionally expressive, nurturing, and physically appealing, yet never overly artificial. Butler’s framework illuminates how these influencer performances are not simply choices but conform to a set of norms that render femininity intelligible. The repetition of makeup tutorials, skincare routines, wellness mantras, and fashion hauls construct an aestheticized version of femininity that aligns with post-feminist ideals of empowerment through consumption (Gill, 2008). These acts, while appearing individualized, are in fact collective performances of gender scripted by platform norms and capitalist incentives. What makes the influencer economy unique is that femininity itself becomes a monetizable asset. Partnerships with beauty brands, sponsored content, and engagement metrics transform the performance of femininity into economic capital.

In the digital age, femininity is not only performed but increasingly aestheticized and commodified. The transition from performativity to product is seamless. Skincare routines become sponsored rituals; morning vlogs become soft branding campaigns. As Dobson (2015) observes, the “Instagram face” which could be considered a globalized aesthetic blending youth, softness, and sexual allure, has become an aspirational norm. This visual template reflects a neoliberal mode of femininity where empowerment is equated with the ability to self-manage, self-optimize, and self-brand. This process is deeply entangled with the visual economies of platforms. The stylization of everyday femininity which includes the breakfast flatlay, the workout post, the “no makeup” selfie, transforms personal identity into public

commodity. These repeated images collectively contribute to what Gill (2007) terms the “post-feminist sensibility”: a cultural discourse that celebrates female autonomy and empowerment while remaining firmly entrenched in consumerism and beauty norms. Such representations are not necessarily deceptive or inauthentic, but they are structured by what platforms deem visible and profitable. According to McRobbie (2009), post-feminism shifts attention from structural critiques of patriarchy to narratives of individual empowerment. Conforming to beauty norms is framed as personal choice rather than social pressure. Yet this agency is limited, as alternative forms of femininity are often either assimilated or erased. Moreover, the algorithmic architecture of digital media intensifies this commodification. Engagement metrics determine which performances are seen, liked, and monetized. Influencers are thus incentivized to reproduce specific visual codes over and over again. This creates a feedback loop in which aesthetic conformity is both a strategy for success and a disciplinary mechanism.

In the algorithmically governed spaces of media, repetition is not merely habitual, it is infrastructural. It governs what forms of femininity are visible, profitable, and legitimate. Femininity is rendered as both a performance and a product: meticulously curated, visually refined, and economically circulated. The power of repetition in this context lies in its ability to stabilize the very gender norms that media is often believed to disrupt. Understanding this performative economy is essential for analyzing strategies like femvertising, which capitalize on the language of empowerment while reproducing commodified femininity.

Feminist Media Critiques and the Gendered Gaze

Feminist media theory has long been concerned with the visual representation of women and the ideological mechanisms through which the female body is coded, controlled, and consumed in media (Mulvey, 1975; Kaplan, 1983; Goffman, 1979). Central to this discussion is Laura Mulvey’s (1975) seminal concept of the “male gaze,” which highlights the ways in which mainstream cinema constructs its narratives and visual style around the pleasures of a presumed heterosexual male viewer. Mulvey (1975) argued that classical Hollywood cinema, through techniques such as point-of-view shots, close-ups, and objectifying framings, positions women as passive objects of visual pleasure, rather than as active subjects with agency. Mulvey’s theory (1975), rooted in psychoanalytic film theory, proposed that cinematic spectatorship is gendered. The camera functions as an extension of the male gaze, rendering women as visual spectacles rather than narrative agents. This process of objectification is not incidental; it is embedded within the structure of the visual language itself. Camera angles, framing, lighting, and editing techniques all contribute to constructing femininity as something to be looked at, consumed, and aesthetically evaluated (Kaplan, 1983). Mulvey’s work laid the foundation for subsequent feminist critiques that interrogated not only who is looking and at what, but also how looking is constructed as an act of power. While Mulvey’s analysis focused primarily on cinema, her insights have been widely adapted to other media forms, particularly advertising, television, and digital platforms. In advertising,

the logic of the male gaze is amplified through repetition and commodification. The female body is fragmented, stylized, and deployed as a vehicle for selling products, ideas, and lifestyles.

Feminist media theory has evolved to critique not only the male gaze but also the systems of value and pleasure that sustain it. bell hooks (1992) challenged Mulvey's model by arguing that not all viewers occupy the same spectatorial position. hooks (1992) introduced the concept of the "oppositional gaze," emphasizing that Black female spectators, in particular, resist and reinterpret dominant representations. This intervention expanded the feminist critique to include race, class, and intersectionality, revealing how visual power operates differently across identity positions. In recent decades, feminist media critiques have shifted toward analyzing how the "male gaze" has evolved, not disappeared, in contemporary media forms, especially under the influence of post-feminist ideologies. Gill (2007; 2008) is a key figure in articulating how post-feminism does not reject the sexualization and objectification of women, but rather repackages them as forms of female empowerment. Gill (2007; 2008) introduces the concept of a "post-feminist sensibility," which normalizes the idea that women are now free agents who willingly choose to participate in practices of beautification, sexual display, and consumerism. The traditional male gaze is thus updated, masked behind narratives of empowerment and self-expression. This ideological transformation is particularly evident in advertising and popular culture, where women are depicted as confident, knowing subjects of their own sexual allure. Campaigns feature female figures who "choose" to be looked at, to be glamorous, to dominate the gaze. However, as Gill (2007) argues, this supposed agency is deeply conflicted, it exists within highly commercial, aestheticized boundaries that still prioritize youth, slimness, whiteness, and conventional beauty standards. Rather than dismantling the gaze, post-feminist media reshapes it in more insidious, market-compatible forms.

Angela McRobbie (2009) further develops this critique by noting that post-feminist culture invites women to believe they have achieved gender equality and can now focus on "choice," "pleasure," and "success." Yet these invitations often serve to deflect attention from systemic inequalities. Female empowerment becomes a brand identity, stripped of political content and reoriented toward consumption. A woman is not empowered by resisting visual codes, but by mastering them, performing them beautifully, and profiting from them—on social media, in branding, in lifestyle media. Jessalynn Keller and Jessica Ringrose (2015) expand on this by analyzing "selfie culture" as an aesthetic regime. They argue that the selfie is often framed as a site of feminist self-representation, but in practice tends to reinforce hyper-feminine, heteronormative visual tropes. The lighting, angles, and facial expressions in selfies mirror conventional beauty photography, even as the framing appears self-directed. Thus, empowerment becomes performative and deeply constrained by algorithmic economies of visibility.

Feminist media theorists have long emphasized that visual representations of women are not only shaped by narrative content, but also by the technical grammar of visual storytelling. Cinematic and photographic techniques such as camera angles, lighting, framing, and editing play a critical role in how

gender is visually constructed and ideologically positioned. The technical language of the visual medium itself often participates in gendered hierarchies of power, privilege, and desirability (Kaplan, 1983). Camera angles are particularly significant in reinforcing hierarchical relations. Low-angle shots tend to convey dominance and authority, which are visual codes frequently associated with male characters. In contrast, high-angle shots, especially when used on female subjects, can convey vulnerability, delicacy, or submission. Women are often framed from a slightly elevated perspective, subtly diminishing their spatial presence while emphasizing their physical traits such as legs, breasts, waistline, through objectifying close-ups. These visual tropes reinforce the fragmentation of the female body, an effect first explored by Mulvey (1975) and later expanded by Gamman and Marshment (1988), who argued that female bodies are not merely seen but dissected by the camera. Light, too, is an ideological tool. Feminist film theory identifies the use of “soft lighting” as a technique that romanticizes and beautifies the female face and body, often to the point of erasure, blemishes are removed, skin appears glossy, features are “feminized.” This soft-focus aesthetic contributes to the myth of the perfect woman: beautiful, effortless, and eternally youthful. By contrast, male characters are often lit in harder, sharper ways that emphasize ruggedness, realism, and texture aligning with hegemonic masculine ideals of authenticity and strength (Tasker, 1993). Framing and editing also serve ideological functions. Women are more frequently subjected to close-ups, especially of eyes, lips, and other facial features which emphasize emotional legibility and sexual availability. Men, by contrast, are often framed in medium or long shots, establishing physical presence, spatial control, and narrative authority. These decisions are rarely neutral; they establish power dynamics in ways that align with broader cultural assumptions about gender roles (Gamman & Marshment, 1988). Even in seemingly progressive or empowering representations, these visual strategies often persist. The strong female protagonist may still be lit seductively, shot in slow motion, or framed from behind in a tracking shot that invites voyeurism. As Gill (2008) and Winch (2013) argue, the post-feminist visual field does not reject objectification, it rebrands it. The “empowered” woman is still beautiful, composed, and camera-aware. She plays to the gaze, but now, it is implied that the gaze is hers. Yet the technical grammar of the visual still encodes her as spectacle, not subject.

Feminist media theory equips viewers to read beyond the surface of representation, to interrogate how images are constructed, circulated, and naturalized. These insights are crucial for understanding gendered representation in advertising, especially within “femvertising” campaigns that claim to subvert traditional stereotypes. Thus, the gendered gaze remains—not despite empowerment rhetoric, but often because of how empowerment itself is visually commodified.

2.2. Women in Advertising

Traditional Gender Stereotypes in Advertising

Advertising has long served as a powerful ideological apparatus that not only mirrors but also actively constructs gender norms. Within this medium, women have historically been portrayed through reductive stereotypes that reflect patriarchal expectations. These portrayals are not incidental but structurally embedded in advertising's visual and discursive grammar (Goffman, 1979; Gill, 2007). It is possible to see how advertisements position women as passive subjects defined by their relational roles to men or to products. Goffman's (1979) influential analysis of gender display revealed a consistent pattern: women were shown lying down, gazing off-camera, touching themselves delicately, or posed in childlike stances—symbolizing vulnerability, dependence, and submission. These visual cues operated as “hyper-ritualized displays” that encoded femininity as decorative, deferential, and emotionally expressive. Subsequent studies reinforced Goffman's findings. Kang (1997), in a cross-cultural analysis, noted that women were overwhelmingly represented in domestic settings and were more likely than men to be shown engaging in beauty or household-related activities. Similarly later, Lindner (2004) found that in fashion advertising, women were consistently sexualized and objectified, even when the product being sold was unrelated to beauty. While advertising strategies vary across cultural contexts, traditional gender roles appear remarkably stable across global markets. A meta-analysis by Eisend (2010), found that stereotypical depictions of women, particularly as homemakers or decorative elements, remained consistent across time and cultures. In many regions, including parts of Asia, Latin America, and Eastern Europe, women continue to be predominantly portrayed in domestic roles, often associated with caregiving, cooking, and personal care (Milner & Higgs, 2004; Paek, Nelson, & Vilela, 2011). These representations not only reinforce narrow conceptions of womanhood but also contribute to a cultural climate in which women's social value is linked to appearance and nurturing capacities. The dominance of such imagery reproduces what Butler (1990) would describe as the performative repetition of gender norms, acts that congeal into what appears to be natural or inherent femininity.

Stereotypical portrayals of women are especially prevalent in specific advertising sectors. Cleaning products, food and beverage, beauty and personal care remain the most gendered domains. Zayer and Coleman (2015) argue that advertising in these sectors reaffirms traditional roles by consistently showing women as caretakers of family well-being. In contrast, sectors like technology, automotive, and finance tend to underrepresent women or frame them as novices compared to male counterparts (Eisend, 2019). This division is not accidental but reflects broader market assumptions about gendered consumer behavior. These assumptions become circular: media representations shape consumer expectations, which in turn shape advertising strategies.

Femvertising: A Shift in Narrative?

The term femvertising, marks a notable discursive shift in how women are represented in advertising. Combining “feminism” and “advertising,” femvertising refers to commercial campaigns that explicitly adopt feminist rhetoric, imagery, and values, most notably empowerment, self-confidence, and female agency (Drake, 2017). However, critical literature questions the extent to which this shift signals real ideological change or simply reflects the commodification of feminist ideals.

Seminal examples of femvertising include Dove’s Real Beauty campaign, Always’ #LikeAGirl, and Nike’s “Dream Crazy”, all of which use narratives of resilience, diversity, and self-love to market products. These campaigns often challenge stereotypical images of women and aim to redefine cultural ideals of beauty and strength. According to Gill & Elias (2014), this represents a move from objectification to subjectification where women are no longer simply to-be-looked-at but are invited to look back, to speak, and to act. Brands no longer market to a passive female gaze but to an “empowered consumer”, one who sees herself as assertive, confident, and self-determined. Yet this empowerment is not political in the traditional feminist sense; it is personalized, individualized, and commodified. Lazar (2009) refers to this as “cosmetic empowerment,” where confidence is sold as a product, often quite literally through skincare, activewear, or hygiene items. This shift is underpinned by what McRobbie (2009) and Gill (2008) call post-feminist sensibility—a discourse that assumes the goals of feminism have largely been achieved and that women are now free to focus on personal development and lifestyle. In this framework, self-care replaces collective struggle, and choice becomes the ultimate feminist act. The female consumer is invited to “choose” to feel powerful, beautiful, and successful by consuming the right products.

Critical Reflections on Femvertising

Femvertising has been subject to significant feminist critique—particularly for offering a surface-level version of empowerment that often prioritizes aesthetics over substance. Scholars such as Gill (2008), McRobbie (2009), and Banet-Weiser (2018) argue that femvertising represents a new stage in the commodification of feminism, where empowerment is marketed not as collective resistance, but as a feeling, a lifestyle, or a product choice. This critique centers on the idea of “choice feminism”, in which personal decisions—what to wear, what to buy, how to present oneself are interpreted as inherently feminist acts. In this model, feminism becomes detached from structural critique and redefined as self-expression. As McRobbie (2009) notes, such frameworks obscure continuing gender inequalities by framing women as already liberated, empowered, and in control of their destinies. Advertising thus reinforces a neoliberal logic: inequality is no longer a social issue but a personal challenge, solvable through consumption and positivity.

Campaigns like Pantene’s “Shine Strong” or CoverGirl’s “I Am What I Make Up” celebrate women’s inner strength and beauty, yet often frame that strength within narrow, appearance-focused ideals. Gill

(2008) identifies this as a “midriff sensibility”, a post-feminist aesthetic in which women are empowered through self-surveillance, bodily control, and sexual appeal. Empowerment is repackaged in seductive terms: be bold, be beautiful, be confident, just not too disruptive. “Commodity feminism,” a term first introduced by Robert Goldman, Deborah Heath, and Sharon L. Smith (1991), refers to the appropriation of feminist ideas and aesthetics by commercial culture, often stripping them of their political content. The concept was later expanded and deepened by Sarah Banet-Weiser (2018) in her work “Empowered: Popular Feminism and Popular Misogyny”, where she critically explores how feminism has been transformed into a marketable identity within neoliberal consumer culture. The term describes how brands adopt feminist values for commercial purposes while neutralizing their political edge. Femvertising fits squarely within this logic. The rhetoric of social justice is employed as a marketing tactic, hollowed out of collective struggle, and transformed into brand loyalty. Feminism becomes trendy, a mood, an aesthetic, a hashtag (#GirlBoss, #Empowerment, #FeministAF), rather than a call for material or institutional change. In this context, feminist language is depoliticized and redirected toward consumer action. Rather than organizing or agitating, women are invited to buy into empowerment, literally. Gill and Elias (2014) describe this phenomenon as “confidence culture,” wherein women are told that their self-esteem is the key to success, and that any lack of confidence can be overcome through consumption. Here, the solution to patriarchal oppression is not resistance, but rebranding the self. This logic mirrors broader neoliberal ideologies: the empowered woman is responsible for her own advancement, wellness, and happiness. She must manage her emotions, control her body, and optimize her lifestyle—all while remaining aspirational, relatable, and camera-ready.

Femvertising’s greatest tension lies in its contradiction, it appears to challenge norms while simultaneously reinforcing them. While brands increasingly feature diverse body types, ethnicities, and age groups, these representations often remain within sanitized, non-threatening frames. Non-normative groups such as disabled, older individuals are underrepresented. When present, they are frequently styled to match dominant aesthetic values, thus reintegrated into the beauty economy. In this way, inclusion does not always disrupt the visual order; it can instead assimilate difference into the same old script of consumable femininity (Gill, 2016). Even the figure of the “empowered woman” is paradoxical: she is assertive but not aggressive, confident but not threatening, visible but not disruptive. Femvertising thus operates through controlled disruption, it gives the illusion of progress while preserving market stability. As Winch (2013) argues, the “girlfriend gaze” creates a safe space where empowerment feels warm and familiar, never radical or confrontational.

Femvertising walks a fine line between possibility and appropriation. On one hand, it opens space for feminist messages in mainstream media and affirms women as complex, powerful subjects. On the other, it often neutralizes feminism by aligning it with market imperatives and self-disciplining norms. The critical literature converges on a key point: femvertising cannot be dismissed entirely, but it must be approached with skepticism.

2.3. Contextual Framework: Women and Media in Türkiye

Understanding the operation of femvertising in Türkiye requires situating it within the broader cultural and ideological landscape of Turkish media. Representations of women in media are shaped by a complex interplay of historical, institutional, and symbolic forces, ranging from the structure of media ownership to the socio-political tensions between modernity and tradition.

Studies on Gender Representation in Turkish Media

Gender representation in media plays a crucial role in shaping and reinforcing societal norms, roles, and expectations. In Türkiye, similar to many other sociocultural contexts, media serves not only as a mirror of prevailing ideologies but also as a powerful tool in the reproduction of traditional gender roles. While some progressive strides have been made, particularly in television advertising through the emergence of femvertising, the bulk of Turkish media content remains grounded in patriarchal and conservative frameworks (Arslan, 2015; Aktaş, 2020).

Studies on TV series (Şakrak, 2020; Aktaş, 2020; Gürer & Gürer, 2020; Ünlü & Aslan, 2016) show that female characters are depicted primarily as mothers, wives, or objects of desire, while male characters are presented as breadwinners, protectors, or authority figures. Even when women are shown as career-oriented, they are often portrayed as lacking in education or skills, reinforcing the primacy of domesticity (Şakrak, 2020; Aktaş, 2020; Gürer & Gürer, 2020). For instance, although the series “Muhteşem Yüzyıl” features strong and influential female characters, it ultimately reinforces patriarchal dominance, allowing empowerment and misogyny to coexist within the same narrative (Zorlu, 2022). Aktaş (2020) and Şakrak (2020) both highlighted the prevalence of traditional gender roles in TV series, with women depicted as caregivers and men as breadwinners or decision-makers. According to Şakrak (2020), television series reinforce patriarchal gender roles by strengthening the perception that women need men in order to be “complete.”

While the overall trend is the persistence of traditional roles, some studies noted emerging, though limited, progressive representations. Akçalı and İnceoğlu (2020) identified a few series (“Kalbimdeki Deniz”) that depict women as independent and equal partners, though these are exceptions. Bikiç and Ercan (2019) contrasted the patriarchal “Paramparça” with “Medcezir,” which offered alternative female characters not judged for their sexuality or motherhood. Yarimoglu (2022) documented the rise of “femvertising” (advertising with pro-female empowerment messages) in Turkish TV ads, but found that only 28 out of 189 advertisements included empowerment activities, indicating the limited reach of such progressive shifts.

The ideological underpinnings of gender representation were consistently identified as patriarchal and conservative, with media serving as a mechanism for reinforcing existing social hierarchies. Multiple studies (Orta, 2013; Tanrıöver et al., 2009) explicitly connected media portrayals to broader sociopolitical and cultural contexts, including the influence of religious conservatism and the role of

media in shaping and reflecting societal norms. The absence of marginalized group representations was noted as a reflection of broader societal exclusion (Akçalı and İnceoğlu, 2020).

The evidence base on gender representation in Turkish media is well-represented for television, with consistent findings of traditional gender role perpetuation, underrepresentation of women in leadership or professional roles, and the dominance of patriarchal and conservative ideological frameworks. Although most studies focused on television, Tanrıöver et al. (2009) provided evidence that sexist discourse and underrepresentation of women are pervasive across print, radio, television, and digital media. Women are underrepresented in news media (21% of front-page news), and when present, are often objectified or depicted in stereotypical roles. The lack of studies on cinema and digital/social media is a notable limitation, restricting the generalizability of findings across all Turkish media forms. Quantitative studies, particularly those with larger sample sizes (Arslan, 2015), confirmed the prevalence of stereotypes. Qualitative analyses provided critical insights into the mechanisms and sociocultural underpinnings of these portrayals.

Advertising à la Turca

Turkish advertisements consistently reflect longstanding cultural values and gender norms. Studies report that television commercials generally depict women in domestic roles and men in public or authoritative positions (Yarimoglu, 2022). Visual and verbal strategies, including emotional appeals and familiar narrative cues, tend to reinforce conventional consumer behaviors while occasionally introducing hybrid or progressive elements.

Çankaya (2013) observed that commercials overwhelmingly depict women in conventional domestic roles while reinforcing the existing gender ideology. This persistent portrayal is further confirmed by Yarimoglu (2022), who documented that among 189 advertisements, only 28 featured any elements of femvertising—pro-female empowerment themes—with women largely appearing in passive roles. Arslan’s (2015) analysis shows that age intersects with gender representation: younger women are more likely to be confined to private, domestic spheres, whereas older and professional figures are often male. Sanay and Şener (2021) reported that while some progressive depiction of women emerged in advertising by 2014, those instantiates remained marginal, with traditional gender roles continuing to dominate. Moreover, Özbek and Toker (2021) emphasized the symbolic marginalization of “others”—women and minority groups—while white male figures maintained dominance. Mustafa and Ozay (2022) critiqued the influence of postfeminist and neoliberal discourses, which, despite claiming to empower women, actually reconstruct hegemonic femininity and reproduce class stratifications. Livberber and Kılınç (2023) affirmed that while the cosmetic brand Elidor attempts to challenge stereotypes through femvertising, it simultaneously establishes new norms rather than subverting old ones. Karamullaoglu and Sandikci (2019) documented that Westernized visual styles coexist with representations that emphasize caregiving, beauty, and subordinate gender roles in women.

Advertising strategies in Türkiye also serve as vehicles for cultural storytelling and identity conveyance. Yücel (2019) noted that advertisements craft an image of the “Turkish being” through symbols, myths, and entrenched stereotypes. Taşdelen and Erdoğan (2019) found that multinational brands, such as Coca-Cola in its Ramadan campaigns, integrate religious and cultural imagery—mosques, drummers, and other traditional signifiers—to localize their messages and foster emotional resonance. Despite these culturally grounded efforts, Özbek and Toker (2021) cautioned that such campaigns often reflect a conservative, hegemonic cultural orientation, marginalizing minority groups. Karamullaoglu and Sandikci (2019) documented strategic hybridization, wherein Western stylistic and thematic elements are localized to fit Turkish cultural contexts.

Scholars also highlight how advertising in Türkiye relies heavily on visual and verbal conventions to sustain dominant ideologies. Çankaya (2013) described the use of traditional models and long-standing narrative strategies as tools for maintaining existing societal norms. Taşdelen and Erdoğan (2019) underscored the deliberate use of religious and cultural symbols in commercials aimed at generating positive cultural associations and emotional engagement.

More recent analyses focus on affective branding. Livberber and Kılınç (2023) observed that Elidor’s marketing mix emphasizes emotional connection, authenticity, and empowerment, hallmarks of a more emotionally oriented femvertising approach. Nonetheless, these strategies, although innovative, operate within a commercially restricted framework. Karamullaoglu and Sandikci (2019) noted that while Westernized compositional and aesthetic standards are increasingly evident, the themes remain anchored in representations of family, beauty, and caregiving.

Collectively, the literature demonstrates that Turkish advertising consistently reflects and reinforces deeply rooted cultural values and gender norms. Women remain largely confined to domestic roles, while men are positioned as public or authoritative figures; only a small fraction incorporate empowering elements (Yarimoglu, 2022). Though hybridization with Western aesthetics and emotional appeals such as those in Ramadan campaigns, suggests a degree of modernization, the core of advertising remains grounded in traditional symbolism, consumer conventions, and gendered expectations. While some ads hint at transformation through selective use of femvertising and cultural hybridity, substantive change is limited. These patterns indicate that advertising practices in Türkiye not only reflect cultural continuity but also function as arenas in which cultural values and gender ideologies are reaffirmed, negotiated, and sometimes subtly reshaped.

CHAPTER THREE: METHODOLOGY

Research Aim and Significance

The primary aim of this research is to examine how the figure of the “strong woman” is represented across different sectors within femvertising campaigns broadcast in Türkiye. While academic interest in feminist-oriented advertising has grown in recent years, most existing studies tend to focus on specific brands, campaigns, or sectors. However, femvertising is no longer confined to isolated cases but has evolved into a widespread marketing strategy adopted by numerous industries and companies. This study seeks to address a thematic and sectoral gap in the literature by offering a comparative analysis across multiple sectors.

The significance of this research lies not only in its contribution to contemporary gender representations in media but also in its ability to uncover the ideological and symbolic mechanisms at play within advertising discourse. Advertisements are not merely marketing tools but also cultural texts that reproduce normative values. In this context, central to this study are the questions of how the image of the “strong woman” is constructed, what ideological codes underpin these representations, and how they vary across sectors. By exploring these issues, the study offers an interdisciplinary contribution to both media sociology and gender studies.

Research Approach and Theoretical Framework

This study is situated within the qualitative research tradition and shaped by interpretivist and critical paradigms. Qualitative inquiry aims to understand social phenomena within their contextual meaning structures, which aligns directly with the objectives of this research. Advertisements are not neutral texts but are embedded with symbolic, cultural, and ideological meanings. For this reason, a methodology sensitive to meaning-making, representational forms, and discursive power structures has been adopted. Accordingly, the primary method of this study is qualitative content analysis. This method is particularly suited for feminist media research as it allows for the in-depth interpretation of intertextual relationships, visual-verbal indicators, and underlying discourses (Krippendorff, 2018; Mayring, 2014). It provides a systematic yet flexible structure for analyzing data based on pre-defined theoretical codes. The choice of qualitative content analysis is justified by the interpretive nature of the theoretical approaches employed—namely, social constructivism, gender performativity, and feminist media theory—which necessitate a meaning-focused, multi-layered mode of inquiry.

The theoretical framework of the study draws upon three major approaches:

1. Social Constructivism – This theory posits that gender is not an inherent biological trait but a socially and historically constructed identity, and media plays a central role in this process (Berger & Luckmann, 1966).
2. Feminist Media Theory – This perspective critiques the objectification of women in media through the male gaze and explores how discourses of empowerment are often commodified within consumer culture. Foundational theorists include Laura Mulvey (1975) and Rosalind Gill (2007), among others.
3. Gender Performativity – Based on Judith Butler’s (1990) work, this approach examines how gender identities are constituted through repeated social performances. The representations of womanhood in femvertising are analyzed through this performative lens.

These theories not only inform the textual analysis of advertisements but also guide the construction of the coding framework and the logic of sectoral comparison. Thus, a strong methodological-theoretical coherence has been established throughout the research design.

Gender performativity, feminist media theory, and social constructivism were not applied in isolation but rather engaged as overlapping, intersecting lenses that shaped a multidimensional reading of the advertisements. Social constructivism provided the foundation for understanding how strong womanhood is not simply an individual trait, but a culturally and socially constructed image shaped by spatial context, social roles, and normative expectations. The placement of women in particular spaces, their class positioning, and their alignment or resistance to dominant norms were analyzed through this lens. Feminist media theory made it possible to explore how empowerment discourse is visualized, commodified, or diluted; how women are objectified or fragmented and how postfeminist contradictions are embedded in supposedly liberatory imagery. Gender performativity theory contributed a lens to examine how womanhood is enacted through repeated stylized acts including gesture, dress, and bodily presence, and how such performances are naturalized through visual repetition.

These three approaches functioned not as isolated tools, but as an integrated framework that enabled the researcher to examine how strength is not only shown, but also aestheticized and ideologically shaped across different sectors. This theoretical triangulation helped reveal both the micro-level visual cues and the macro-level discursive formations underlying femvertising campaigns. As such, the analysis remained attentive not only to content, but also to the ideological systems that structure how strong women are imagined, branded, and performed.

Data Collection Process and Sampling Strategy

The dataset of this study consists exclusively of Turkish-language strong women focused ads (femvertising) published on the YouTube platform in which the words “güç” (power) or “güçlü” (strong) are verbally articulated within the advertisement’s script. The data collection process was initiated using the keyword “güçlü kadın reklam” (strong woman advertisement), followed by the inclusion of thematically similar videos recommended by YouTube’s algorithm. The search was concluded once the algorithm began to suggest repetitive content, indicating that theoretical saturation had been reached. YouTube was selected as the sole platform due to its wide accessibility, rich public archive, and availability of metadata such as upload date, title, and description, which facilitated systematic documentation and verification of sources.

In the initial stage, a total of 79 advertisements were collected. Of these, only those that thematically referenced women’s empowerment and included a verbal mention of “güç” or “güçlü” were deemed eligible. After applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria, a total of 51 advertisements were retained as the sampling universe. These criteria included the requirement that the keywords be spoken, rather than merely displayed visually or in the title, as verbal articulation introduces an additional layer of meaning through tone, emphasis, and contextual delivery. Furthermore, only advertisements from commercial brands were included to ensure alignment with the market-oriented nature of femvertising. Public sector or NGO campaigns, which are often non-commercial in intent, were excluded for analytical coherence.

From this universe of 51 ads, 19 advertisements, one from each sector, were purposively selected for in-depth analysis. This sampling strategy ensured both thematic variation and sectoral representation. In cases where more than one ad was eligible within a single sector, a randomized selection process using was applied to prevent bias and maintain balance across industries.

Each selected advertisement was cataloged with key metadata including brand name, sector, video title, upload date, and descriptive notes, to ensure traceability and analytical transparency.

The final sample spans 19 sectors categorized under 8 broader industry groups, each represented by selected brands. The Beauty & Personal Care group includes advertisements from Pantene, L’Oréal, and Remove, covering subcategories such as Hair Care, Cosmetics, and Personal Care. The Finance & Insurance group is represented by campaigns from Türkiye İş Bankası (Banking and Finance) and AXA Sigorta (Insurance and Financial Services). The Food group includes Lezita (Food Production) and Domino’s Pizza (Fast Food), while Automotive & Mobility are covered by Mercedes (Automotive) and Corendon Airlines (Aviation and Tourism). The Fashion is represented by Nocturne (Fashion) and Trendyol (E-commerce), reflecting a mix of fashion and digital retail. The Technology & Telecommunications group includes Vodafone (Telecommunications) and Yandex Türkiye (Technology and Digital Services). The Home & Domestic Industries group features Yurtbay Seramik (Ceramics and

Building Materials), Beko (Household & Everyday Consumer Goods) and Atia Interiors (Furniture, Interiors, Home Textiles) spanning appliances, ceramics, and furniture. Finally, the Industrial & Agricultural Sectors group include Syngenta (Agricultural Science and Crop Protection), Cengiz Holding (Multi-sector Industrial and Service), and Opet (Energy), with the latter being particularly prominent due to its 19 advertisements under the “Kadın Gücü” (Women’s Power) campaign. This comprehensive distribution ensures not only discursive diversity but also enables a comparative exploration of how the notion of female strength is constructed, commodified, and negotiated across distinct industrial domains.

Due to YouTube’s algorithmic personalization, initial searches were conducted in incognito mode to minimize personalized biases in search results. However, given that incognito mode disables history-based recommendations, it limited the algorithm’s ability to generate suggestion-based saturation. Therefore, after completing the initial round of keyword-based sampling in incognito mode, the researcher temporarily switched to standard browsing mode to observe algorithm-generated suggestions. This two-step approach allowed for both a neutral starting point and a more organic exploration of related content, facilitating thematic saturation.

Coding Strategy and Analytical Process

This study employed qualitative content analysis to examine how representations of strong women are constructed and differentiated across femvertising campaigns in Türkiye. This method allows for the interpretation of not only what is communicated, but also how meanings are constructed through symbolic, visual, and discursive strategies. Aligned with feminist media research, this approach emphasizes multi-layered meaning-making through visual and auditory elements. The analysis extended beyond surface-level messages to include symbolic, aesthetic, and ideological structures. Each advertisement was examined through the interplay between visual scenes and verbal expression, revealing the underlying networks of meaning.

The coding process was conducted manually by the researcher, a decision justified by the level of interpretive sensitivity required to analyze visual and verbal cues, as well as the strong structure offered by the theoretical framework. The codes were directly derived from the study’s three theoretical foundations—gender performativity, feminist media theory, and social constructivism. Rather than employing a rigid or hierarchical system, the process was guided by theoretical intersectionality, enabling a flexible and integrative approach.

Codes grounded in gender performativity theory focused on how femininity is enacted through repeated gestures, stylistic elements, and camera performance. These included: body language and positioning, clothing and style performance, disruption of gender performance, staging and on-screen presence, and repetition and performed femininity. Feminist media theory informed the development of codes

addressing empowerment discourse, objectification, ideological contradiction, and collective representation. These included: position of female representation, visual objectification/male gaze, empowerment discourse, slogan and discourse analysis, female solidarity, and postfeminist contradiction. Codes derived from social constructivism focused on how gender is shaped by socio-cultural and spatial norms, including: gender role, spatial positioning, temporal and situational context, conformity or resistance to norms, constructed image of the strong woman, and class/status representation.

The application of theoretical codes revealed distinct sectoral patterns in the portrayal of empowered femininity. For example, in Beauty & Personal Care group campaigns such as those by L'Oréal and Pantene, codes from the gender performativity framework, particularly “body language and positioning” and “clothing and style performance”, were prominent, as women’s strength was often communicated through visual transformation and aesthetic confidence. In contrast, Finance & Insurance group advertisements like those by Türkiye İş Bankası and AXA Sigorta placed emphasis on “empowerment discourse” and “constructed image of the strong woman”, linking strength to themes of financial agency, leadership, and generational progress. In Fashion, brands such as Nocturne and Trendyol exhibited ambivalence: while Trendyol employed slogans celebrating female independence (“slogan and discourse analysis”), Nocturne also activated “visual objectification/male gaze” codes, creating tensions between empowerment and stylized femininity. This variation not only underscored the need for a multimodal and theoretically grounded analytical approach but also demonstrated how each sector draws on distinct symbolic resources to perform and package the image of the strong woman.

The coding process extended beyond thematic categorization to include multimodal analysis of visual-verbal interactions. Specifically, the verbal articulation of the words “güç” (power) and “güçlü” (strong) was analyzed in terms of tone, emphasis, affective delivery, and alignment with visual elements—offering a layered interpretation of how meaning is performed.

The overall analytical procedure followed five systematic stages. First, advertisements were retrieved from YouTube via keyword search and algorithmic suggestions, and key metadata were documented. Second, the sample was refined according to strict inclusion criteria, resulting in a final pool of 51 Turkish-language commercials that audibly featured the keywords and were produced by commercial brands. Third, these ads were categorized by sector and group, and one advertisement per sector was randomly selected, yielding a final sample of 19. Fourth, each ad was analyzed based on the theoretical codes, each ad group (intragroup analysis) was held. Fifth, a comparative analysis across sector groups (intergroup analysis) was conducted to identify recurring patterns, differences, and dominant narrative strategies in the portrayal of strong women.

While the codes provided a structured basis for analysis, not every advertisement included all codes. Code applicability varied depending on each ad’s thematic focus and narrative structure—reflecting the interpretive and flexible nature of qualitative research.

Limitations and Ethical Considerations

This study, while comprehensive in its theoretical and analytical scope, is not without limitations. First and foremost, the dataset is exclusively composed of Turkish-language advertisements retrieved from the YouTube platform. This medium was selected due to its open access, archival continuity, and rich metadata. However, the platform’s algorithmic filtering and recommendation mechanisms, which vary based on user history and geographic location, may influence the visibility of certain advertisements, introducing a level of selection bias beyond the researcher’s control. Another limitation concerns the sampling strategy. While 51 advertisements were identified as eligible based on the study’s criteria, only 19 were selected, one per sector, for in-depth analysis. This sector-based selection was designed to enable comparative interpretation, but it inevitably reduced the internal diversity of discourses within each industry. Furthermore, the emphasis on the verbal articulation of “güç” or “güçlü” as an inclusion criterion, while theoretically justified to avoid interpretive ambiguity, has inevitably excluded potentially relevant advertisements where strength may be implied but not spoken. Similarly, the decision to exclude public sector and NGO campaigns was based on the commercial focus of femvertising discourse but also narrows the interpretive field by excluding non-market narratives of empowerment.

Among the 19 advertisements analyzed in this study, only the campaigns by Beko, Nocturne, Corendon Airlines, Mercedes-Benz, Remove, L’Oréal, and Pantene were released outside the context of International Women’s Day (March 8). The remaining 12 advertisements are directly tied to March 8 themes. This indicates that the sample is largely composed of content produced within a specific historical moment. Given that March 8 campaigns typically carry a celebratory, commemorative, and symbolic tone, it can be argued that these representations of gender do not reflect universal narratives, but rather situational and strategic portrayals. While this concentration may be considered a contextual limitation, it does not compromise the core aim of the study—namely, to conduct a comparative, sector-based analysis of how female empowerment is portrayed. On the contrary, examining representations specifically crafted for symbolic moments like March 8 provides an important framework for understanding how femvertising strategies are shaped by time- and context-dependent logics.

From an ethical standpoint, the study adheres to standards of academic integrity and media research ethics. All advertisements analyzed were publicly accessible, and no content was manipulated or altered. The researcher did not collect any personal data, nor was there any interaction with human subjects;

hence, formal ethical clearance was not required. Brand names and campaign identifiers have been used strictly for analytical purposes, with appropriate citation where applicable.

Researcher Positionality and Reflexivity

This study is shaped by a positionality grounded in both lived experience and academic engagement with gender dynamics in Türkiye. The interpretive approach adopted throughout the analysis reflects an awareness of how gender inequality is culturally produced, informed by extensive exposure to feminist theory, critical discourse analysis, and media critique. These intellectual foundations have guided the identification of power relations, aesthetic strategies, and the construction of normative femininity embedded within advertising narratives. Such a perspective may have resulted in heightened sensitivity to themes such as stereotyping, tokenism, and postfeminist contradictions. Rather than being regarded as a source of bias, this sensitivity is considered a form of theoretical attunement and analytical depth. The analysis was conducted with a commitment to both critical reflexivity and methodological rigor, ensuring a balance between conceptual insight and systematic evaluation. In this sense, the study not only presents an academic inquiry but also foregrounds the interdependence between feminist knowledge production and the positional context in which that knowledge is generated.

CHAPTER FOUR: ANALYSIS AND FINDINGS

4.1. BEAUTY & PERSONAL CARE: PRETTY BUT STRONG BUT PRETTY

L'Oréal | Fahriye Evcen Elseve Reklamı - Dökülmeyen, İçten Dışa Güçlü Saçlar

Sector: Cosmetics

YouTube link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=8RNFO71rYhc>

Auditory Transcript (Translated)

(Moderate-paced music begins.) Actress Fahriye Evcen: “To appear strong on the outside, you must be strong on the inside, too. Becoming an actress was my biggest dream. My first audition... That excitement, that stress... (The sound of a boxing bell rings; the music intensifies.) That’s when I discovered my inner strength and landed my first role. Acting and university at the same time... ‘No one can do it, and neither can you,’ they said. But I resisted until the very end. I grew even stronger, more resilient. I trusted the strength within me. You should trust yours too. Because real power comes from within. For you and for your hair. If you are strong inside, you are strong outside too.”

Visual Transcript

Figure 1: L'Oréal ad – Woman boxing

Figure 2: L'Oréal ad – Product pose

The advertisement opens with a screen featuring the brand’s name and slogan. In the background, Fahriye Evcen, is seen leaning against a table in front of a large window, gazing out at the view. Outside, a massive billboard displays an advertisement featuring her. She wears a black, form-fitting, knee-length dress; her long, styled hair is worn down. The camera first focuses on the billboard, then cuts to the scene of her looking outside. In this second shot, she is captured from the left-back diagonal at torso height, with her arms crossed and a proud smile on her face. In the next scene, a flashback begins with the title “2005 – Acting Auditions.” The actress is seated on a chair under a spotlight in a room. She is dressed in a simple black dress and pink high heels; her hair is tied in a ponytail. The camera slowly rotates around her at torso level. Her face appears anxious; a close-up shot follows, showing her touching

her head with worry. This scene transitions to her empowered present self: she now wears a pink top, her hair tied back, voluminous and shiny. She lifts her hands to her hair, fluffing it—emphasizing its thickness and health. In another interior scene, she is shown wearing boxing gloves and gear, facing the window light. The camera captures her from behind and from a low angle. Immediately after, she punches directly toward the camera wearing the same pink outfit and styled hair. Following a new flashback titled “2009 – University,” the word “RESIST” appears on-screen alongside a hair shot. Now in a dimly lit gym, she trains with a punching bag, wearing a pink sports tank top, tights, and gloves. The scene is lit only by natural light seeping through small windows; again, the camera captures her from below. A subsequent shot from behind focuses on her hair as it swings back. She then looks directly into the camera, portraying her strength through boxing gestures. Throughout this sequence, she is alternately shown in the black dress from the opening and in her athletic gear. In a final shot, she grasps her hair with both hands, highlighting its fullness and healthy appearance. As the advertisement concludes, it returns to the opening view scene. In the final shot, the actress looks straight into the camera while holding the product in one hand and striking a boxing pose. The camera is positioned at eye level, and the ad closes with the brand’s slogan.

Analysis

Social Constructivism

The commercial constructs changing representations of gender through various spaces and practices in the life cycle of the female actress Fahriye Evcen. Settings such as acting auditions, a university environment, a boxing gym, and domestic interiors collectively showcase the presence of a woman in both public and private spheres. Her clothing ranges from sophisticated items like a sleek black dress to athletic wear like leggings and a tank top. This stylistic diversity symbolizes middle-to-upper-class belonging and the preservation of feminine aesthetic norms, while also signaling the capacity to enter domains requiring resistance and discipline. The line “They said no one could do it, and neither could you. But I resisted.” highlights individual empowerment and defiance against societal norms. The commercial, therefore, attempts to dismantle traditional gender roles that assign passivity to women, inviting the viewer to rethink female identity.

Gender Performativity

The L’Oréal ad implies that strength comes from within and is merely reflected in the hair. In this sense, hair is not the source of empowerment but rather a symbolic manifestation of it. The shampoo is positioned not simply as a physical product, but as an external expression of an internal transformation. One does not become strong by using shampoo; rather, when you are strong, your hair becomes strong too—a stylized performance from the inside out. The commercial reflects Butler’s notion that “gender is an act”, showing that strength is constructed through repeated and embodied practices. Evcen’s

gestures—throwing punches, flipping her hair, placing her hands on her head to express inner tension—exhibit traces of a performative transformation. Especially in boxing scenes, the use of low-angle shots reinforces the visual portrayal of strength through the body. This aligns with the idea that gender is constructed through the repetition of bodily acts. The character’s performance of strength is supported not only through gesture but also by the camera’s positioning, revealing gender as a bodily and visual construct. Transitions between her black dress and pink sportswear aesthetically bridge femininity and resistance, directly reflecting Butler’s argument that gender emerges through repetitive acts that become internalized by the body over time. In this context, the advertisement constructs femininity not solely through beauty norms, but through lived experience and acts of resistance, aligning with a performative understanding of gender.

Feminist Media Theory

The representation of the woman shifts between objectification and subjectification. Initial scenes focus on idealized beauty—hair flipping, soft lighting, flawless skin—making them open to critique under the “male gaze” framework. However, the camera avoids fragmenting the female body into isolated parts (legs, lips) and instead offers more holistic, action-centered frames. The low-angle shots during boxing scenes portray the woman in a powerful and dominant position. This visual choice marks her as an active subject rather than a passive object, shifting the emphasis from exhibition to agency. Eye-level shots foster a sense of equality, while low angles align her with power. In line with notions like “non-sexist sexiness” or “repackaged empowerment,” the woman is portrayed as both beautiful and strong—even while boxing, the shine of her hair is highlighted. Though the message “strength comes from within” reinforces subjectivity, her constant gaze at the camera and pose-like positioning may reduce her to a visual object. The commercial thus attempts to subvert traditional femininity while risking its reproduction.

Turkish Context

The commercial aims to represent the rise of the modern woman in Türkiye. Spaces of individual achievement—university, profession, and sports—signal a move beyond traditional female roles, while the diction, clothing, and aesthetics position her within a middle-to-upper-class framework. Evcen’s narrative glorifies personal strength and achievement, with no mention of motherhood, morality, or family—placing the ad in subtle conflict with traditional Turkish gender discourses. Expressions like “resist” and “believe in your inner strength” foreground individualism, and the sports scenes and boxing metaphor create a space where women can respond to patriarchal power structures through their own bodies. Against the backdrop of frequently passive female portrayals in Turkish advertising, this commercial offers a counter-narrative of an active, decisive, and powerful woman.

Pantene | Saçlarımız böyle güçlüyken, biz daha güçlüyüz! #GösterSaçlarımızınGücünü

Sector: Hair Care

YouTube link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=OC15GCdkP-M>

Auditory Transcript (Translated)

Actress Demet Özdemir: “Our hair doesn’t just affect how we look, it also affects how we feel.” (Boxing sound effects enter.) World Champion and Olympic Medalist Boxer Buse Naz Çakıroğlu: “Every time I step into the ring, my hair is my shield, a part of my strength. Having beautiful hair is just as effective to me as winning.” Actress: “The new Pantene miracle serum, with its Pro-V formula, penetrates deep into each strand, making your hair three times stronger.” Demet and Buse Naz (together): “When my hair is this strong, so am I. You too, show the power of your hair!”

Visual Transcript

Figure 3: Pantene ad – Confident hair flip

Figure 4: Pantene ad –Buse Naz Çakıroğlu in athletic pose

The ad opens with a set scene featuring actress Demet Özdemir, captured from the waist up in a direct frontal shot. The camera first frames her from behind, highlighting her meticulously styled hair at the center of the shot. She then flips her hair dramatically and turns around to cast a striking gaze directly at the camera. This is followed by another waist-up shot from the front, and then a full-body shot of her walking toward the camera. She is wearing a black sleeveless blouse with an open neckline and black tailored trousers. The next frame captures her upper body from a rear diagonal angle as she maintains direct eye contact with the camera. This is followed by a scene where she flips her hair back confidently, chin raised and expression self-assured. In the second scene, Olympic medalist and world champion boxer Buse Naz Çakıroğlu appears in front of a boxing ring in the set. Her hair is tied up; she’s in athletic gear, looking down at the camera from a high angle with her hands on her hips. As the camera approaches this powerful figure, a series of scenes follow: putting on her gloves, adjusting her hair, jumping rope, and working the punching bag. These segments are mostly shot from a low angle, creating a strong point of the view. At the end of this sequence, she appears with her hair down, smiling at the camera, and flipping her hair. She then raises her chin, extends her arms wide, and leans back against the ring ropes in a defiant pose, with the camera again looking up at her from below. The following

scene features a product shot on screen. In the final sequence, the athlete first appears without makeup and with her hair tied up, looking directly at the camera while performing boxing moves that mimic attacking an opponent. Immediately afterward, within the same frame, she transforms: now with styled hair, earrings, radiant makeup, and a smiling face. In the closing shot, Demet Özdemir and Buse Naz Çakıroğlu stand side by side facing the camera. Captured from the waist up at eye level, they both place their hands on their waists and smile confidently at the viewer. The advertisement concludes with the product image on screen.

Analysis

Social Constructivism

This commercial reconstructs women's societal roles through scenes of athletic success and media visibility. Actress Demet Özdemir appears on a film set, while boxer Buse Naz Çakıroğlu demonstrates her physical strength in the ring in set. Together, they represent female empowerment through media and sports. Özdemir's elegant and assertive attire (black tank top, tailored trousers) conveys upper-middle-class aesthetics, while Çakıroğlu's athletic gear reflects a more active and functional female identity. Although both remain within normative gender expressions, they are portrayed as open to transformation. The line "With hair this strong, we are this strong" links aesthetic expectations of the female body to strength, reconfiguring traditional beauty narratives. The ad illustrates how female identity is socially constructed and open to redefinition.

Gender Performativity

Both Özdemir and Çakıroğlu's body language and gestures exemplify gender as a staged performance. Özdemir's hair flips, assertive gaze, and walk toward the camera reflect a theatrical display of traditional femininity. In contrast, Çakıroğlu's actions—punching, skipping rope, hitting a heavy bag—highlight the repetition of masculine-coded strength performances through a female body. By juxtaposing her makeup-free, aggressive persona with her styled and smiling self, the commercial makes visible the duality of gendered performance. Low-angle shots of Çakıroğlu reinforce strength, while Özdemir's dramatic styling blends beauty with power.

Feminist Media Theory

From a feminist media perspective, the commercial blends critique and empowerment. Özdemir's stylized, idealized appearance—smooth skin, visible makeup, perfect hair—invites "male gaze" interpretations. Yet her presence becomes more than aesthetic; she speaks and acts, challenging passive objectification. Aligned with "repackaged feminism," empowerment is aesthetically rendered: the woman is both beautiful and strong. Çakıroğlu's makeup-free scenes in the ring offer a more "authentic" portrayal of strength, but her later stylized appearance may commercialize that authenticity. The ring

scene is not a real match but a controlled set, suggesting her sporting identity is aestheticized for marketing. This reflects “commodity feminism,” where female strength is transformed into a marketable product. The focus is not on sweat or struggle, but on how attractively strength can be displayed. Rather than delivering a genuine empowerment message, the ad sells the aesthetics of empowerment—an issue central to feminist media critiques.

Turkish Context

The Pantene commercial offers a departure from traditional Turkish portrayals of women—there’s no focus on motherhood, family duties, or conservative values. Instead, it emphasizes individual success, physical strength, and self-confidence. While Çakıroğlu’s athlete identity aligns with state-sponsored female sports narratives, the ad softens this alignment by integrating aesthetic ideals. Women are positioned within the upper-middle class through clothing, diction, and lighting. The use of modern studio and boxing ring settings legitimizes women’s presence outside traditional spaces. In Türkiye’s media climate, this ad functions as a “silent revolution,” not directly opposing state narratives, but subtly surpassing their limitations. It marks a positive shift in the visibility of strong, successful women in Turkish advertising.

Remove | Hayatının Başrolünde Sen #YanımdaRemove

Sector: Personal Care

YouTube link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=zXYHSf8sl-8>

Auditory Transcript (Translated)

(Energetic music begins.) (Female voice-over) “There are smooth touches, not only changing your skin, but your energy. There are smooth sensations, guiding you toward your inner self, your dreams, your goals. There are smooth details, revealing your passion, your talent, your sparkle. Smooth moments, and with the strength taken from those moments, you take the lead role in your life, with Remove by your side.”

Visual Transcript

Figure 5: Remove ad – Being watched unknowingly

Figure 6: Remove ad – Applying hair removal to hairless arm

The advertisement opens with the brand logo on screen. In the first scene, a woman is seen sitting on a bed in a home setting, wearing a bathrobe and applying a wax strip to her leg. The camera cuts to a close-up of the leg being waxed. A gentle smile appears on the woman's face, and the next shot slowly moves from her smooth leg to the hand gently feeling it. In the next scene, a woman dressed in activewear, a crop top and leggings, appears upside down while performing a yoga pose. This is followed by a bathroom scene: a woman with a towel wrapped around her head and body, just stepping out of the shower, is filmed from a distance as if unaware. The camera then shifts to a close-up, capturing the moment she applies the product to her arm. The shot moves from her arm to her smiling face, directly facing the camera. The following scene focuses on a woman sitting at a design table, smiling as she creates fashion sketches. Then, another woman is shown waxing her upper lip hair while smiling. After that, a woman performing on stage is shown. The camera films her from below, as if from the audience's perspective. In the final scene, while three women are seen smiling and chatting together, the camera zooms in on the Remove brand products on the table in front of them, and the advertisement ends with a product shot.

Analysis

Social Constructivism

The commercial's spatial composition places women in homes, bathrooms, gyms, and on stage—suggesting that women can be subjects not only in private but also public domains. They are shown doing yoga, acting on stage, and producing fashion sketches, making them visible through productivity as well as bodily presence. However, this productivity is constructed around the theme of “smoothness”: through waxing, depilation, and product application, women construct both themselves and their success. The auditory message— “Smooth moments, and with the strength taken from those moments”—supports this notion. From a social constructivist perspective, the ad both reproduces traditional cleanliness and beauty practices and repositions them as gateways to individual success, offering a contemporary revision of normative gender roles.

Gender Performativity

The female characters are presented in scenes drawn from daily life but stylized to emphasize performance. Waxing, doing yoga, or performing on stage are not only actions but gendered performances embodied in “smooth” bodies. The upside-down yoga pose signals not just physical capability but control and flexibility. Bodily control is equated with self-esteem: smooth skin, and yoga-toned bodies are framed as the currency of empowerment. The stage actress is filmed from a low angle, evoking power. The camera repeats women’s poses, gestures, and gazes, reinforcing gender as a product of repeated acts. These stylized bodies turn gender into a set of behaviors rather than a biological fact. The link between style and strength resonates with the “confident woman” discourse.

Feminist Media Theory

Remove’s ad frequently employs fragmented visuals: in the waxing scenes, only legs are shown; during product application, just an arm. The face appears only near the end, aligning with the “male gaze” framework that fragments and aestheticizes the female body for a presumed male viewer. Soft lighting, flawless skin, and the absence of visible hair construct an idealized beauty standard. The complete omission of hair in scenes involving depilation suggests invisible norms governing what must not be shown. The female body is policed not only by how it should appear but by what must be concealed. Power here is not an experience but an aesthetic ideal emerging after the erasure of perceived flaws. Yet the ad attempts to subjectify this “well-groomed woman” by also presenting her as an actress or designer—visible not just for beauty, but talent. This representation, aligning with “non-sexist sexiness,” seeks to make women both desirable and strong, but still operates within patriarchal boundaries.

Turkish Context

Though the ad seems to support female agency and autonomy, these representations are deeply intertwined with Turkish gender norms. The aesthetic codes that construct a “well-groomed but strong” woman also conform to Türkiye’s conservative media climate. Sexuality is not explicitly represented, but bodily “perfection” is silently glorified. Social acceptance of women requires constant grooming framed as “self-care,” but this is masked by a layer of modesty. Empowerment is only acceptable insofar as it aligns with beauty norms. In a narrative where even body hair cannot be shown, the woman is not a liberated subject but one who quietly disciplines her body. Thus, Remove’s commercial reflects the tension between feminism and marketing in Türkiye: women are represented, but only in culturally permissible forms.

Beauty & Personal Care Intra-Group Analysis

The Beauty & Personal Care group includes advertisements from three key sub-sectors: Cosmetics (L'Oréal), Hair Care (Pantene), and Personal Care (Remove). These sectors have historically targeted female consumers and continue to be shaped by visual culture, idealized femininity, and commercialized empowerment narratives. In this section, the advertisements are analyzed to assess how the image of the “strong woman” is portrayed across different categories. While each brand promotes its own version of empowerment, a closer look at their visual and verbal strategies reveals both recurring patterns and sector-specific distinctions. Within the framework of femvertising, this group poses a crucial question: does female strength in the Beauty & Personal Care remain aestheticized, or does it push against the boundaries of traditional gender codes?

All three commercials deploy visual languages of strength and empowerment, yet do so through aestheticized and stylized femininity. In the Beauty and Personal Care sector group, bodily control is presented as an indicator of self-worth and empowerment; smooth skin, voluminous hair, and yoga-sculpted bodies are transformed into commercial symbols of strength. A central visual element repeated across all advertisements is the prominence of hair and skin as symbolic indicators of inner strength. In both L'Oréal and Pantene ads, the transformation or perfection of hair is not only a beauty ideal but a metaphor for personal empowerment. Similarly, in the Remove ad, smooth skin becomes the medium through which agency and confidence are narrated. From the perspective of gender performativity, the commercials highlight repeated bodily gestures such as hair flipping, punching, stretching, walking, waxing, which are not merely aesthetic choices, but as performative acts that construct femininity as an enacted identity. (Butler, 1990). These acts are not incidental but deliberately emphasized with cinematic techniques such as close-ups, slow motion, and low-angle shots. The repeated bodily gestures—ranging from flipping one's hair to throwing punches—are not merely aesthetic choices, but performative acts through which femininity is enacted. In both L'Oréal and Pantene, low-angle shots during boxing scenes assign women a position of physical dominance, visually linking power to the body. The Remove ad, though devoid of direct athleticism, features women in active yoga poses and stage performances, again associating control over the body with inner power. Across all three, post-feminist empowerment discourse is strongly present (Gill, 2007). Verbal expressions like “trust your inner strength,” “when my hair is strong, I am strong too,” and “take the lead role in your life” align with Gill's notion of commodified agency, where empowerment is simultaneously aestheticized and depoliticized. The message is clear: strength is something you achieve through consumption—of a serum, a wax strip, or a beauty routine. These commonalities suggest that femvertising within the beauty sector, regardless of product type, often constructs strength through visible bodily perfection. Empowerment is made pleasant through visual codes of elegance, cleanliness, and control—making strength beautiful, and beauty strong.

Despite their shared visual grammar, the three advertisements differ notably in how they frame the source and function of female strength. The L'Oréal commercial centers on individual struggle and career development, narrating actress Fahriye Evcen's rise through emotional tension and professional resistance. Here, strength is internal, linked to resilience and ambition, and reinforced by biographical storytelling. In contrast, Pantene's commercial offers a dual portrait of female power, blending celebrity femininity with athletic prowess. The juxtaposition of Demet Özdemir's cinematic glamour and Buse Naz Çakıroğlu's sporting discipline creates a hybrid model of empowerment that blends beauty with physical action. The association of female empowerment with physically demanding sport such as boxing, reveals a significant evolution in how brands construct the image of the "strong woman." In the 2017 advertisement by L'Oréal, actress Fahriye Evcen is depicted performing boxing movements. While the ad leverages the aesthetics of physical strength, its use of a celebrity rather than a professional athlete positions empowerment as a stylized performance rather than a lived reality. In contrast, the 2023 Pantene advertisement features world champion boxer Buse Naz Çakıroğlu. This shift from actor to athlete suggests a notable increase in authenticity and representational depth, framing strength not only as symbolic but as embodied and earned through discipline. This progression reflects a broader move in femvertising strategies—from performative gestures to more grounded portrayals of power. The use of an actual athlete enhances the credibility of the empowerment narrative and reconfigures the strong woman not as someone performing strength for the camera, but as someone whose body is genuinely shaped by effort, resilience, and mastery. In both cases, boxing functions as a visual metaphor for power; yet, while L'Oréal's version emphasizes controlled aesthetics, Pantene's version foregrounds lived experience, suggesting an increasing alignment between representation and reality in contemporary beauty advertising. Moreover, the duality of appearance in these ads—before/after shots, styled vs. no makeup—visually stages transformation as the core narrative, suggesting that strength can exist in multiple gendered expressions. Remove, on the other hand, focuses more on daily rituals and inner peace. Unlike the drama and spectacle of boxing or stage performance, Remove's tone is softer, its visuals more intimate. The ad links strength to wellness and emotional harmony, achieved through the act of grooming. However, it also presents the most fragmented visual representation of the female body, showing depilated legs, smooth arms, and makeup-free skin. This aligns with male gaze theory (Mulvey, 1975), wherein the body is still policed and fragmented—even within an empowerment discourse. Socioculturally, while L'Oréal and Pantene challenge traditional female roles by showing women in boxing gyms or career struggles, Remove remains more firmly rooted in conservative codes of femininity. Although it features women in public spaces (a stage, a design table), the emphasis on physical beauty as prerequisite for power subtly reproduces the logic it seeks to question. This reveals a class-based divide as well: L'Oréal and Pantene lean toward upper-middle-class urban women balancing professional and personal identities, while Remove appeals more to traditional respectability mediated through "clean" femininity.

Across the Beauty & Personal Care group, the recurring equation of strength with aesthetic refinement reveals a core contradiction within femvertising: while aiming to empower, these commercials often repackage traditional beauty standards as vehicles of power. Whether through resilient hair, flawless skin, or toned bodies, strength becomes visible only when it conforms to visual ideals. Yet, within this contradiction lies a subtle evolution—these ads bring athleticism, ambition, and inner voice into spaces traditionally occupied by passivity and silence. The nuanced distinctions between sectors—L’Oréal’s narrative of career perseverance, Pantene’s fusion of athleticism and glamour, and Remove’s smoothing rituals—prepare the ground for broader comparisons. When these narratives are placed next to femvertising in sectors such as finance, industry, or technology, it becomes possible to critically assess whether the rebranding of women’s strength truly challenges gender norms or merely refashions them for new markets.

4.2. FINANCE & INSURANCE: TERMS REWRITTEN

AXA Sigorta | AXA SİGORTA - #GÖRSÜNLER Kadınlar Günü Filmi

Sector: Insurance and Financial Services

YouTube link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=nH4n9EXTx_4

Auditory Transcript (Translated)

(Female voice-over) “Is life tough? Does it seem that way to you? Come ask me about that. Let them see. (Throughout the ad, the word ‘let them see’ is chanted collectively by multiple voices.) Let them see what time to get up in the morning and how I start the day. Let them see how to the look against their gaze. Let them see what it means to read, to write, to underline and how deep a love that is. Let them see how and where we dress, how we go out, let them look at us. Let them see who I talk to, how I talk, let them listen carefully. Let those who say ‘everything is about power’ look at us and see our strength. Let those who say ‘we’ll do it, you stay out of it’ come and see for themselves. Let. Them. See. Let them see. Let them see. Let them see. (On-screen text: A beautiful day to see. March 8, International Women’s Day.)

Visual Transcript

Figure 7: AXA Sigorta ad – Women with crossed arms

Figure 8: AXA Sigorta ad – Woman with headscarf

The advertisement opens with a scene featuring six women of varying hair types, body sizes, heights, and styles standing before the camera. The shot is filmed from a low angle; the women look directly into the lens with a defiant gaze, their arms folded firmly in front of them. The second scene shows a classically dressed woman retrieving heavy packages from her car in the evening darkness. With her hands full, she struggles to close the door with her foot. She is then seen walking away in a rear shot, carrying the load. Next, a young woman is jogging along the seaside in black and pink athletic wear. The camera first follows her from behind at head level, then captures her from the left side at body level. This is followed by a calm scene of a smiling woman starting her day at home. In the next shot, a woman in conservative clothing (headscarf) and sunglasses stands outside a store, looking down at the camera. Filmed from a low angle, this scene gives her posture a powerful visual impact. The scene changes to a woman seen in the driver's seat of a car, applying red lipstick using the rearview mirror. Next, another woman is shown in a corporate meeting setting, dressed in formal attire, from various angles. Finally, she appears in a shot from below, raising her chin slightly and staring boldly into the camera. In another scene, a fit, blonde woman in a tight red dress walks across a red-lit terrace with a view of Galata Tower. The camera follows her from behind. She suddenly turns around and looks straight into the camera. Then, a woman with glasses, casually dressed young woman of average build is seen looking at herself in the mirror. In the following shots, two middle-aged women wearing the same red dress smile at each other with approval, and two little girls lie down and giggle joyfully at one another. In the next series of scenes, the muscular upper body of a woman doing pull-ups in athletic gear and boxing gloves is highlighted from the back. The camera later captures her boxing in a dimly lit, enclosed space. After that, a young woman is shown chopping vegetables alongside a male chef in a professional kitchen. An image of a middle-aged, modestly dressed woman leaning against a taxi follows. Her driving scenes are also captured from the rearview mirror and the gearshift perspective inside the car. The advertisement closes with shots of the six women from the beginning dancing, again filmed from a low angle, looking directly and defiantly into the camera. In the final sequence, every woman who appeared throughout the ad is shown one by one, staring into the lens with determined, strong, and confident expressions.

Analysis

Social Constructivism

AXA Sigorta's #GÖRSÜNLER campaign makes female representations visible through diverse spaces and activities. Women are shown at home, in the office, inside vehicles, at the gym, on the street, and at the beach; performing tasks such as chopping vegetables, driving, exercising, or attending meetings. These varied portrayals support the idea that gender roles are socially constructed. The woman is depicted not only within the home but also as a powerful agent in public and physical spaces. The narration during sports scene "Let those who say everything is strength look at us and see our power" constructs a discourse that reverses normative definitions of femininity and challenges the association of womanhood with passivity. While the verbal narrative demands visibility for women, the visual narrative layers the social construction of female identity by including women from diverse class, physical, and cultural backgrounds.

Gender Performativity

During the ad, each articulation of "görsünler" functions not only as a call for visibility but also as a performative act that constructs the figure of the "strong woman" through linguistic recurrence. This discursive repetition actively participates in the social production of empowered femininity, transforming visibility itself into a mode of gendered self-performance. The women in the commercial re-enact gender's performative aspect through body language, posture, gestures, and spatial actions. Low-angle shots, upright stances, direct gazes into the camera, and "defiant" attitudes illustrate how gender is constructed through repetition. By repeating the same pose, the women transform their bodies into instruments of empowerment. Their differing appearances such as business suits, red dresses, workout clothes reveal that gender is not a singular performance but a spectrum of expressions. Especially, the focus on the muscular body of the woman boxing underscores that strength and discipline are not exclusively male traits; the female body can embody these symbols as well. Camera framing reinforces the subjectification of the female body: the body is not only visible, but active.

Feminist Media Theory

The ad attempts to portray women not only as aesthetic objects but also as active agents. Yet, scenes like the one focusing solely on a woman applying lipstick highlight a potential critique rooted in the "male gaze." While the campaign's core message is to portray strong women, that strength is at times intertwined with beauty, grace, and elegance. The woman in the red dress turning toward the camera or the driver applying lipstick recall representations of the "non-sexist but sexy" woman. Some women appear with flawless, made-up skin; others are natural and makeup-free. However, the prevalence of direct gazes and the presence of women of varying ages, bodies, and identities suggest that the ad frames women as not only the watched but also the watchers—challengers and agents of their own visibility.

Turkish Context

AXA's #GÖRSÜNLER commercial offers a compelling example of plurality in female representation within Türkiye. The inclusion of both veiled and unveiled women, as well as women exercising, cooking professionally, boxing, presenting in offices, or walking in red dresses, shifts the focus from a singular notion of womanhood to multiple states of femininity. While concepts like family, honor, and morality are not explicitly mentioned, the ad still diverges from traditional roles such as homemaking or motherhood, creating subtle tension with culturally embedded expectations. Elements like clothing and setting signal varying class affiliations, suggesting a broad target audience. Compared to state rhetoric, the ad promotes the visibility and agency of women using an inclusive rather than confrontational tone. Among femvertising examples in Türkiye, this ad stands out as a hybrid discourse—avoiding direct conflict with traditional values while emphasizing female subjecthood.

Türkiye İş Bankası | 8 Mart Dünya Kadınlar Günü

Sector: Banking and Finance

YouTube link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2khBj5zMlxY>

Auditory Transcript (Translated)

Woman 1: We've broken the chains both inside and out.²

Woman 2: We've shouted to the world: "We are here!"

Woman 3: And today, we still know how to create new things.

Woman 4: We are here, and the youth of Türkiye is here.

Woman 1: The things entrusted to our hearts as a legacy...

Woman 5: ...will find and have found their most unshakable foundation.

Woman 4: This is the voice of thousands of young people, rising as one.

Woman 6: We will not fall behind...

Woman 2: We will not stop on the road.

² Kayseri Textile Factory opening. Full video available at <https://filmmirasim.ktb.gov.tr/en/film/opening-of-the-kayseri-textile-factory-02>

Woman 4: We will keep running!

Woman 3: We will not be left behind.

Woman 1: We will reach the goal. Yes, we will reach the goal.

(Female voice-over) The women of this country draw their strength from the past and their courage from their belief in the future. Happy March 8, International Women’s Day.

Visual Transcript

Figure 9: Türkiye İş Bankası ad – Archival speech on stage Figure 10: Türkiye İş Bankası ad – Modern woman at podium

The ad opens with Woman 1, in archival footage from the 1935 opening ceremony of the Kayseri Textile Factory. The black-and-white footage reflects the era’s atmosphere. She is seen in full-body shot, facing the camera directly while addressing an enthusiastic crowd. Standing on an elevated platform, she delivers a powerful speech with expressive gestures. Woman 2 appears next, standing behind a podium in a modern conference room. She wears a formal blue blazer and a delicate necklace. Her hair is long and loose. As she speaks into the microphone, the camera shifts from a wide shot to a closer portrait view. Woman 3 is speaking outdoors, at a podium in a garden. The camera captures her from eye level. She is giving a speech in front of four people consisting of three women and one man listening to her speech, camera is behind the listeners. She is middle-aged, with medium-length, straight hair and a simple, formal top presenting a modest, professional appearance. Woman 4 wears a white blouse and a blue blazer evoking the brand’s blue-white color palette. She is young, with her hair neatly tied back, and no accessories. Her speech is filmed from a low angle, positioning the viewer as a member of the audience. The scene briefly returns to Woman 1, and then to Woman 5: she is young, dressed in a white shirt, and wears a lanyard with a name badge. Her naturally curly hair stands out. The camera is again positioned from below while her speech. Next, Woman 4 is shown again, now filmed from eye level. Then Woman 6 appears middle-aged, wearing a plain blue blouse, short hair, and a light scarf around her neck. She speaks while looking directly into the camera. Toward the end of the ad, Women 2, 4, 3, and 1 are each shown once more in close-up shots. They are seen being applauded or clapping themselves while addressing their respective audiences, the ad ends.

Analysis

Social Constructivism

This commercial reveals how gender roles are historically and culturally constructed through both visual and verbal narratives. The statement “The women of this country draw their strength from the past ...” defines female identity through cultural memory and a collective vision of the future. In this approach, women’s strength is presented as the product of a construction shaped by historical and societal values; thus, the discourse aligns with the core premise of social constructivist theory, which asserts that gender is produced within a specific cultural context. Women are mostly portrayed speaking in public spaces—on podiums, before microphones—as active agents. The appearance of Woman 1 at the opening of the Kayseri Textile Factory in 1935 recalls the historical role of women in Türkiye’s modernization, while contemporary scenes emphasize the continuity of this legacy. The women’s attire—blazers, plain blouses, elegant accessories—signals a middle-to-upper-class identity and suggests representation in professional domains. Phrases like “we’ve broken the chains within and without” legitimize women’s shift from traditional roles to public agency. The women’s speeches align with societal norms while subtly aiming to transform them, revealing that gender is not fixed but a structure that evolves historically.

Gender Performativity

Despite their diverse ages and appearances, the women in this ad perform a unified display of strength. Their upright posture, raised heads, and direct gazes communicate that power and confidence are not intrinsic to gender but are performed and socially validated. Low-angle shots position the women as power centers. Stylistically, their clothing—blue jackets, formal yet unembellished outfits—recodes traditionally male symbols of authority onto female bodies. These choices reflect that female identity is shaped not only physically but symbolically, creating a space where the body becomes a vessel for ideological positioning. Thus, the female body is not just a symbolic presence, but an ideological stance.

Feminist Media Theory

The commercial depicts women as political subjects rather than aesthetic or sexual objects. Their bodies are shown holistically, with no fetishization of specific parts (legs, lips, etc.). This appears to be a conscious strategy to avoid the “male gaze.” Lighting is natural and soft; faces are shown realistically without excessive idealization. Women are not glamorized but maintain realistic appearances. Lines like “we are here!” and “we will always run!” assert empowerment through historical awareness, intellect, and solidarity rather than beauty. The women communicate directly with the viewer, demanding not to be passively observed but actively seen. Thus, they are not just “looked at” but compel the gaze.

Turkish Context

This ad is a symbolic narrative linking Türkiye's modernization to female representation. The 1935 scene refers directly to early Republican gender policies, while modern depictions make this legacy visible and renewed. There is no mention of family, morality, or honor; instead, the focus is on social progress, equality, and national unity—secular values. Women are placed in podiums, halls, and gardens—spaces beyond the traditional domestic realm (kitchens, children's rooms). This positions the woman as a subject of the public, not the home. Their speech, dress, and accents reflect an urban, educated middle-upper class—clearly defining the target audience. Rather than opposing state narratives, the commercial embraces the Republican image of the woman, reproducing the values of the existing system. This femvertising example strategically aligns feminist representation with national ideology.

Finance & Insurance Intra-Group Analysis

The Finance & Insurance group comprises advertisements from two key sectors: insurance (AXA Sigorta) and banking (Türkiye İş Bankası). These sectors have historically maintained a masculine-coded public image, often associated with authority, stability, and rationality. In recent years, however, financial institutions have increasingly embraced femvertising strategies to broaden their appeal and engage in social discourse on gender equality.

Both commercials articulate female strength through public visibility and vocal agency. Here, the emphasis is placed on voice, language, and presence in public space. In both advertisements, women are portrayed as speakers—standing at podiums, addressing audiences, delivering messages—rather than as visual objects. This shift from image to voice represents a significant divergence from the aesthetic-based empowerment seen in many femvertising examples. From the lens of social constructivism, both ads deconstruct fixed gender roles by placing women in roles of authority and action. Whether delivering historical speeches (Türkiye İş Bankası) or performing physical and professional tasks (AXA), women are shown as producers of meaning, capable of transforming their environments. The public staging of women's work, sports, and speech acts reinforces the notion that gender is learned and enacted through experience and participation (Lorber, 1994). In terms of gender performativity, both ads showcase recurring bodily practices that construct strength: upright postures, direct gazes, low-angle shots, and confident hand gestures. These elements create a shared visual grammar of authority. The AXA ad, in particular, uses repetition—both verbal (“Let them see”) and visual (similar camera angles and poses)—to performatively build a collective female subjectivity. Türkiye İş Bankası complements this by threading historical imagery with modern action, portraying strength not as inherent but as inherited and rehearsed. From a feminist media theory perspective, both ads actively resist the male gaze (Mulvey, 1975). Women are filmed holistically, realistically, and with emotional restraint. There are no lingering shots on body parts, seductive lighting, or aestheticized glamor. The intention is clear: to reposition the

woman as a subject of history, politics, and public discourse. The camera often places the viewer in the position of the listener or subordinate, rather than the traditional gazer. As Rosalind Gill (2007) argues, this move toward female subjectification signals a shift from passive representation to self-authored presence.

Despite thematic harmony, the two commercials differ in their approaches to emotional tone, historical positioning, and symbolic strategy. Türkiye İş Bankası constructs its narrative around continuity and legacy, drawing a symbolic line from the early Republican period to today's female leaders. The use of archival footage and podium-centered visual positions women as agents of modernity and civic responsibility. The tone is formal, solemn, and nationalistic—reinforcing an image of strength rooted in institutional history and collective progress. By contrast, AXA's #GÖRSÜNLER campaign employs a more visceral and affective strategy. The repetition of the phrase “Let them see” becomes an emotional rallying cry. The ad highlights not only formal authority (e.g., office settings) but also informal strength: boxing, driving, dressing, cooking. It blends diverse aesthetics—headscarves, red dresses, bare skin, lipstick—without moral hierarchy. This pluralism suggests a fluid, decentralized notion of strength, as opposed to İş Bankası's unified and ideologically framed narrative. In terms of visual coding, Türkiye İş Bankası avoids all physical markers of traditional femininity (makeup, fashion, hair styling), presenting women in plain suits with minimal ornamentation. AXA, on the other hand, walks a fine line between non-sexist sexiness and inclusive representation—portraying beauty as part of, rather than a contradiction to, empowerment. While this opens the ad to male gaze critiques, it also reflects the complexity of female identity in contemporary Türkiye, where empowerment often occurs within, not against, aesthetic norms. Class distinctions also emerge. Türkiye İş Bankası's ad clearly targets an educated, urban, professional demographic, aligning itself with secular, Republican values. AXA's ad, however, traverses class, regional, and lifestyle lines—showcasing women from diverse socioeconomic backgrounds. This makes the campaign more commercially inclusive and socially layered, albeit more ideologically ambiguous.

The Finance & Insurance group introduces a new layer to the discourse on femvertising by prioritizing female voice, presence, and plurality over bodily aesthetics. Both advertisements portray women not as consumers or beautified symbols, but as speakers, agents, and professionals. While Türkiye İş Bankası constructs a unified, legacy-based representation of strength grounded in national identity, AXA's campaign opens up space for a more heterogeneous, affect-driven model of female empowerment. This contrast within the same sector group reveals the versatility of femvertising as a strategic discourse. It can align itself with institutional narratives of progress and continuity, or diverge into emotionally charged, culturally inclusive appeals. These distinctions set the stage for broader inter-group comparisons, particularly with sectors like Beauty or Technology, where bodily representation and product-centered empowerment dominate. In this regard, the Finance & Insurance group functions not

only as a case study in empowerment, but also as a litmus test for how far femvertising can push the boundaries of representation without losing commercial legibility.

4.3. FOOD: A SLICE OF SOLIDARITY

Lezita | 8 MART DÜNYA KADINLAR GÜNÜ KUTLU OLSUN!

Sector: Food Production

YouTube link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=wzPlem7byYg>

Auditory Transcript (Translated)

Woman 1: “I’m Kıymet.” (Male voice-over) At Lezita for over 13 years, Kıymet has continued to improve herself each year. She now shares what she learned at Lezita with her son, who dreams of becoming a police officer. With Lezita’s support, she overcame the hardships of her past.

Woman 2: “I’m Ceyda.” (Male voice-over) Still at the very beginning of her career, Ceyda started in production and has been steadily rising ever since. Thanks to Lezita, she is a woman who stands on her own feet, expressing her ideas freely and with confidence.

Woman 3: “I’m Binnur.” “Ceren, my dear... How are you, my daughter?” (Male voice-over) Binnur, whose story at Lezita spans seven years, speaks of how Lezita stood by her while she was dealing with her daughter’s health issues. She believes Lezita played a major role in helping her get through tough times and now walks her path with greater confidence.

Woman 4: “I’m Hacire.” (Male voice-over) Defying all the “You can’t”s, Hacire never listened to the doubters and showed everyone the power of women. She learned how to lead at Lezita. Never losing her energy for a moment and reflecting that strength onto those around her, she overcomes every obstacle with the determination she gained at Lezita. Behind Lezita’s strength are countless women like Hülya, Nilgün, Büşra, Öznur, Ayşe, and Merve. At Lezita, women’s labor is valued. Happy March 8 to all women who shine like pearls with their grace.

Visual Transcript

Figure 11: Lezita ad – Looking at her son’s photos at work

Figure 12: Lezita ad – Women waving together

The advertisement begins with a general view of the Lezita factory and the brand’s slogan displayed on screen. Kıymet, wearing a white headscarf and work uniform, looks directly into a camera positioned at eye level. Her arms are crossed, her head is tilted slightly to the right, and she appears to smile with her eyes. She is wearing a face mask and gloves. She is then shown working in the production area, equipped with arm guards and earmuffs. In an outdoor seating area, she is seen chatting with other women, this time without gloves, her wedding ring is visible. In another scene, she smiles at photos of her son on her phone; the camera films her from a low angle. Later, in an office setting, Ceyda Çağlar, a young woman with a neat bun and modest attire, works at a computer. The camera captures her from the left diagonal at eye level. Following this, she is seen receiving documents and speaking on the phone. As the ad progresses, another female employee in work uniform is shown speaking on the phone outdoors. On her phone screen is a photo of her daughter with a report card. Smiling at her phone, she is filmed from below. The same woman is later shown packaging products in the factory. Another female employee, wearing a headscarf and work uniform, looks directly at the camera in a mid-shot from the waist up. She also appears to smile with her eyes. In the background, machines and boxes are visible. She is also shown working on the production line and taking notes on a document. Wide shots of women working together inside the factory follow. In the final scene, women from various departments stand with their arms crossed, facing the camera. The shots are at eye level, and each woman makes direct eye contact with the viewer. The ad ends with a wide outdoor shot of women of different ages, styles, and appearances waving at the camera. The camera pulls back to show the full group, and the commercial concludes with the brand’s logo on screen.

Analysis

Social Constructivism

This commercial reconstructs women’s roles through scenes from Lezita’s production facilities. The woman’s continuous smile toward the camera presents her as positive, emotionally balanced, and harmonious—reinforcing traditional expectations of women’s emotional labor, patience, and calmness. This reinforces patriarchal expectations not through aesthetic, but emotional alignment. Women are

shown in factories, offices, and garden sheds—spatial diversity points to their identities as both producers and caregivers. A woman wearing a wedding ring is seen viewing her child’s photo at work, while another calls her child during a break—suggesting the social expectation that motherhood must be maintained across contexts. Women pack goods, prepare files, and work on the production line, asserting that they are subjects not just in the private sphere, but in economic production. Their clothing—overalls, headscarves, rings, office wear—indicates various socio-economic backgrounds, but the dominant portrayal is of modest women empowered through institutional support. Narration emphasizes women’s empowerment and resilience, but attributes these to Lezita’s enabling role. This aligns with social constructivism: womanhood is not fixed, but shaped through institutions, experiences, and relationships.

Gender Performativity

Kıymet’s direct gaze, her arms crossed, her head tilted in a gentle smile; Binnur lovingly addressing her daughter over the phone; Hacire’s assertive tone—all indicate the performativity of gender through repeated acts. Eye-level and low-angle shots place women in strong positions vis-à-vis the viewer. Their stories and postures emphasize resilience and self-respect. Womanhood here is not innate but performed through repeated behaviors, discourses, and roles. The repeated association of women with “hard work,” “sacrifice,” “motherhood,” and “perseverance” reflects how gender becomes internalized and reproduced.

Feminist Media Theory

The commercial avoids objectifying the female body. Women are shown in full, holistic shots rather than fetishized close-ups. Their faces appear unretouched, favoring realism over ideal beauty. Women are not passive figures but positioned as narrators and subjects: Kıymet, Ceyda, Binnur, and Hacire state their names and speak their stories. However, this subjecthood is short-lived: a male narrator soon takes control of the story, recounting their lives with emotional, nostalgic tones—recasting them as passive narrative objects. This structure, as critiqued in feminist media theory, positions women as represented but not self-defining. The quiet, hardworking, self-sacrificing, and humble ideal is reproduced here. The handover of narrative control to a male voice reflects the kind of femvertising Rosalind Gill critiques: while it seems feminist on the surface, it remains entrenched in traditional media codes.

Turkish Context

The ad merges traditional and modern portrayals of women in Türkiye. Veiled women are shown in workspaces, implying that integration into modern labor markets can occur without renouncing religious and cultural identity. While motherhood is indirectly highlighted, there are no overt references to honor or morality. Showing women in factories and offices removes them from domestic confines, making them active agents of production. Their class positioning reflects working women whose success relies

on institutional support. These women belong to the lower-middle class and gain empowerment not through individual feminist struggle, but corporate backing (Lezita). The ad aligns with state rhetoric: female empowerment is framed as a result of institutional endorsement rather than personal resistance, illustrating how feminist representation becomes softened and confined within capitalist and state-sponsored narratives.

Domino's Pizza | 8 Mart Dünya Kadınlar Günümüz Kutlu Olsun!

Sector: Fast Food

YouTube link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=0d0NthPPXgg>

Auditory Transcript (Translated)

(Music fades in. Female voice-over) Let us celebrate not only the effort we put into our lives, the passion we bring to everything we do, and the love we add into all that we offer, but also every moment we live, the strength we draw from our smiles and our unity. On the 100th anniversary of the Republic, we celebrate Women's Day together with one hundred women leaders and hundreds of female employees.

Visual Transcript

Figure 13: Domino's Pizza ad – Employees in front of store Figure 14: Domino's Pizza ad – Collage of working women

The commercial opens in front of a Domino's Pizza store with two female employees in uniforms: one in black, the other in red, standing side by side. They fold their arms across their chests and look directly into the camera. The camera angle is low, capturing them from the waist up, gradually zooming in. In the next sequence, various close-up shots depict hands preparing dough: combining flour, spreading sauce, placing pizzas into the oven, and packaging, all actions performed by different women. The camera focuses on hands that are clean, unadorned, with no rings or nail polish, highlighting a minimalist and practical aesthetic. The camera then shifts focus to the women performing these tasks: female employees are shown from the waist up, smiling as they work. All are wearing work uniforms and caps. The advertisement nears its conclusion by returning to the opening shot: the two women standing confidently in front of the store, arms crossed, staring into the lens. The final scene presents a slideshow

of various Domino's employees smiling, working, and making heart and thumbs-up gestures. The ad ends with the brand logo and the message: "Happy Women's Day of ours."

Analysis

Social Constructivism

The advertisement constructs gender not as an innate characteristic but as a socially acquired and culturally reproduced identity, shaped through spatial organization, visual codes, and symbolic labor. Women are presented as active subjects within a fast-food service environment. The space is redefined through women's collective labor, becoming a gendered setting. By engaging in tasks such as kneading dough, spreading sauce, placing pizzas in the oven, and packaging, their actions frame labor as both a source of empowerment and an element of economic contribution. The camera's focus on plain hands emphasizes a functional and minimal aesthetic that highlights productivity over decoration. This visual choice constructs femininity not through appearance but through functionality. Standard work uniforms symbolize the women's inclusion in an institutional structure, while their confident posture—arms folded and eyes fixed on the camera—symbolically reinforces their subjectivity within that structure. The words in the voice-over, such as "effort," "passion," "love," and "unity," indicate that gender is also constructed as an affective and relational practice. The phrase "the strength we draw from our smiles and our unity" constructs female empowerment not as an innate trait but as a product of shared social values and interactions. It emphasizes that gender and power are shaped through culturally embedded collective meanings. In this context, gender is a dynamic construct, continuously produced through participation in both economic and emotional domains.

Gender Performativity

The two female employees in the opening and closing scenes fold their arms across their chests and look directly into the camera—a stylized performative gesture that conveys strength, confidence, and self-awareness. These postures are framed through low-angle camera shots, visually and symbolically elevating the female figures. The repetition of this scene at both the beginning and end of the advertisement emphasizes the construction of the empowered woman image through a stable and rhythmic performance. The repeated scenes of manual labor—kneading dough, spreading sauce, placing pizzas into the oven—are ritualized and embodied performances of femininity in the brand's workspace. Here, femininity is constructed repeatedly through procedural, productive gestures. The women's standard uniforms contribute to the stylization of the performance. While these elements may suggest a loss of individuality, they also show how gender is enacted within a corporate framework. The absence of aesthetic exaggerations—no prominent makeup, jewelry, or styled hair—grounds the performance of femininity not in attraction or spectacle, but in functionality and discipline.

The voice-over complements this performative structure with the idea of emotional labor. Words such as “effort,” “passion,” “love,” and “unity” show that the performance is not only physical but also emotional, relational, and collective. These expressions code female identity as something not limited to the body, but constructed through gestures, speech, and affective attitude. The heart and thumbs-up gestures at the end of the advertisement can be read as ritual affirmations of collective belonging. While visually light and cheerful, these gestures are embedded in a cultural grammar of recognition and repetition. Thus, the visibility and community of female employees are reinforced—not as passive recipients of celebration, but as co-creators of its meaning.

Feminist Media Theory

From a feminist media studies perspective, the advertisement avoids objectifying representations by portraying women as whole, autonomous subjects engaged in meaningful labor. The camera does not fragment or eroticize the female body; instead, it focuses on action, productivity, and functionality. In this sense, the advertisement challenges narratives dominated by the “male gaze.” Close-up shots of hands without nail polish or adornment reflect a shift in focus from aesthetics to labor and question representations of femininity as passive or ornamental. The women are shown with natural appearances and work uniforms, avoiding heavy makeup or exaggerated hairstyles. This presentation deviates from traditional norms frequently encountered in media and subverts the “strong-but-sexualized woman” binary often criticized in postfeminist advertisements. Their confident stance and direct eye contact with the camera position them not as visual objects but as subjects in control of their representation.

Turkish Context

The advertisement situates its narrative within Türkiye’s socio-cultural landscape by referencing national history and values. Specifically, the commemoration of the 100th anniversary of the Republic links women’s labor not only to individual identity but also to national progress. The phrase “100 women leaders and hundreds of female employees” emphasizes women’s roles in public life, merging everyday professionalism with a broader historical consciousness. Women are represented not through maternal or familial roles, but as productive, capable individuals within the workforce. This contributes to a form of everyday feminism in Türkiye — quiet but persistent — that does not directly oppose traditional values, yet subtly redefines womanhood through labor, visibility, and dignity. In this context, strength is not framed as an executive or elite trait but as something rooted in collective presence and shared work.

Food Intra-Group Analysis

The Food group includes advertisements from two distinct sectors: food production (Lezita) and fast food (Domino’s Pizza). While these industries differ in their market orientation and corporate structure, they share a common goal in their International Women’s Day campaigns: to recognize and celebrate the role of women in everyday labor, both emotional and physical. This chapter explores how each

advertisement constructs the image of the “strong woman” through workplace visuals, verbal narratives, and affective coding. Food-sector femvertising tends to ground empowerment in production, routine, and community. These representations offer insight into how labor and gender intersect—raising questions about whether empowerment is framed as individual achievement or collective effort, and whether it resists or reinforces traditional cultural norms.

Both advertisements portray strength not through abstraction, but through labor. In both cases, women are shown working—kneading dough, preparing food, managing files, answering phones, packaging products. These procedural actions are not merely background; they are the visual core of the narrative. Across both *Lezita* and *Domino’s*, femininity is symbolically constructed not through aesthetics or spectacle, but through daily, visible, productive gestures. From a gender performativity perspective, women perform strength through repeated acts of labor, stance, and speech (Butler, 1990). Both ads use arm-crossing gestures and direct eye contact—often filmed from eye-level or low angles—to construct an embodied performance of confidence and agency. The workplace routines (typing, stretching dough, boxing products) reinforces the performativity of gendered labor within a corporate framework. Meanwhile, ads foreground repetition of domestic or productive gestures—kneading, designing, cooking, managing—as tools of gender socialization. Social constructivism also plays a central role in these narratives. Femininity is presented as shaped not by nature, but by socio-economic context. Uniforms, production environments, and affective labor (smiling, caregiving, perseverance) are all presented as components of a gendered identity that is cultivated through institutional affiliation. Particularly in *Lezita*, where motherhood is subtly referenced through visual cues like rings or photos of children, gender becomes an intersection of labor and care. Both commercials also draw on affective discourse—emphasizing not only what women do, but how they feel. Voice-overs include terms like “effort,” “passion,” “unity,” and “grace,” creating a semantic overlap between productivity and emotional resilience. This emotional dimension is a common strategy in femvertising (Gill, 2007), which often blends sentimentality with empowerment to elicit both identification and admiration.

Despite these commonalities, the two commercials diverge in narrative control, emotional tone, and ideological framing. *Lezita’s* advertisement is biographical and emotionally layered, built on testimonial storytelling—yet these stories are not told by the women themselves. Although women introduce themselves by name, the bulk of the narrative is voiced by a male speaker. This narrative shift subtly repositions women as objects of admiration rather than self-narrating subjects, aligning with critiques from feminist media theory about the illusion of agency in patriarchal storytelling (Gill, 2008). In contrast, *Domino’s* allows women’s actions and presence to speak for themselves. The visual strategy relies heavily on gesture and repetition rather than verbal storytelling. The absence of individual names, voices, or backgrounds depersonalizes the figures but universalizes the message: the strong woman is any woman performing work with pride and focus. The camera repeatedly returns to two women standing in front of the *Domino’s* store—arms crossed, gazing directly at the viewer—as symbolic

guardians of both space and representation. The tone of each ad also differs. Lezita adopts a nostalgic, emotionally rich tone, reinforcing a care-based femininity deeply rooted in family, patience, and gratitude toward the employer. The empowering message is filtered through institutional benevolence: the company as enabler, the woman as loyal subject. Domino's, on the other hand, chooses a more secular, collective voice. By marking the 100th anniversary of the Turkish Republic, the ad blends individual labor with national progress—suggesting a feminism of visibility, not exceptionality. Cultural and class differences are also evident. Lezita's portrayal emphasizes working-class women—modest clothing, headscarves, factory labor—who gain strength through community and corporate support. Domino's presents a more standardized corporate femininity: clean uniforms, minimal styling, middle-ground aesthetics. There is less emphasis on motherhood or family and more on functional visibility and shared discipline.

The Food sector group introduces a grounded, labor-centric narrative into the landscape of femvertising. These advertisements reject glamorous portrayals of female strength in favor of functionality, repetition, and emotional authenticity. Yet while both ads position women as central to economic productivity, they diverge in their narrative logic: Lezita emphasizes corporate-enabled personal resilience, while Domino's celebrates collective identity and national belonging. Both, however, remain cautious in how far they challenge the traditional boundaries of gender. Empowerment is framed within existing systems—of work, care, and modesty—rather than in defiance of them. This group frames female strength not through glamorous representations, but through labor, belonging, and perseverance.

4.4. AUTOMOTIVE & MOBILITY: SHE'S GOT THE MOTION

Corendon Airlines | Beşiktaş TRC İnşaat Kadın Basketbol Takımı Corendon Airlines Reklam Filmi

Sector: Aviation and Tourism

YouTube link: <https://youtu.be/90DU48bDJZ8?si=PLYmPb4ZYbjMk5lu>

Auditory Transcript (Translated)

(Throughout the ad, rhythmic music and eagle cries are heard.) (Male voice-over) A new day begins in the harsh climate of Akatlar. As if signaling the start of a new battle, female eagles lock their sharp gaze onto the target, their vision is remarkably sharp. The eagle, with its powerful talons, is always ready to strike. The opponent has no idea what's coming. The female eagle approaches her prey silently, and suddenly, she makes her move. She delivers the finishing blow. Eagles always fly high. Corendon Airlines, Official Sponsor of the Beşiktaş Women's Basketball Team.

Visual Transcript

Figure 15: Corendon Airlines ad – Hands forming claw

Figure 16: Corendon Airlines ad – Player's intense stare

The advertisement opens with a bird's-eye view of a basketball court. A women's basketball team is training under the hoop. The camera gradually descends and closes in on the players. One player signals to a teammate with her eyes; the other picks up on the cue and catches the ball to continue the play. The scene then returns to an aerial shot showing the coordinated movements of the players on the court. The players wear the team's colors black-and-white sleeveless jerseys and mid-length shorts. Most of them have their hair tied back. The team includes both Black and White women. In the next scene, the actors lift their gaze from the ground and focus forward. Their eyes are shown in a close-up shot from a low angle. In the following scenes, they position their hands in the shape of the team's claw symbol to grip the ball, which they pass quickly between one another. These actions are mainly filmed from below. The camera focuses on hands, feet, and ball movement, capturing their dribbling and running. A low-angle shot shows a player making a layup. Immediately afterward, the ball is seen going into the hoop, scoring a point. The players come together to celebrate. In this moment, the camera is at body level, capturing the athletes hugging and jumping with joy. The camera then drops slightly lower and offers a closer shot from the body level. The final scene returns to an overhead shot of the court and transitions to a Corendon Airlines airplane. In the closing frame, the brand's logo, slogan, and the team's emblem appear on screen.

Analysis

Social Constructivism

In this commercial, women appear on a basketball court—a public sports space traditionally dominated by men—thus challenging spatial gender norms. The female athletes are portrayed in active motion, directly confronting conventional associations of women with motherhood, housework, or caregiving. Their sports uniforms and simple hairstyles signal team identity rather than any class privilege. The male voiceover describes the women as “female eagles,” evoking the team's mascot and attributing strength, strategy, and silent efficiency to them. This metaphor constructs the women not as passive or delicate, but as predatory and resolute—contrary to societal expectations. However, the use of a male voice to

articulate female strength suggests that even this rupture is legitimized through male approval, underscoring how representations of female power still often rely on external validation.

Gender Performativity

The gestures, facial expressions, and bodily movements of the female athletes are presented in direct association with strength. Their upright stances, focused gazes, and in-game movements—such as signaling, passing, or layups—symbolize the reproduction of gender through powerful physical performance. The claw-like hand gestures before attacking the ball visually resonate with masculine-coded behaviors. Low-angle shots throughout the ad associate their bodies with dominance and power. The absence of overt sexualization in favor of functional uniforms supports Butler’s notion that identity is constructed through repeated actions. These women are not just athletes; they are bodily performers of a reconfigured femininity.

Feminist Media Theory

The camera primarily focuses on the players’ movements—dribbling, footwork, claw gestures—emphasizing functionality over objectification. The metaphor “The eagle, with its powerful talons, is always ready to strike” exemplifies how femvertising can rely on hypermasculine and militarized symbols to convey female strength. Within the framework of feminist media theory, such imagery illustrates how empowerment narratives often remain embedded within dominant visual grammars of aggression and control, rather than challenging them. Neutral lighting and unpolished aesthetics—minimal makeup and natural presentation—signal a turn away from idealized beauty toward functionality. The women engage in team dynamics and goal-oriented actions rather than posing for the camera, which reinforces their subjecthood. However, the male narration and external framing of the success story remain a limiting factor, suggesting that full subjectivity is still mediated through a male lens.

Turkish Context

This commercial constructs a representation of the modern Turkish woman in public life. By showcasing women in a domain of physicality and power like sports, and excluding references to motherhood or traditional family values, it initiates a quiet rupture from normative portrayals. The players’ minimal uniforms and professional composure suggest a middle-class sports professionalism. The absence of markers of regional accents or ethnicity implies a unifying national representation. Rather than clashing with state discourse, the ad aligns with narratives that celebrate successful Turkish women, though it does so through corporate—not governmental—support. This reflects a model of feminism embraced by non-state actors, signaling an alternative form of legitimacy.

Mercedes-Benz | She's Mercedes. Gücünü ilham veren kadınlardan aldı.

Sector: Automotive

YouTube link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=-ITjweFrMH8>

Auditory Transcript (Translated)

(With a rhythmic background music, female voice-over) She set her goals sky-high. And never lost her courage. She crossed the finish line as a champion despite all the prejudice and the ones who said, “She could never make it.” She didn’t just believe in a car, she pioneered a journey that changed history. She is Mercedes. She drew her strength from women who inspire.

Visual Transcript

Figure 17: Mercedes-Benz ad – Woman seating with help

Figure 18: Mercedes-Benz – Woman with two boys

The advertisement opens with a close-up of a woman’s eyes seen through a car’s rearview mirror. The on-screen text reads: “Steph Davis, Wingsuit Athlete.” The next scene shows her in a rocky outdoor environment, opening the trunk of her parked car and letting her dog out. She is dressed in athletic wear, a purple sweatshirt and shorts. Next shots capture her engaging in wingsuit flying, shown in both close-up and wide-angle frames. Then, she appears in full-body view wearing a helmet and gear, with the camera positioned at body level. A shot of the sunrise and the horizon follows. Then, fully suited in her gear, she jumps off a cliff and begins to glide through the air; the camera watches from above as she flies. The next scene features the text: “Ewy Rosqvist, Winner of the 1962 Argentine Grand Prix.” A different woman is seen sitting in a classic race car, wearing a helmet. A man standing outside the car gestures toward the camera, so she turns to the lens and smiles. In the next scene, she is shown driving close-up, and the car takes off from a slope and briefly lifts off the ground. The camera follows the car from the outside, then cuts to a very close-up, eye-level shot of the woman’s face. Aerial footage of the road’s landscape is also shown. Next, the screen displays the text: “Bertha Benz, the First Driver in History.” The camera shows a woman in historical dress, a long black gown and a hat, filmed slightly from below. She is surrounded by a crowd. She removes a device from her head and uses it on the car. Then, holding a young boy’s hand, she boards the vehicle. Just before the car starts moving, the camera

focuses from below on her face as she wipes sweat from her brow with the back of her hand. A young man then starts the motor. As the car moves, the woman glances back at the camera; beside her in the car are the boy and the young man who started the engine. The shot is again taken from a low angle. Toward the end of the ad, the car drives off while the entire crowd looks after it. The setting evokes a historical village atmosphere. In the final scene, the on-screen text reads: “Mercedes draws its strength from women who inspire.” The ad closes with the brand’s logo.

Analysis

Social Constructivism

The commercial features three women in different historical contexts—all situated in public, male-dominated spaces: wingsuit athlete Steph Davis in nature, Ewy Rosqvist as a racing driver in 1962, and Bertha Benz, the first woman to drive a car. Their environments—mountains, racetracks, and mechanical settings—have traditionally been seen as masculine territories. Their clothing (sportswear, racing suits, historical costumes) aligns with their functional roles and suggests a bourgeois, upper-middle-class identity. The narration emphasizes that these women broke stereotypes, crossed finish lines as champions, and left marks in history, suggesting that societal norms are historically constructed and open to change. Female strength, therefore, is portrayed as something that transcends social barriers and redefines itself.

Gender Performativity

Each woman rearticulates the performative nature of gender through her physicality. Steph Davis’s body in mid-air during wingsuiting becomes a site of feminine courage, while Rosqvist’s gestures—firm grip on the wheel, steady gaze—and Benz’s act of wiping her brow exemplify Butler’s notion that identity is built through repeated performances. Low and eye-level shots associate these bodily acts with symbols of power. Style and function blend with context; the women are not only powerful but subjectivized in ways unique to their environments. Davis’s solitary figure against nature especially underscores the formation of an individualized performative identity.

Feminist Media Theory

The camera avoids eroticizing the female body, favoring functionality. Fragmented body shots are minimal and tied to contextual actions (steering, flying, etc.). With “She drew her strength from women who inspire”, empowerment is conveyed through phrases like “inspiring women,” “championship,” and “changing history.” The camera elevates the women’s actions rather than objectifying them. Lighting is natural and grounded; visual representation emphasizes lived experience over ideal beauty. Women do not pose directly at the camera—they act, move, and decide. They are “doers,” not “objects of the gaze.” However, full subjectification is not always achieved. For instance, the final scene—where a woman

engages with the car but the boy takes over the ignition—hints at narrative closure resting with male agency. This limits the female character’s role, showing she is technically skilled but not the ultimate driver of the story. Thus, power is visible but contained within a structure mediated by male support.

Turkish Context

Although centered on international women, the ad echoes patterns in Turkish femvertising that focus on female visibility in public space. The women are not depicted as maternal or emotional caretakers but as professionals and pioneers. Instead of family or moral values, the narrative emphasizes historical achievement and individual agency. In this way, the ad reflects a secular, individualistic, and professional model of womanhood, countering family-centered portrayals common in Türkiye. However, by surrendering key moments of narrative control to male characters, the ad also signals that gender equality is still an incomplete project within representation.

Automotive & Mobility Intra-Group Analysis

The Automotive & Mobility group includes advertisements from two distinct sectors: Aviation and Tourism (Corendon Airlines) and Automotive (Mercedes-Benz). These industries are historically coded as masculine due to their association with technology, mobility, and control. Within this context, femvertising campaigns offer a rare opportunity to reframe these gendered associations through the portrayal of strong, capable women. The selected commercials feature narratives of female athletes, pioneers, and team players who navigate and dominate spaces conventionally reserved for men. This section analyzes how strength is constructed through performance, space, and symbolism, and whether these portrayals break new ground or remain tethered to traditional media structures.

Both commercials construct female strength through physical action, public presence, and visual codes of control. The main characters are portrayed as decisive, mobile, and determined—whether on a basketball court, in the air, or behind the wheel. Visual repetition plays a central role: low-angle shots, confident gazes, and goal-directed body language recur across both ads. These techniques establish women not as passive figures but as embodied agents of transformation. From the perspective of gender performativity, the ads foreground repeated bodily acts—gripping the basketball, flying through mountain air, steering a racecar, or initiating a layup. These gestures function as performative scripts that reinforce gendered identity through visible repetition (Butler, 1990). For example, the basketball players’ claw gestures and team coordination rituals, as well as Steph Davis’s solitary dive from a cliff, are stylized performances of power and autonomy that go beyond the symbolic—they are embodied enactments of gendered resistance. Both commercials also present functionality over aesthetics, aligning with feminist media theory (Gill, 2007; Mulvey, 1975). There are no fragmented shots of lips, legs, or torsos—camera work prioritizes full-body or action-oriented frames. Lighting is natural and unglamorous, focusing on realism rather than seduction. Women are dressed in uniforms, athletic wear,

or historical costumes appropriate to their environments, stripping femininity of its ornamental layer and embedding it within a narrative of purpose. Furthermore, both ads use symbolic spatial codes to redefine the meaning of female presence. The basketball court and the open sky are spaces of movement and strategy. Similarly, the racetrack and the historical village become stages for women to assert visibility and authorship. These are not domestic or aestheticized settings; they are terrains of challenge, risk, and victory.

Despite these shared codes, the two commercials diverge in their tone, narrative strategy, and the degree of agency attributed to female subjects. Corendon's ad relies heavily on metaphor and collective identity. The athletes are symbolized as "female eagles," echoing team spirit and animalistic power. However, this metaphor is voiced by a male narrator, who dictates the metaphorical framework through which female strength is interpreted. This introduces an external gaze that—while admiring—nonetheless mediates and potentially limits subjecthood. In contrast, Mercedes-Benz features individual women from different eras whose achievements have been historically documented. The women are introduced by name and context, supported by on-screen text that elevates them as figures of innovation and transformation. The voice-over is female, and the emphasis on personal legacy—"she changed history," "she crossed the finish line"—suggests a more self-authored form of empowerment. However, even here, the ad subtly reintroduces male validation: Bertha Benz initiates the journey, but the ignition is started by a man; the final "departure" moment is symbolically shared. Aesthetically, Corendon's ad offers a minimalist, contemporary team aesthetic with no makeup, matching uniforms, and a cool-toned color palette. Mercedes-Benz, meanwhile, emphasizes individuality through costume and context—each woman's environment, whether nature, track, or historical village, reinforces her uniqueness. In this way, Corendon prioritizes collective performance, while Mercedes foregrounds individual legacy. Culturally, Corendon's ad is rooted in a Turkish context, showcasing a local team, yet avoids nationalist or state-centric discourse. Mercedes-Benz, though global, adopts a universal message through historically significant female figures and subtly reflects values resonant with modern secular feminism. Both maintain a corporate-centric model of representation, whereby empowerment is made possible through brands—not political mobilization.

The Automotive & Mobility group presents a distinct mode of femvertising that emphasizes performance, mobility, and discipline. Across both ads, female strength is rooted in bodily action, spatial presence, and symbolic rupture. Yet, they differ in their narrative strategies: Corendon relies on metaphor and collective symbolism framed by male narration, while Mercedes highlights individual historical agency, albeit with some reliance on patriarchal closure. This group locates power in physical challenge and legacy. It asks not whether women are strong, but how they move through space, time, and resistance. This spatial and historical orientation provides a valuable reference point for assessing the full spectrum of femvertising in Türkiye and beyond.

4.5. FASHION: PATTERN BREAKERS

Nocturne | Nocturne X Hande Erçel – #WOMANofPOWER

Sector: Fashion

YouTube link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=FerJYi7wu9w>

Auditory Transcript (Translated)

(Voice-over by actress Hande Erçel) This is my lifestyle. My character. My true self. I'm powerful, more than I've ever been. With every step I take, in the dark or in the light... My attitude is the same, so is my style. On the streets, right in the heart of life, exactly where every woman should be. My voice is loud, and so is my stance. Lighting up the dark is in your hands. Step outside. Show your power to everyone. Nocturne, woman of power.

Visual Transcript

Figure 19: Nocturne ad – Power pose through legs

Figure 20: Nocturne ad – Multiples of woman in red suit

The commercial opens with the brand name on screen, followed by the name of the female actress. She is first seen in full-body shot, looking directly into the camera. The camera slowly zooms in. She is wearing a black leather trench coat and pointed-toe black leather boots. Her hair is slicked back and left down. Her inner outfit is not visible; she poses with her right leg exposed through the trench coat, maintaining direct eye contact with the camera. In the next scene, she is shown again in the same outfit, this time framed from the waist up. The camera angle is head-on. She has one hand resting behind her waist, and the other hand placed in her pocket with one finger visibly sticking out. Her posture is strong, and she stares into the camera with a firm gaze. This is followed by a rapid series of close-up shots showing the texture of the clothing, her eyes, and facial features. In the next scene, she appears in a different outfit, again shown from the waist up, facing the camera directly. She is wearing a white strappy crop top with a plunging neckline and a crocodile-textured yellow leather jacket. A vertical beam of light running down the center of her face highlights her features. Her hair is again slicked back and loose,

with minimal makeup. The next scene shows a close-up of the details of her jeans. In the following scene, the woman is shown taking off the yellow leather jacket. The camera, starting below her waist, circles her body from a low angle, emphasizing her toned physique. The camera moves in closer, shifting focus from her waist to her chest and finally to her face. She continues to look directly at the camera. The following scenes present close-up shots of the stitching and surface details of the leather jacket she's wearing. Then, she is seen in a zebra-patterned, long-sleeved, high-neck swimsuit. Over it, she wears a leopard-print yellow coat and white boots. The camera first shows her full-body from the front, then transitions through her legs to a shot of her squatting and gazing directly into the camera. The details of the jacket are shown again. Then, the previous black trench coat look returns, displayed from multiple angles: full-body, angled, direct, and close-up. In the next scene, she appears in a navy blue blazer, looking straight into the camera in a portrait-style frame. The camera remains at eye level. After this, she is shown in the swimsuit look again, this time triplicated into three mirrored versions of herself. The camera films her from below, with her body in the frame. Next, she appears in a red jumpsuit with a matching red jacket. Her shoes are pointed red high heels. The camera films her full-body from a low angle as she faces the camera directly. The shot begins in close-up, then gradually pulls back to show the same outfit from five different angles and distances. This is followed by a montage of all the previous outfits she has worn, shown sequentially from various angles and in both full-body and close-up shots. Then, she appears wearing a black crop top with a brown zebra-print jacket and matching pants. While posing, she leans back, then covers her eyes with her hand and plays to the camera with expressive gestures. This scene features a series of moments where she poses directly toward the camera, showcasing the outfit. In the final scene, she is seen wearing a thick-strapped white tank top, a black leather skirt, and a leather jacket. On her feet she has white cowboy boots. The outfit features a chest-revealing neckline, and her poses are directed straight at the camera. In this scene, the camera shifts between close-ups and wide shots, focusing on her stance and facial expressions. The commercial ends with the appearance of the brand name and logo on screen.

Analysis

Social Constructivism

The ad positions the woman as a subject in public space—especially on the street, day and night. The emphasis on being “on the street, in the heart of life” signals her entitlement to public visibility beyond domestic confinement. Her activity is not tied to work or production, but to presentation and self-representation—walking, posing, casting gazes. Her outfits (leather trench coats, crop tops, blazers, swimsuits, heels) signal upper-middle-class status through fashion and luxury. Statements like “my voice is loud, my stance is bold” invert cultural expectations of women’s quietness, modesty, and invisibility. Yet, the emphasis on individual freedom—without critique of systemic inequality—confines the ad to a liberal individualist framework.

Gender Performativity

In this commercial, power is reproduced through repeated aesthetic forms of femininity. The woman appears in multiple outfits, poses, and walks across the screen in duplicated frames, visually reflecting Butler's idea that gender is not innate but constituted through repetition. Her confident posture, hands on hips, and unwavering gaze channel traditionally masculine-coded traits like assertiveness and stage presence. Low-angle shots imbue her body with power, though not through masculinity but via hyper-feminine style—heels, makeup, revealing clothing. Animal-print outfits further symbolize wildness, natural aggression, and elegant danger, challenging the docility typically associated with femininity. This suggests that femininity can be both powerful and aesthetic.

Feminist Media Theory

The ad is ripe for critique through the “male gaze.” The camera frequently fragments the woman's body, legs, waist, chest, in close-up. While the low-angle shots reinforce her power, they simultaneously risk objectification. Her direct posing to the camera may seem active, but it is ultimately performative for the viewer. By stating “my true self” and “my character” before declaring strength, the ad suggests that empowerment originates from authentic identity rather than imposed roles. However, this internal strength is still conveyed through visual performance—style, confidence, and public visibility, turning individuality into a consumable narrative. Empowerment is packaged in aestheticized individuality: “Show your power to everyone.” This power stems from outer transformation legitimizing subjecthood through display rather than inner capability or systemic equality. Dramatic lighting idealizes her face, offering a stylized rather than realistic representation. The animal-print clothing further situates her in a “femme fatale” aesthetic—desirable yet dangerous, subject and object at once.

Turkish Context

Nocturne's ad aligns with representations of the “modern, urban, stylish woman” seen in social media and fashion-driven platforms in Türkiye. Her fashion sense, standard Turkish accent, and global aesthetics evoke a universalized “strong woman” ideal. The exclusion of themes like family, motherhood, or honor subtly signals secular individualism, opposing dominant conservative femininity discourses. The woman is defined solely by her individual presence—-independent, assertive, and in control. Yet the ad lacks any critique of systemic gender inequality. Its slogan “Women are everywhere” offers surface-level diversity without depth. Her social position is marked by privilege—stylish clothes, professional lighting, confident posture—all encoding upper-class identity. This narrows the ad's representational reach, reproducing a stylized feminism accessible mainly to urban, privileged women.

Trendyol | #GelecekKadınların

Sector: E-Commerce

YouTube link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EjDI8cs82Ss>

Auditory Transcript (Translated)

Trendyol Business Partner Şiyar Ağca: Did I ever imagine I'd have my own brand one day? I did. It never left my mind. I've been dreaming about it since I was fifteen.

Trendyol Business Partner Deniz Eyüboğlu: I never asked, "How would it work? How would I do it?"

Trendyol Business Partner Zehra Aksöyek: I got to work early in the morning.

Trendyol Business Partner Pelin Giydiren Çakmak: I bought beads from Eminönü and started making jewelry.

Trendyol Business Partner Şiyar Ağca: Once I set my mind to it, that was it. I said, "If someone else can do it, so can I."

Trendyol Business Partner Aycan Ercengiz: That was the day my future began.

Women (speaking in turns): Now there are 150 of us; our workshops are buzzing with work 24 hours a day. They ask me what the secret to success is. And I tell them this: I believed in my strength, the power of my imagination. Let's be even bolder, let's produce more, let's create more value. We women, let's be an example for the future.

Visual Transcript

Figure 21: Trendyol ad – Woman walking in warehouse

Figure 22: Trendyol ad – Woman at work

The commercial opens with a shot of a red jacket displayed on a mannequin. The scene takes place indoors, in what appears to be a workspace where clothing is designed or sewn. The lighting is dim, gradually brightening as the woman's voice begins to speak. As the speaking woman appears on screen,

we see a woman with styled, loose hair, wearing a white formal shirt and a burgundy long jacket. She wears high heels and trousers. The interview scene takes place in a better-lit warehouse. Her name and title appear on the screen. The camera films her frontally in a full-body shot. In the next scene, the hands of a woman drawing a design sketch are shown. Then, a new woman's name appears on screen; she is shown in profile, smiling. In the following shot, another woman is seen riding public transportation alone. She has blonde hair worn down, and is wearing a trench coat and black boots, with a large bag beside her. The camera films her from a low angle, capturing her full body. The journey scene is supported with views of Istanbul. Next, a woman is seen working in a closed workshop environment. She is wearing a long-sleeved blouse and black pants. Then, in a warehouse scene, a woman walks down an aisle between boxes, she is first seen from a distance and then approaches the camera in a full-body shot. Following that, a blonde woman sits on a chair wearing a burgundy blouse, formal trousers, and pointed high heels. The camera films her head-on. She appears to be in a workshop environment. Scenes of the same woman working behind machines in a factory, engaged in tasks such as sewing and ironing, are shown. These scenes are accompanied by close-up shots of detailed machinery used in the production process. As the commercial continues, women are shown one by one in their own workspaces (workshops, warehouses, design departments, etc.). Then, a scene shows a group of women chatting and laughing together around a table. The next scenes show women individually managing their tasks: working at desks on computers, presenting during meetings. The camera is mostly at eye level. The commercial ends with a silhouette of a woman walking outdoors against a scenic view. Then, the brand's slogan and name appear on screen, marking the end of the ad.

Analysis

Social Constructivism

Women are depicted in various professional roles—from production to management—asserting their agency in public spaces. Shown in offices, workshops, warehouses, factories, and public transport, they break free from domestic confines and emerge as producers, entrepreneurs, and decision-makers. Their formal attire (blazers, pants, heels) signals a middle-to-upper-class professional identity. This may also imply that gender barriers are only breakable with class privilege. The line “Could I ever imagine having my own brand?” reveals implicit societal doubt about women's economic agency. The reply—“I could. I never stopped thinking about it.”—acts as a powerful internal rebuttal, revealing not just a dream but a long-held conviction. Repeated affirmations—“If others can do it, so can I,” “I trusted my strength”—reposition the woman as a confident subject. The ad aligns with the core of social constructivism: gender roles are not fixed but historically, culturally, and economically produced, reproduced, and transformed.

Gender Performativity

Throughout the ad, women's body language, attire, and actions reflect a performative construction of power. They stand tall, walk with confidence, and actively engage with the production process. Shoulders are back, gazes firm, gestures deliberate. For instance, the woman sitting alone on public transport is framed not as vulnerable but as autonomous. Repeated movements—walking between shelves, operating machines, presenting at a computer—signal her as a consistent subject of action. Eye-level and low-angle shots reinforce her empowered stance. Lighting, color tones, and understated style convey strength without hyper-masculinity—strength with professional seriousness.

Feminist Media Theory

The ad refrains from objectifying women, presenting them holistically and functionally. The camera emphasizes action (drawing, walking, producing) over isolated body parts. Empowerment is framed through individualized and emotional personal expressions like “I believed in my strength, the power of my imagination.” rather than systemic critique. The ad avoids glamour and instead highlights values like effort, creativity, and determination. Lighting is realistic, and the women are either narrators or in action—not passive objects. This challenges traditional media depictions and proposes a more collective, productive, and grounded feminism, distinct from aestheticized or consumer-based narratives.

Turkish Context

The ad presents a modern image of Turkish women, omitting traditional themes like family, motherhood, or honor. Women are framed as individuals. However, their legitimacy is still tied to values like “hard work,” “dedication,” and “perseverance.” They are coded as middle-upper class—reflected in their attire, urban settings, and entrepreneurial roles. While not openly defying state narratives, the ad implies divergence through its individualist and entrepreneurial framing. By increasing female visibility in public life, the ad contributes to renegotiating gender norms in Türkiye—yet it remains focused on metropolitan, economically privileged women, limiting its broader representational scope.

Fashion Intra-Group Analysis

The Fashion sector group comprises two advertisements from Nocturne and Trendyol, representing high-street fashion and e-commerce retail, respectively. Both ads foreground the image of the “strong woman,” but they do so through different visual narratives and empowerment strategies. While Nocturne's ad centers on aesthetic expression and public visibility in urban spaces, Trendyol takes a documentary-style approach that foregrounds women's entrepreneurial agency and labor. Analyzing these advertisements together offers a nuanced lens into how the fashion industry navigates between empowerment as self-presentation and empowerment as production. This group, within the broader

scope of this study, offers a meaningful stage to test whether female strength in advertising can move beyond a shining surface to become a substantive, structural narrative.

Both advertisements utilize the visual grammar of empowerment by placing women in public, often traditionally male-dominated spaces, with confident postures, controlled gazes, and assertive body language. In both cases, the female figures are not passive recipients of the gaze; they are framed as active agents—posing, walking, working, speaking. The camera reinforces this agency through eye-level or low-angle shots, symbolically elevating their presence within their respective domains. From a gender performativity perspective (Butler, 1990), the repetition of confident stances, stylized outfits, and direct eye contact in the Nocturne ad mirrors the construction of gender as a reiterated performance. The woman's power is communicated through visual multiplicity—her image tripled on screen, her body rotated, her outfits changed—conveying femininity as a curated, dynamic force. Similarly, Trendyol's advertisement employs repetition of workplace actions—drawing, managing, presenting, sewing—as gendered performances that re-signify women's societal roles beyond domesticity. These are not random acts but embodied gestures that, repeated over time, construct the subjectivity of the “professional woman.” The discourse of post-feminist empowerment also runs through both ads, albeit in different registers. Nocturne's slogan “Woman of Power” and the voice-over's declaration “My voice is loud, and so is my stance” exemplify what Gill (2007) terms “self-authoring” agency, where empowerment is expressed through personal style and confidence. Trendyol echoes this discourse with statements like “I believed in my strength and imagination,” suggesting that success is a product of inner conviction rather than external conditions. Both ads thus commodify empowerment, albeit through different symbols: fashion and style in Nocturne; production and entrepreneurship in Trendyol. In this way, both advertisements employ femvertising strategies that celebrate women's strength while aligning it with commercial products or platforms. Whether in luxury outerwear or startup ambition, power is framed as a consumable ideal—a lifestyle, a brand, a path forward.

Despite these shared thematic cores, the ads diverge significantly in form, tone, and the type of subjectivity they construct. Nocturne's commercial embraces an aesthetic of spectacle: the woman is a solitary figure, always impeccably styled, captured in stylized poses under dramatic lighting. She appears as a fashion icon—assertive, glamorous, and enigmatic. However, her strength is largely visual and symbolic, constructed through fashion-coded aesthetics: leather, animal prints, heels, and slick hair. The power she embodies is performative and individualized, grounded in visibility and style rather than action or social impact. In contrast, Trendyol offers a multi-vocal narrative that documents real-life women entrepreneurs, focusing on their journeys from dream to production. Here, strength is not constructed through aesthetics but through work, community, and process. The ad avoids glamorous lighting or body-fragmenting close-ups; instead, it emphasizes hands sketching, feet walking, mouths speaking—offering a holistic and grounded view of female agency. The representation is collective, not solitary; functional, not ornamental. The representational differences between the Trendyol and

Nocturne campaigns may stem not only from narrative choices, but also from the distinct sectoral positions of the brands. Originally established as a fashion retail website and later evolving into a marketplace-based e-commerce platform, Trendyol reinforces its sense of connection with female users by emphasizing women’s labor and versatility. In contrast, Nocturne, a brand directly rooted in the fashion industry, constructs the theme of empowerment primarily through bodily aesthetics and visual appeal. This divergence suggests that representational strategies are shaped not only by thematic concerns, but also by the brand’s target audience, communication strategy, and corporate positioning. Moreover, class and cultural signaling also differ across the two ads. Nocturne’s solitary model represents a cosmopolitan, upper-middle-class subject defined by consumption, beauty, and Western-style independence. Trendyol’s women—despite also appearing professionally dressed and urban—are framed in workspaces, reflecting a meritocratic ideal that links power to creativity, labor, and entrepreneurship. While both are aspirational, Trendyol’s ad presents empowerment as accessible through effort; Nocturne’s, through image and attitude. Furthermore, feminist media theory (Mulvey, 1975) helps elucidate these differences. The Nocturne ad, while seemingly empowering, flirts with objectification through repeated fragmentation of the body—legs, waist, chest—highlighted by close-ups and revolving camera angles. Trendyol actively resists this gaze, portraying women as subjects rather than objects, defined by their work and community presence, not their bodies.

Taken together, two advertisements reflect contrasting strategies within femvertising’s evolving landscape. Nocturne reclaims aesthetics and sensuality as domains of power, while Trendyol constructs strength through economic participation and collective agency. Yet both rely on visual codes that cater to middle-class, urban femininity, reflecting a partial and selective vision of empowerment. These distinctions set the stage for broader cross-sectoral comparisons. When placed alongside representations in finance, food, or industrial sectors, the fashion group reveals a split in femvertising discourse: between visibility and productivity, between spectacle and substance. This tension becomes central to understanding whether the image of the strong woman in advertising is truly transformative—or merely tailored to fit different market niches.

4.6. TECHNOLOGY & TELECOMMUNICATIONS: CTRL+NARRATIVE

Vodafone | Kazandırdıkları, başardıklarından çok daha fazlası.

Sector: Telecommunications

YouTube link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=6mOwkeEkdM8>

Auditory Transcript (Translated)

(Female voice-over) Climbing to the top of the world, is it easy? You've done it. You turned those little girls into the world's strongest women. And you'll do even more. (Male voice-over) What you'll win isn't just a match; (Boy voice-over) It's hope and courage for millions. (Female voice-over) Yes, every athlete dreams of winning, but thanks to you, thousands of women will say "I made it." Millions of children will grow up with growing dreams. And you'll always be remembered as the women who proved that every dream can be dreamed and every dream that's dreamed can come true. (Male voice-over) What they inspire goes far beyond what they've achieved. As Vodafone, we stand with all women who say "We are here." Happy International Women's Day, March 8.

Visual Transcript

Figure 23: Vodafone ad – Eda Erdem, team captain

Figure 24: Vodafone ad – Team power pose

The ad begins with the Vodafone logo and social media comments about the national team appearing on screen. Then, in black-and-white footage, a woman sits down on a chair in a dimly lit room with a plain background. The on-screen text reads: "The words you'll hear in this video were created by combining real social media comments about Filenin Sultanları (Sultans of the Net) using artificial intelligence." Next, three female volleyball players are shown sitting side by side during a match. One rests her chin on her hands and looks up, another covers her face with her hands, while the third clasps her hands over her knees and stares off into the distance. The camera films them frontally. They wear team jerseys and mostly have their hair tied back. Following this, a young woman is shown and reads a comment aloud: "You wanted it so badly and finally, you did it." She is filmed from eye level and straight on. Her hair is loose and natural, and she wears a casual outfit. A celebratory moment follows: players are seen hugging and smiling on the court. The camera captures them from waist up, at eye level. Then, three players are shown lying on the floor, overwhelmed with joy. Archival images of the players as children and early sports moments are shown. Next, an intense portrait of an enthusiastic player (Zehra Güneş) appears, hair tied back, brows furrowed, mouth open in a shout. Another player is seen raising her clenched fists upward, eyes closed, in an expression of joy. These moments are filmed directly from the front, with fixed shots. Later, a group of players hold trophies and smile as they look up. Their makeup is minimal. A new comment appears on-screen: "What you've won is so much more than just a match." The comment is voiced by a young man in a black T-shirt, looking directly into the

camera. Then, one of the players (Eda Erdem) is seen throwing her hands up and shouting, her brows are furrowed, her expression is full of passion. She is captured from chest level, frontally. In the next shot, she stands still with her head bowed, eyes closed, focused, holding the ball. Ebrar Karakurt appears next, raising her fist, shouting with intensity, brows furrowed, body leaning forward. These are followed by clips of different players raising fists and shouting on court. Then, a shot from behind shows three players holding hands, filmed from waist level. They are followed by match moments where players raise their arms and shout in unison. These scenes are mostly filmed from mid-body or low angles. Toward the end, player portraits are shown one by one, each smiling as the scene transitions. Various social media comments continue to be voiced by different profiles. In the final sequence, Melissa Vargas is seen jumping into the air to spike the ball; her feet are off the ground, and the camera captures her whole body from a low angle. On-screen text reads: “What they inspire goes far beyond what they’ve achieved.” The final moments feature joyful team celebrations presented. The ad ends with Vodafone’s slogan and logo.

Analysis

Social Constructivism

The commercial portrays female athletes in fields, during training, in moments of celebration, and in portrait sessions. These women are represented not only as agents of physical performance but also as carriers of emotional depth and collective success. Their outfits (jerseys, plain t-shirts) and make-up-free appearances position them not as idealized objects of consumption but as active agents in the public sphere. The recurring use of expressions such as “succeed,” “dream,” and “dare” in the female voiceovers contradicts passive female imagery rooted in societal norms. Representations of women athletes as “difficult” or “impossible” are dismantled; instead, women are framed as symbols of achievement, representation, and hope—signaling a reconstructed female identity.

Gender Performativity

Repetitive bodily actions— players’ clenched fists, celebratory jumps, and low-angle shots of powerful stances— reinforce the idea of femininity as an embodied strength enacted through repetition. Melissa Vargas’s jump while spiking the ball, filmed from a low angle, reinforces the message that female bodies can also signify power. The gestures in ad signal athletic dominance but also emotional openness— players shout, cry, and embrace, blending traditional emotional expressivity associated with femininity with the physical aggression typically coded as masculine. The players wear minimal makeup and standard team uniforms, indicating that their power is not tied to aesthetic labor but to skill, unity, and effort. The camera, often shooting from waist or below, transmits both physical and symbolic strength, suggesting that womanhood is not just something to be observed, but something performed and transformative. The ad also disrupts normative gender performance by placing women in a domain

(competitive sports) historically reserved for male bodies. The emotional arc of the commercial—combining victory, vulnerability, and legacy—constructs femininity as relational and historical. The line “You turned those little girls into the world’s strongest women” metaphorically links generational transformation to a collective gender performance, highlighting how identity is also shaped through social perception and cultural memory. Frequent close-ups, eye-level framing, and varied voiceovers (female, male, child) invite the viewer to recognize and validate the players’ strength. However, this strength is legitimized not through self-declaration alone but through the public’s (and the brand’s) recognition. The Vodafone ad represents female empowerment as a lived, visible, and culturally mediated performance—constructed through repetition, discipline, and public affirmation, aligning it deeply with the theoretical tenets of gender performativity

Feminist Media Theory

Contrary to the male gaze, the female athletes are shown as strong, active, and unpolished. The commercial refrains from sexualizing the female body and instead presents it holistically and functionally. The scenes of Eda Erdem, Zehra Güneş, and Ebrar Karakurt—celebrating with screams, sweating through struggle, and intensely focused—frame the female body as an active and productive subject. Lighting is natural and unfiltered; realism is favored over aesthetic idealization. The emphasis is on women in action rather than on appearance, creating a narrative grounded in collective success and social representation, rather than consumer-driven “empowerment.” Yet, the male voiceover at the commercial’s climax—“what they give is far greater than what they achieve”—marks a symbolic limit. Though women achieve, their success is interpreted, celebrated, and validated through a male voice, subtly re-inscribing their narrative under male authority.

Turkish Context

In the Turkish context, this Vodafone ad subtly signals a transformation in women’s representations without clashing overtly with traditional values. There is no explicit focus on family, motherhood, or morality. Instead, female athletes are depicted as publicly visible individuals known for international accomplishments. The use of black-and-white filters and epic narrative tones arguably positions women not as individuals, but as symbolic figures of national pride. Thus, they are framed as not only achievers but as officially endorsed representatives. Despite this progressive tone, the use of a male voiceover in phrases like “we stand by them” risks reinforcing the idea that women still require support to legitimize their autonomy. The ad delivers both a progressive and controlled narrative of feminism.

Yandex Türkiye | Tüm Kadınlarımızın Dünya Kadınlar Gününü Kutlarız!

Sector: Technology and Digital Services

YouTube link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Df3erD0tAhg>

Auditory Transcript (Translated)

(With a gentle-paced background music, female voice-over) We followed our dreams and achieved many firsts. We touched the sky and always stood by what we believed in. We made our voices heard. As applause rose, we felt the joy of achievement. We never gave up on teaching. We searched for the truth. We made it our duty to heal what we touched. (Music tempo increases.) We, women, followed our dreams and discovered the strength within us. (Male voice-over) Despite all challenges, we celebrate the women who have succeeded in every aspect of life and continue to reach new accomplishments every day. Happy International Women's Day.

Visual Transcript

Figure 25: Yandex Türkiye ad – Woman pilot

Figure 26: Yandex Türkiye ad – Woman teacher

The commercial begins with the word “Our Women” appearing on screen. A series of stylized illustrations follow, each showing different women. In the first scene, the Turkish flag waves in the background, alongside mountains, clouds, and an airplane. A woman stands on a platform wearing beige trousers and brown boots. Her wavy, red hair is loose. In the next illustration, the background depicts a courtroom with the inscription: “Justice is the foundation of the state.” A woman stands on the platform in a black judicial robe, holding documents. She has short black hair and wears a shirt with a tie, a black skirt down to her ankles, and black heels. She lifts the folder as speaking. The following scene shows a woman performing on stage. She wears a burgundy, voluminous stage gown, stage accessories on her head, and gloves on her hands. Her eyes are closed, her arms are raised, and she appears to be singing. Next, a woman is depicted in front of clouds, trees, a house, and artificial lighting. She wears a fedora hat, a fur-collared blouse, a long skirt reaching her ankles, gloves, heels, and make-up. With her eyes closed, she leans forward in a graceful bow. Another scene features a school building, with a Turkish flag waving out front. On a platform with a blackboard and a stool, a female teacher is seated, reading

a book. She wears a shirt with a tie, a jacket, a long skirt, and a classic hat. The next illustration takes place in what appears to be an office. A desk, papers, and a typewriter are present. A woman sits on top of the desk, wearing a tie, shirt, blazer, long skirt, and heels, with a fedora on her head. She is writing in a notebook. In the following scene, the platform resembles a hospital. There's a stretcher, a screen, and IV equipment. The female healthcare worker wears a nurse's cap, a modest blouse, a skirt below the knees, and flat shoes. At the end, the real names of the pioneering women depicted throughout the ad are listed on screen in the following order:

First Female Doctor: Safiye Ali, First Female Pilot: Bedriye Tahir Gökmen, First Female Lawyer: Süreyya Ağaoğlu, First Female Opera Singer: Semiha Berksoy, First Female Theater Actress: Afife Jale, First Female Teacher: Refet Angın, First Female Journalist: Selma Rıza.

The commercial concludes with the Yandex logo and its slogan.

Analysis

Social Constructivism

Yandex's ad depicts women in symbolic, historically charged public spaces such as courtrooms, theaters, schools, and hospitals. Representing roles like lawyer, teacher, doctor, and journalist, these settings mark women's entrance into traditionally male-dominated spaces. Outfits like robes, shirts and ties, and stage costumes make their professional identities visible. The pilot and nurse contrast is notable: the pilot, the only woman wearing pants, is presented in a role coded as masculine, while the nurse wears a below-the-knee skirt and plain uniform—embodying caregiving and compassion. Most female figures wear ankle-length skirts and historically coded clothing, reinforcing a moderate and traditional femininity. The pilot and nurse, as exceptions, symbolically mark the spectrum: one as a pioneer entering male domains, the other as an embodiment of intrinsic womanhood. Through terms like “succeed,” “dream,” and “touch,” the ad opens a space for quietly renegotiating gender norms.

Gender Performativity

The women's gestures and expressions are theatrical and historically referential—speaking with documents, stepping onto the stage, or writing notes. The women enact professional and public roles rather than femininity per se. Each appears in context-appropriate attire—gloves, skirts, heels, hats—visually echoing cultural codes. These repetitions not only reproduce historical aesthetics but reveal how gender performance becomes stabilized through such codes. Showing the real names of the historical figures at the end grounds the performativity in actual history, reinforcing an authentic womanhood narrative. Yet, this performative model remains bound to a single acceptable version of womanhood: secular, respectable and state-aligned. By excluding non-conforming gender performances, the ad unintentionally marginalizes other realities of gender expression.

Feminist Media Theory

At the beginning of the ad, phrase “our women” used can be interpreted as a patriarchal representational practice that prioritizes collective ownership over individual female subjectivity. This discourse positions women as bearers of societal honor, while relegating their existence as autonomous individuals to the background. By framing women through such possessive expressions, the advertisement reproduces the protective and paternalistic codes of patriarchal ideology. Although women’s visibility in the public sphere is legitimized, this visibility is not anchored in their own voices, but rather confined within an institutional framework that speaks on behalf of society. In this context, female strength is represented not as autonomous subjecthood, but as the symbolic embodiment of national value. While the phrase “We, women” appears to emphasize collective solidarity, the statement “followed our dreams and discovered the strength within us” reduces empowerment to an individual journey of inner discovery. This narrative, as critiqued by feminist media theory, obscures women’s collective struggles against systemic inequalities by framing female strength within the confines of personal determination and inspirational storytelling. The use of illustrations in the ad bypasses typical sexualization and objectification. This aesthetic choice reframes women not as objects to be looked at but as subjects of stories and thought. The female figures are not depicted with erotic connotations, but with professional and holistic identities. While the aesthetic idealizes them, it avoids eroticization. Using a female narrator centers internal experience over external judgment. However, the shift in narration at the end—where a male voice celebrates women’s success—undermines this internal focus. It symbolically returns authority to a male figure, reinforcing the patriarchal structure even in a tribute intended to empower women.

Turkish Context

The ad builds a national narrative around historical women from Türkiye’s modernization era. Iconic female figures from Atatürk’s reforms—doctors, pilots, lawyers—are honored. Women are portrayed as both “state women” and “social pioneers.” Though themes like motherhood or morality aren’t stated, the figures’ seriousness and discipline signal these values implicitly. Their clothing (skirts, jackets, hats) encode a secular, urban, Republican ideal. This creates a unifying visual language that represents modern Turkish womanhood as rational, restrained, and mission-driven. Yet, by exclusively focusing on historical milestones, the ad romanticizes the past and risks depoliticizing the present. The absence of contemporary voices, intersectional struggles, and everyday realities makes this tribute feel symbolic rather than systemic. While the ad honors women as historical subjects, its reliance on idealized memory and elite archetypes ultimately limits its emancipatory potential.

Technology & Telecommunications Intra-Group Analysis

The Technology & Telecommunications group comprises two commercials from distinct sub-sectors: telecommunications (Vodafone) and digital technology services (Yandex Türkiye). Both ads were

launched for International Women’s Day and center on representations of strong women as part of broader corporate narratives. Despite differences in visual style—one employing realistic footage, the other animated illustrations—both commercials operate within a cultural discourse that seeks to reframe female empowerment through national symbolism and collective success. This sector group analysis reveals how strength is visualized and narrated in an industry that shapes not only consumption but also digital identity and symbolic communication.

Both commercials mobilize the language of achievement, legacy, and collective pride, constructing “strong women” as emblematic figures of national and moral progress. In Vodafone’s ad, strength is built through dynamic physical actions—jumping, shouting, spiking, celebrating—as well as emotional resilience. Similarly, Yandex’s commercial depicts women in historically male-dominated professions such as law, medicine, and aviation, suggesting that strength lies in breaching professional boundaries and claiming public space. From a social constructivist perspective, both ads reconstruct womanhood as a learned, performative identity inscribed through institutions and historical scripts. Vodafone reclaims the sporting arena as a site of female achievement, while Yandex rewrites national memory by visually situating women at the foundation of Türkiye’s modern professions. Both create strong female figures not as isolated individuals but as agents formed through cultural institutions—sports federations, courts, hospitals, schools—and thus mirror the way gender is socially constructed across time. Gender performativity also marks a crucial commonality. In Vodafone, the repeated bodily gestures—fist raises, celebratory shouts, low-angle jumps—mirror the notion of gender as “a stylized repetition of acts.” Likewise, in Yandex, each illustrated woman enacts gender through stylized, professional rituals—holding gavels, singing, teaching, writing—underscoring how gender identity is created through the repetition of culturally coded performances. These acts stabilize womanhood through gestures that affirm collective labor and visibility. Both advertisements also exhibit post-feminist and affective strategies (Gill, 2007). Instead of calling for structural change, they focus on celebrating individual and historical accomplishments. The empowering tone is filtered through corporate voice-overs, emotional music, and idealized language like “dream,” “strength,” “hope,” and “legacy.” This aestheticization of empowerment is consistent with Gill’s critique of how commercial media repackages feminist values as personal victories, stripped of political urgency but made palatable for broad audiences.

Despite shared rhetorical and visual motifs, the two commercials diverge significantly in their representational strategies and ideological frames. Vodafone’s ad presents a contemporary, embodied, and emotionally raw narrative. The female athletes—real-life figures such as Zehra Güneş, Ebrar Karakurt, and Eda Erdem—are shown in action, sweat, and vulnerability. The ad refrains from glamorizing their appearances; instead, it captures their expressions of pain, joy, and determination through close-ups and eye-level camera angles, creating a realistic portrait of resilience. Yandex, by contrast, adopts a historicized and idealized aesthetic. The women are not current individuals but symbolic renderings of early Republican pioneers. The use of vintage outfits, stage-like settings, and

formal body language reinforces a more moderate, secular femininity coded with nationalistic overtones. The emphasis is not on the physical body but on visual symbols of social progress: the pilot uniform, the opera dress. While Vodafone depicts women in the present moment, Yandex positions them within a nostalgic myth of nationhood. This distinction also reflects a difference in performative emphasis. Vodafone’s strength is dynamic and collective—female athletes physically express power in the public eye. Yandex’s women, on the other hand, embody a more restrained performance of gender, rooted in national duty and elite respectability. Even though both represent achievement, one celebrates active disruption (sporting success against the odds), while the other idealizes integration into the existing national fabric (professionalism within state institutions). Vodafone’s ad breaks away from conventional moral tropes like motherhood or modesty, instead portraying women as global athletes and public icons. This positions the ad as relatively progressive, though the use of a male voice-over in the final moments introduces a subtle tension—suggesting that even in celebration, male validation remains necessary. Yandex, meanwhile, constructs a nationalistic and conservative feminism, grounded in Atatürk-era modernization. Its depiction of women as “the firsts” reinforces a state-aligned vision of womanhood—heroic but domesticated, pioneering yet controlled.

The Technology & Telecommunications group reveals how femvertising can shift between bodily realism and symbolic abstraction while maintaining recurring themes of national pride, accomplishment, and perseverance. While Vodafone’s ad embraces contemporary athleticism and emotional resonance, Yandex constructs an idealized archive of Turkish femininity—celebrating progress while subtly reinforcing tradition. These contrasts illustrate the flexibility of femvertising across the technology sector, suggesting that even in future-oriented industries, gendered storytelling remains tethered to national narratives and respectability politics. Technology & Telecommunications group frames female strength in relation to cultural legacy and public contribution. In doing so, it gestures toward structural empowerment—though not without reinscribing patriarchal boundaries in subtler forms.

4.7. HOME & DOMESTIC INDUSTRIES: DUST, DUTY, DYNASTY

Atia Interiors | 8 Mart Dünya Kadınlar Günü Reklam Filmi

Sector: Furniture, Interiors, Home Textiles

YouTube link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Ko71yQma7Gs>

Auditory Transcript (Translated)

(Male voice-over) “You can’t do it. You can’t do it. You can’t do it. You can’t! What are you going to do among all those men? Go take care of your children. You’ll be crushed under such heavy work, do

something suited to your strength. While there's all that ironing waiting at home, are you going to carry firewood?" (Female voice-over enters, with rising background music) "They don't see what I'm capable of. They don't see what we're capable of. That we can both raise children and do hard labor... That we can both cook meals and provide for our families... We've never been able to make them understand. Because labor has no gender. Happy International Working Women's Day, March 8."

Visual Transcript

Figure 27: Atia Interiors ad – Woman carrying heavy

Figure 28: Atia Interiors ad – Workers together

The commercial opens with a headscarf-wearing woman in work attire, a long-sleeved, collared shirt, looking directly into a camera positioned at eye level in a furniture workshop. The camera captures her from the waist up. This is followed by another woman wearing a black headscarf and a turtleneck sweater in a similar workshop setting, also gazing directly into the camera from the same angle. In the next frame, a woman with glasses, her hair natural and unstyled, wears a jacket and holds a pen while looking into the camera. She stands in a workshop space. Another headscarf-wearing woman, dressed in work clothes, is then shown looking directly at the camera; in the background, a male worker can be seen working. A full-body shot follows of a headscarf-wearing woman actively working in the workshop. Then, a scene shows a woman crafting with her hands in a workplace where two male coworkers are also visible in the background. In the next frame, a man and woman are seen working together on a bathroom design. Following scenes display women actively participating in manual labor alongside men. Women wearing headscarves are seen placing wooden panels on shelves, engaging in tasks that require physical strength. Other women are shown drawing, taking measurements, cutting and shaping wood, and carrying construction materials. These are presented in either full-body or mid-body shots. In one poignant scene, a woman's hand is shown holding a baby's hand. This is followed by a shot of two headscarf-wearing women lifting a heavy load together. Next, a woman is shown cooking in a kitchen, followed by another woman handling financial paperwork and using a calculator. The final scene features a woman wearing safety goggles, an apron, a bandana, and with a sledgehammer on her shoulder, looking directly into the eye-level camera. A man wearing a shirt, apron, and goggles stands slightly behind her to the side, with his arms crossed over his chest, also looking into the camera. To

conclude, the images of all the women featured throughout the commercial reappear in a sequence. The ad ends with the brand logo displayed on screen.

Analysis

Social Constructivism

The external voice in the ad uttering phrases like “This is a man’s job,” “Take care of the children,” or “Do the ironing,” reflects entrenched societal expectations and gender-based labor divisions. Meanwhile, portraying women engaging in physical labor, multitasking, and demonstrating technical competence challenges these normative roles. Women are not only depicted through domestic responsibilities but also through public and manual labor, presenting a representation that questions the fixedness of gender roles. The commercial places women in physically demanding, traditionally male workspaces like furniture workshops. They are shown carrying wood, cutting planks, drafting designs, and doing calculations—framing them as more than mothers or homemakers. Their clothing—aprons, headscarves, glasses, jackets—marks them as working-class but also professionally competent. The women’s dialogue directly challenges patriarchal norms, with lines like “I wasn’t aware of my strength” underscoring their resistance to societal expectations. These women embody subjectivity in defiance of the “you can’t do it” narrative. Ultimately, the message that “labor has no gender” rejects socially constructed distinctions between “men’s work” and “women’s work,” highlighting how gender roles in working life are culturally shaped.

Gender Performativity

The ad foregrounds the female body’s performative capacity in male-coded labor. Women are filmed performing lifting loads or taking measurements, with focused, controlled gestures. In the advertisement, women continuously perform the identity of the “strong woman” not only through occupational practices but also through their posture in front of the camera, direct gazes, and assertive actions. This repetition deviates from traditional “feminine” representations and constitutes a repetition with a difference. The “strong woman” is portrayed as calm, skilled, and nurturing—this repeated image reflects a gendered pattern of empowerment: progressive in visibility, yet conservative in its use of familiar, socially approved roles. Rather than challenging norms, such repetition often reinforces them, revealing both the limits and the potential of femvertising as a transformative discourse. Their natural, makeup-free appearance displaces normative femininity. Stylistic elements like the headscarf, apron, and work goggles affirm Butler’s “re-signification” of gender. Frequent direct eye contact with the camera signals subjecthood. Womanhood is thus not presented as a passive identity to be worn, but as an active, resistant performance that reconstitutes and challenges gender expectations.

Feminist Media Theory

The visual language aligns with feminist theory: the female body is not objectified or subjected to the male gaze. Shots are mostly medium or wide, not eroticized close-ups. Lighting is natural, expressions are authentic. The camera captures women through labor, not aesthetics. Empowerment is rooted in action, not display. In the final scene, a woman holding a sledgehammer and gazing directly into the camera exemplifies repetition with a difference, rewriting power symbols through female embodiment. The man standing behind, arms folded, may be interpreted as either support or symbolic control, echoing the feminist media critique that female subjectivity in public space still negotiates male approval. The ad constructs political visibility, not performative empowerment. However, the silent male figure behind the woman at the end raises questions: is he supportive, supervisory, or a symbol of necessary approval? This ambiguity reflects the ongoing negotiation of female autonomy in patriarchal contexts.

Turkish Context

The ad blends modern and traditional codes. Most women wear headscarves, signaling religious conservatism, yet their presence in the workspace suggests modernization on local terms. The portrayal of women balancing work, childcare, and domestic duties reflects societal expectations of women's multitasking. While empowering, it also risks normalizing the burden of invisible labor. Themes like family, morality, and motherhood are subtly embedded. The ad aligns with state narratives, reinforcing the ideal of the "hardworking and moral Turkish woman."

Yurtbay Seramik | 8 Mart Dünya Kadınlar Günü Kutlu Olsun

Sector: Ceramics and Building Materials

YouTube link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=keEN1mtdZLo>

Auditory Transcript (Translated)

(Male voice-over) Women are the ones who keep this world turning. Their imagination... Their compassion... Their intelligence... No one else could carry such responsibility on their shoulders. They light the way. They show the path. They ignite hope. With every step, they brighten the future. On the streets, in the office, at home... Everywhere you can imagine... Always with sacrifice, always with dedication, always with love. There is nothing a woman can't do, Nothing she can't achieve if she sets her mind to it. Because women are the ones who keep this world turning. And the women of this country are stronger than anyone. Happy March 8th, International Women's Day. Yurtbay Ceramics.

Visual Transcript

Figure 29: Yurtbay Seramik ad – A mother with a kid

Figure 30: Yurtbay Seramik ad – Woman harvesting apples

The commercial opens with the silhouette of a woman performing ballet in a living room setting. She is wearing ballet attire, and the camera captures her from a slightly low angle. On screen, the sentence appears: “Women are the ones who keep this world turning.” The next scene features a woman outdoors, dressed in a red coat and a beanie, smiling as she looks upward. The camera frames her at eye level. Then, a woman in a yellow short-sleeved blouse is seen smiling alongside a small girl seated at a table. After that, a woman is shown conducting research with a microscope. She wears safety goggles and gloves, along with a lab coat and shirt. The shot is taken from a portrait angle and slightly from below. In the following scene, the hands of a female pilot, manicured and adorned with nail polish, are shown gripping the aircraft yoke. Her face is not visible in the frame. Next, a woman dressed in a plain white shirt and trousers is seen outdoors, playing with her small daughter on a blanket laid on the grass. She lifts the child onto her back and smiles. This is followed by an image of a short-haired female teacher wearing optical glasses, smiling directly at the camera in a waist-up shot. Behind her, both male and female students are visible. Transitions between scenes show various women: a woman painting on canvas with a young girl and a boy; another holding hiking gear; a silhouette of a woman drawing back curtains to reveal a sunlit view from inside the home; and a woman in a trench coat, white shirt, and cream-toned formal attire walking down a hallway, smiling at the camera. A young woman with natural, loose hair, wearing a white shirt and gray blazer, is then shown working on her laptop with a smartwatch on her wrist.

In another home setting, a woman wearing optical glasses spends time with her two children, playing with them while also working on her computer. This is followed by a scene of two women in traditional clothing with headscarves working in a tea field, holding tea-harvesting tools. Then, a conservatively dressed woman wearing a long-sleeved blouse, knitted vest, and headscarf is seen picking apples from the top of a tree. Next, a woman in full laboratory gear (lab coat, gloves, mask, goggles, and cap) is shown from a portrait angle, holding a glass tube directly toward the camera. Following this, a woman dressed in a black crop top with her hair tied back and boxing gloves on is training with a punching bag. The camera captures her directly from the front. Further scenes show a woman outdoors spinning with her arms wide open, dressed in a white shirt and sweater, turning joyfully in nature. Another woman

stands with her arms open in front of a water source, seen from behind. The commercial ends with a woman boarding a ferry and gazing toward the sunny landscape of Istanbul. The ad ends with the logo.

Analysis

Social Constructivism

The ad represents women across multiple spheres—home, lab, school, nature, tea fields, boxing rings, ferries, offices, airplanes—offering fluid transitions between private and public roles. Women are not limited to caregiving but associated with intellectual and physical labor. Their clothing signals class and profession: lab coats, business suits, traditional outfits, boxing gear, and casual wear symbolize diverse roles. “Women keep this world turning” elevates women through traditional values like compassion and sacrifice, while also constructing them as subjects of public power. This reflects the social constructivist view that gender roles are historically and contextually built.

Gender Performativity

The advertisement’s portrayal of women in diverse roles—mother, scientist, teacher, athlete, artist—demonstrates that gender is not a fixed identity but a performance constituted through repeated social actions. These varied representations highlight how femininity is not confined to domestic roles but is enacted across multiple public and private spheres. The ad depicts repeated gestures—punching a bag, working with a microscope, twirling in nature, playing with a child—as embodied expressions of feminine power. The repetition shows womanhood not as passive or aesthetic, but active and multifaceted. Low and eye-level shots position women as both subjects and equal citizens. The boxer’s crop top versus the tea worker’s traditional garb illustrates not contradiction but cultural reproduction of power performances. However, since the performances of women are consistently framed through traditionally “feminine” values like love, sacrifice, and hope, they risk reinforcing normative gender codes rather than subverting them. In this sense, although the ad showcases gender as performative, it falls short of Butler’s concept of “repetition with a difference,” instead aestheticizing female strength through emotional and metaphorical narratives that reproduce, rather than challenge, existing gender norms.

Feminist Media Theory

In the ad, women are mostly portrayed in full or portrait shots, with minimal body fragmentation. The ad avoids the male gaze, favoring active representation. Lighting is soft but realistic; women appear natural, sometimes makeup-free. The empowerment message is embedded in action, not aesthetics. Although empowerment is central, the male narrator introduces patriarchal codes. Women are not posing; they are working, playing, and moving—active subjects. However, the advertisement shows female power through personal inspiration and emotional attributes, reproducing the codes of

“emotionally charged feminism.” A representation of women as “sources of inspiration” adorned with traditional feminine values—such as sacrifice, love, and intuition—is foregrounded. The phrase “women are the ones who keep this world turning” conceals structural inequalities, reducing women’s social power to a metaphorical and sentimental narrative. This is followed by the statement “the women of this country are stronger than anyone,” which romanticizes the burdens women carry. Ultimately, the narrative shifts away from the idea of collective transformation and instead produces a representational practice that confines womanhood to emotional responsibilities.

Turkish Context

The ad presents a hybrid of traditional and modern femininity. Rural women in tea fields, headscarved women in production, crop-top athletes, and lab professionals represent Türkiye’s social diversity. Yet, traits like sacrifice and compassion still idealize femininity. The slogan “Women keep this world turning” conveys symbolic strength but reinforces idealized womanhood. The message aligns with state narratives—women are hardworking, family-oriented, and beneficial to the nation—offering a feminism compatible with cultural unity.

Beko | Kadının İşi, Gücü!

Sector: Household & Everyday Consumer Goods

YouTube link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9Kuh3GsJfvo>

Auditory Transcript (Translated)

Girl 1: Come on, let’s divide up our roles for the game. I’ll pretend I’m cooking.

Girl 2: Then I’ll pretend I’m arranging the furniture.

Boy 1: But I’m stuck with hoovering? I’m not doing that, I’m a boy!

Girl 2: What does that have to do with being a boy?

Woman 1: That’s how I grew up, Zeynep.

Woman 2: Laundry, dishes... it was always on me.

Woman 1: They always said, “Laundry, dishes, ironing, that’s your job.”

Woman 3: And one day, you’ll teach your own daughter, too.

Woman 1: That's not what they meant. But... all of this really has become my job now.

Male Employee: Boss, can I get your signature?

Woman 1: So, Zeynep, your job is to be a strong woman who stands on her own feet. And whatever your dream job is, that's the one you should do.

(Male voice-over for the brand) Beko supports equal opportunity for a healthy society. With the "100 Women Dealers" project, women entrepreneurs are becoming their own bosses with exclusive incentives and investment advantages. Because we know: A woman's job is her power.

Visual Transcript

Figure 31: Beko ad – Children playing house

Figure 32: Beko ad – "Can I get a signature, boss?"

The commercial opens with a domestic interior scene where two middle-aged men are seated on armchairs while a woman leans in and smiles politely at one of them. The home is decorated in a traditionally Turkish style: a lace doily on the coffee table, Turkish coffee cups, framed motifs on the wall, and an old rotary phone. In an adjacent room, children are seen playing on the floor. On-screen text indicates that the year is 1987. The camera shifts focus to the children's room: three girls and one boy are playing with toys. The girls wear soft-toned tops and colorful bottoms; one wears a white shirt under a black dress. The boy is dressed in a dark sweater and jeans. In the game, the girls take on household roles like cooking and arranging furniture, while the boy resists doing the cleaning task, associating it with femininity. The scene shifts to 1992. A setting resembling a traditional Turkish women's gathering ("gün") is shown. Women wear skirt-suit sets and have styled hair. The table is full of homemade foods. In the background, an older woman (a mother figure) serves tea to a young girl in a school uniform. Meanwhile, a middle-aged woman is explaining to another that laundry and dishwashing are a woman's duty. Next, it moves to 2000. A middle-aged woman is shown ironing. In the background, a man, presumably her husband, is drinking tea while seated. A young girl, sitting nearby, is reading a book. The woman says, "One day you'll teach your own daughter." In the present-day scene, the girl is now an adult professional in a modern work environment. She wears a blue shirt and a simple, elegant necklace. Her makeup and hairstyle are natural. She is seen speaking to a little

girl, Zeynep, about her future. A man holding a folder approaches her for a signature, indicating her managerial role. In the final moment, she holds the little girl's hands and offers her motivational words. The camera films her from a slight low angle, left diagonal, focusing on her expression. The ad then shifts to a montage of diverse women supported by Beko. These women represent different regions and styles, some wearing headscarves, some not; some with short hair, others with long. They all wear formal outfits such as blazers and shirts, with minimal accessories. The commercial concludes with Beko's slogan and logo on screen.

Analysis

Social Constructivism

By chronologically portraying domestic scenes from 1987 to the present day, the commercial reveals how gendered divisions of labor—such as associating women with cooking, cleaning, and ironing—are learned and normalized through intergenerational discourse. Lines like “laundry, dishes, ironing—that’s your job” and “one day, you’ll teach your daughter too” illustrate how societal expectations are reproduced within the family, positioning women’s labor as culturally coded and naturalized. The ad emphasizes domestic interiors, gendered toys, traditional Turkish aesthetics, and familial hierarchies to show how roles are socially scripted and performed. The children’s roleplay scene directly reflects learned gender norms: while girls imitate domestic caretaking in a houseplay, the boy rejects Hoovering on the basis of being male, reinforcing the socially constructed binary between “male” and “female” labor. The girl wearing a black dress over a white shirt—visually coded as a figure that does not conform to norms—stands out among her peers dressed in light pastel-colored tops, subtly signaling an early resistance to traditional gender roles through style. Moreover, by saying to the boy, “What does that have to do with being a girl?”, she moves the representation beyond the visual and into the verbal realm, taking a position that challenges normative roles on both levels. However, the shift to the present-day woman—confident, managerial, and professionally dressed—marks a symbolic rupture in this inherited script. She reframes female labor not as a burden passed down, but as a self-determined path. This narrative arc challenges the fixity of gender roles by suggesting that they can be reconstructed through new models of behavior and aspiration. The final brand message “A woman’s job is her power” ties empowerment to labor, echoing a neoliberal framework where worth is often defined through productivity. Despite its progressive gesture, the ad subtly re-inscribes gender within a capitalist logic that validates women’s strength through economic contribution. The ad aims to deconstruct and partially re-script the gendered meanings of “work” and “power.”

Gender Performativity

The Beko advertisement reenacts gender as a performative construct by juxtaposing generational scripts of femininity. It portrays the “strong woman” through recurring visual and thematic elements such as

emotional resilience, multitasking, and symbolic labor—these shared motifs reveal that empowerment is constructed through performative repetition. This reflects what Judith Butler (1990) defines as the reproduction of gender norms through stylized acts. Through scenes spanning from 1987 to the present day, the commercial demonstrates how normative gender roles are internalized through repetition and socialization. These early performances are later disrupted by the adult woman’s transformation into a professional figure, symbolizing the subversion of inherited gender scripts. The shift from “laundry, dishes, ironing” to managerial authority embodies a “repetition with a difference” where past gendered acts are re-performed with new meanings. As Butler’s thesis on performativity suggests, childhood role assignments, the intergenerational transfer of domestic responsibilities, and modeled behavior all reveal gender as a repeated, embodied performance. The line “You’ll teach your daughter too” encapsulates this cycle. Yet in the present-day scene, this cycle is ruptured by a confident, professional woman who speaks assertively and interacts meaningfully with a child. The use of low-angle shots positions her as empowered, while her understated, professional attire subtly reinforces gender as a stylized and performative expression rather than a fixed, natural identity.

Feminist Media Theory

The ad illustrates the normalization of gendered work. The voices of older women affirming these roles, childhood scenes of house-play, portray mechanisms of patriarchal socialization. These representations echo critiques like media often reproduces limiting gender scripts. While the advertisement introduces a break from this cycle and transforms by portraying a confident, professional woman, its empowerment narrative remains confined to individual transformation rather than collective resistance. The ad reflects postfeminist discourse, which emphasizes autonomy and overlooks structural inequalities. Consequently, the commercial risks diluting the transformative potential of feminist critique by offering motivation in place of systemic challenge. Visually, the advertisement avoids objectification. Women are not reduced to aesthetic objects; rather, they are portrayed as decision-makers and active participants. Camera angles favor medium or portrait-level shots, avoiding fetishistic close-ups. The lighting is soft yet natural, contributing to a realistic tone. Notably, the empowerment rhetoric is supported by tangible corporate action, such as the “100 Female Dealers Project,” which promotes female entrepreneurship. Overall, the commercial makes room for a more holistic and agency-centered portrayal of women.

Turkish Context

Beko’s ad reflects Türkiye’s collective memory through generational visuals—lace doilies, wall phones, “tea party” culture, and shifting family roles. The ad draws a direct parallel with Türkiye’s gendered cultural memory by depicting how young girls are associated with domestic roles from an early age and how these norms are passed down from one generation of women to the next. Women of various backgrounds—headscarved and not, from diverse cities—appear by the ad’s end. While themes like motherhood and education are subtly present, women’s participation in the workforce is idealized. The

“100 Women Dealers Project” align with Türkiye’s growing state-led policies promoting female entrepreneurship. In this sense, the advertisement does not offer a critique that opposes Türkiye’s existing social structure but rather presents a narrative that remains within it while attempting to stretch its boundaries. It proposes a form of empowerment that is not oppositional but system-compatible and institutionally endorsed.

Home & Domestic Industries Intra-Group Analysis

The Home & Domestic Industries group comprises three advertisements from diverse yet thematically linked sectors: Furniture and Interiors (Atia Interiors), Ceramics and Building Materials (Yurtbay Seramik), and Household & Everyday Consumer Goods (Beko). These industries, traditionally associated with the private sphere and the feminized domain of domestic labor, offer a unique ground to examine how femvertising strategies recode the image of the “strong woman.” While the products vary in function and market orientation, each ad grapples with notions of labor, strength, care, and womanhood in culturally resonant ways. This section explores the internal consistencies and divergences in how female empowerment is visually, verbally, and ideologically constructed, asking whether strength is framed as resistance, continuity, or integration within gendered traditions.

All three commercials foreground labor—manual, emotional, and managerial—as a central metaphor of feminine power. This convergence is especially significant in a cultural context like Türkiye, where domesticity, motherhood, and sacrifice are often the cornerstones of idealized womanhood. In Atia Interiors, women are depicted performing heavy industrial labor traditionally coded as masculine: carrying planks, designing furniture, and lifting sledgehammers. The persistent use of eye-level camera angles, full-body framing, and direct gazes highlights their agency and subjectivity. Butler’s (1990) theory of gender performativity is particularly salient here, as these women embody “power” through iterative, laborious acts that redefine what is legible as feminine. Similarly, Yurtbay Seramik’s montage of women across professions and social roles presents a medley of embodied performances—boxing, piloting, caregiving, researching—each a repeated act within a specific cultural script. While the aesthetic leans toward the poetic and celebratory, the underlying repetition of empowered gestures aligns with what Butler terms “repetition with a difference.” Here, femininity is not negated but expanded, rewritten through culturally acceptable yet dynamic forms of subjectivity. In the Beko advertisement, intergenerational gender performativity is made explicit: childhood games, motherly warnings, and eventual disruption of the “domestic woman” trope. The slogan “a woman’s job is her power” encapsulates the strategy of resignifying work—a feminist media tactic Gill (2007) associates with post-feminist sensibilities where empowerment is reframed as choice and aspiration. Yet unlike the celebratory abstraction in Yurtbay’s ad, Beko roots this transformation in realism: a girl in black defies pink-coded normativity; a professional woman signs documents in an office. All three advertisements use non-objectifying visual language. Medium shots, natural lighting, and minimal makeup or filters contribute to what feminist media theorists have long called for: representations of women as active

subjects rather than passive objects (Mulvey, 1975). The choice of voice-over—two male narrators, one female—also reflects how voice authority is still mediated in patriarchal registers, but simultaneously challenged through female visuals and labor scenes.

Despite their shared focus on labor and empowerment, each advertisement constructs “strength” through distinct socio-cultural lenses. *Atia Interiors* centers on collective resistance. Working-class women—most wearing headscarves—are positioned in visible, physical confrontation with societal doubt (“you can’t do it”). This direct appeal to patriarchal exclusion renders the ad politically charged and socially grounded. The sledgehammer becomes a feminist symbol of reclamation, and the ambiguity of the male figure in the final shot invites critique: Is he ally or overseer? In contrast, *Yurtbay Seramik* adopts a more universalist and idealized tone. Strength is linked to values like sacrifice, compassion, and imagination—traits long feminized in nationalist rhetoric. The ad’s power lies in its emotive montage and symbolic multiplicity: ballerinas, pilots, lab scientists, and tea workers coexist in a seamless visual flow. However, this idealization risks flattening structural inequalities by suggesting that “all women” already possess this power equally, thereby depoliticizing labor. Unlike *Atia*’s realism, *Yurtbay*’s femininity is stylized, more aspirational than insurgent. *Beko*, meanwhile, delivers a narrative of evolution. From 1987 to the present, gender norms are passed down, negotiated, and ultimately subverted. The “good girl” pastel clothing is contrasted with the monochrome defiance of the child in black—her rebellion visualized even before verbalized. This diachronic structure allows the ad to critique tradition while honoring it—a delicate feminist balancing act. Its focus on entrepreneurship via the “100 Women Dealers Project” grounds empowerment in concrete economic opportunities, offering a tangible feminist praxis within a neoliberal framework. Furthermore, stylistic codes vary: *Atia*’s industrial grit contrasts with *Yurtbay*’s bright naturalism and *Beko*’s nostalgic domestic realism. Clothing cues range from aprons and work goggles to formal blazers and vests, demarcating not only different social classes but also symbolic registers of femininity: functional, aesthetic, and managerial.

The Home & Domestic Industries group illustrates how femvertising can navigate the fine line between tradition and transformation. While all three ads deploy labor as a medium of empowerment, they do so through varied registers: *Atia* through physical resistance, *Yurtbay* through emotional symbolism, and *Beko* through temporal evolution. Together, they demonstrate that “strength” in advertising is not a fixed archetype but a negotiable, context-dependent performance.

4.8. INDUSTRIAL & AGRICULTURAL SECTORS: IN LABOR AND IN UNITY

Syngenta TR | 8 Mart Dünya Kadınlar Günü | Güçlü kadınlar, özgür yarınlar!

Sector: Agricultural Science & Crop Protection

YouTube link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=SwqWm8UJsN8>

Auditory Transcript (Translated)

(Female voice-over) They told you, “You can’t.” You didn’t listen. (Music with an accelerating tempo begins.) You tore up the rules, overcame the obstacles, broke down the taboos one by one. Because you fought not just for yourself, but for all of us. You. You. You. All of you. All of us. We are strong women building a world that is equal and free. Happy International Women’s Day.

Visual Transcript

Figure 33: Syngenta ad – Low-angle camera perspective

Figure 34: Syngenta ad – Woman as a supervisor in construction

The commercial opens with a little girl looking at the camera while facing a nighttime city view. This is followed by a scene where an elderly man shakes his head disapprovingly, and then several young men, filmed from a low angle, angrily point and gesture toward the camera, shouting. These male characters use harsh expressions and commanding gestures. In the next scene, a woman seated at a desk throws a paper toward the camera with frustration. Again, the camera is positioned low. Then, outside an office building, a woman in a blue shirt gives a slight smile to the camera. The angle is quite low. The following scene shows a woman working at a computer in an architecture office. Her hair is tied up, and she is wearing a blue blouse. Then, outdoors, a woman in a crop top trains with boxing gloves. This scene, too, is filmed from a very low angle. In the next scene, a woman is shown working with a microscope. The portrait-style shot reveals she has two earrings, one of them a piercing. Her hair is tied back, she appears without makeup, and she wears a white lab coat over a white shirt. Following that, a woman doctor is seen working at a computer in a hospital setting. She wears a blue shirt, simple jewelry, a lab coat, and a watch on her wrist. The shot is taken from eye level, slightly from the right. Her hair is down and natural-looking. Next, a woman in a black blouse, black trousers, and white shirt is seen giving a presentation while standing. Another woman is shown watching her in the same frame. Then, a woman

with blonde, wavy hair and sunglasses is driving a car and looking out the window. She wears a white blouse. In the following scene, young girls smile at the camera at eye level. After that, a darker-skinned woman with natural hair, wearing a long-sleeved blouse, is seen driving a tractor. Next, at a construction site, a woman wearing an orange hard hat (indicating a supervisory role), a white shirt, and a work vest looks directly at the camera. Her arms are crossed. The background shows an outdoor construction area. Next, a woman in a navy-and-white shirt and a blue bandana on her head is seen at home, looking at the camera. She wears light makeup. In the following scene, in a kitchen background, three women sit together on a couch, leaning on one another and smiling at the camera. They wear yellow, green, and pink dresses, and their nails are painted. In the next scene, three women, elderly, middle-aged, and young, wearing classic shirts and pastel-toned blouses (pink, blue, and purple), embrace each other and look directly at the camera in a home setting. Their hair is natural and their appearance modest. The final scene shows a young woman walking in an outdoor space resembling a university campus. She wears a white blouse and blue shirt, holding a notebook and a pen. Her hair is down, her face is natural. She walks with her chin held high, smiling and looking straight ahead. In the last frame, an elderly woman is shown walking through the city, smiling. She wears a blue coat and a blue checkered scarf, and her hair is natural. The camera films her from a low angle. The commercial ends with the brand's logo.

Analysis

Social Constructivism

In the Syngenta commercial, women are shown across diverse settings—laboratory, hospital, office, car, home, and construction site. This variety illustrates how gender is constructed via social norms and cultural practices. Women appear both in traditionally “female-coded” domestic and caregiving spaces and in physically and technically defined “male” areas such as construction, agriculture, and engineering. Their attire—ranging from crop tops to lab coats, bandanas to safety vests—reflects a spectrum of class and occupational positions. Through direct refutation of sexist taboos and the phrase “they said you can’t—but you can,” the narration advocates for building an “equal and free world” centered on female agency, destabilizing normative discourse.

Gender Performativity

Scenes of a woman working with boxing gloves, another young woman walking confidently with chin lifted in university settings, all performatively re-stage images of strength. The camera frequently shoots from low angles to reinforce their powerful presence. Showing women actively performing tasks—under the microscope, driving a tractor, or leading meetings—underscores that gender is performed through agency, not passivity. Feminine and masculine style codes are woven together via natural hair, minimal makeup, and workwear, signaling a gender performance that transcends traditional norms. The

final shot of an older woman walking firmly with a smile may symbolize intergenerational transmission of empowered femininity.

Feminist Media Theory

When evaluated through the lens of feminist media theory, the advertisement stands out for offering a non-sexualized, inclusive, and diverse portrayal of women. Females are portrayed as holistic subjects. The camera privileges their active labor and professional identities. Their bodies are not eroticized. Instead, we see women working, deciding, producing, and leading—representing empowerment through visibility and action. Camera angles, natural lighting, and minimal makeup present women as subjects rather than objects. Phrases like “They told you you can’t—you didn’t listen” frame female power through personal resistance and motivation. Although the slogan “Strong Women, Free Tomorrows” gestures toward a collective vision, the content ultimately individualizes this claim. The slogan “We are strong women building a world that is equal and free” positions women as active agents of social change; however, this collective discourse may be limited by the advertisement’s focus on individual success and personal resistance. If collectivity remains only at the surface level, the message risks becoming inspirational yet detached from structural transformation—resulting in a feminism that is motivating but lacks systemic depth. While the advertisement marks a positive step in terms of representation, it remains limited in critical depth, reproducing a model of empowerment built on personal triumph rather than collective transformation.

Türkiye Context

The ad reflects Türkiye’s cultural diversity by featuring women of various ages, ethnic backgrounds, and socioeconomic statuses. The absence of explicit motherhood references, offset by the appearance of children, suggests generational change. Lines like “an equal and free world” and “you fought for all of us” frame female progress as collective political action—an alternative to the state’s domestic-focused female narrative. Overall, women are coded as middle-class, educated, industrious, and confident—positioned as active agents in society.

Cengiz Holding | #KadınGücününYanında !

Sector: Multi-sector Industrial & Service

YouTube link: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=2i2_NJvYn8Y

Auditory Transcript (Translated)

(Female voice-over) We share the power of unity with excitement. Every moment of mine is valuable. I always secure my work. I carry my responsibility with me. But I also know how to enjoy life. My joy

is shared. Our strength is one. I'm always ready, right on time. I'm here, by your side. We're not rivals, we're a team. Happy International Women's Day of ours.

Visual Transcript

Figure 35: Cengiz Holding ad – Solidarity among female rivals

Figure 36: Cengiz Holding ad – Team spirit

The commercial begins with a scene in front of a sports complex where Eti Bakır employees are welcoming the female handball players of Kastamonu Dinamik Sports Club with smiles. The employees greet the athletes stepping off the shuttle with enthusiasm; they hug and greet each other warmly. Everyone is wearing work uniforms. The women walk into the complex together, talking and laughing. The camera films from the front, focusing on their facial expressions, conversations, and interactions. The camera angle is at eye level. In the next scene, the players enter the locker room. They approach the lockers where their jerseys are hanging and look at their uniforms, the ball, and their shoes. The camera first captures these objects in close-up, then pulls back into a wide shot. During this, moments where the players look directly into the camera are shown. In the following scenes, the female players are seen smiling together while looking at a trophy they have won. Then all the players run onto the court together. The female referee blows the whistle, and the match begins. While the camera shows the players' performance on the court, it also captures moments of solidarity, applause, and high-fives from an eye-level perspective. After one player scores a goal, she walks toward the camera, clenches her fists with her arms wide open, and smiles. In another scene, a player runs toward the goal with the ball; the camera films slightly from below, and a close-up shows the moment her body touches the ground. Then, another athlete from the opposing team is shown helping her up with an outstretched hand. Sweat droplets on a player's neck and her intense gaze are captured in a close-up. The next scene, from a bird's-eye view, shows a player taking a shot at the goal, and the goalkeeper leaping to block it. The goalkeeper's face is filmed from a low, slightly side angle as she lifts her chin while looking into the camera. In ongoing scenes on the field, players from both teams come together shoulder to shoulder and hand in hand, forming a joyful circle. The camera is placed on the ground, looking upward to capture the faces of all the players from below. Then the angle completely reverses into a bird's-eye view. The players are shown raising their hands together in celebration. The commercial ends with all the team

members standing, looking directly into the camera, smiling with their fists raised and arms stretched wide. The logo and hashtag appear on the screen.

Analysis

Social Constructivism

Women are featured in physically demanding, competitive spaces—sports complexes, locker rooms, handball courts—highlighting arenas where gender norms are challenged and re-negotiated. In this commercial, gender is constructed not through domestic imagery or traditionally “feminine” activities, but through scenes of collaboration, discipline, and physical exertion—coded practices typically reserved for masculinity in mainstream media. Team sports redefine femininity by positioning women as athletes who move, win, fall, and uplift each other. Their gear and environments place them as sporting professionals. Phrases like “Not rivals, we’re teammates” and “I’m here, stand with me” foreground solidarity over individual achievement, offering a gender vision that both confronts and transforms normative roles.

Gender Performativity

Female gestures—clenched fists, head-up gaze, jumps, recoveries, helping hands—perform gender as an active, powerful body practice. Low-angle camera shots elevate these performances. Women’s appearance—pulled-back hair, natural sweat, little-to-no makeup—signals sporty strength over feminine grace. Repeating collective movements—entering the court together, celebrating in unison—reinforces gender as communal, repeatable, and transformable. These are performative acts that collectively resignify strength, care, and resilience as feminine.

Feminist Media Theory

The ad offers a non-objectifying, solidarity-driven portrayal of women that challenges traditional gender narratives. The commercial positions female athletes and industrial workers as empowered, collaborative, and emotionally expressive agents of collective strength. The absence of fetishized camera angles—no fragmented body parts, voyeuristic gazes, or sexualized imagery—demonstrates an intentional departure from the male gaze. Instead, the use of eye-level and ground-up shots affirms the subjectivity and agency of the women portrayed, emphasizing their strength, camaraderie, and shared joy. This advertisement builds its empowerment narrative around collective experience. The recurring emphasis on unity and shared success suggests more relational, inclusive model of power. Moreover, the intermingling of industrial workers and athletes visually disrupts sectoral and class divisions, proposing an alternative feminist imaginary where labor—both physical and emotional—is valued equally. Close-up shots of sweat, gazes, and supportive gestures serve to humanize these women without sensationalizing their bodies. The celebratory tone, supported by visuals of embrace, laughter, and

resilience, constructs a positive, holistic representation of women as capable, assertive, and collaborative. In this regard, the ad contributes to the feminist call for media that portrays women not as objects of desire but as full subjects of action, emotion, and social transformation.

Türkiye Context

Featuring factory workers and handball players together highlights women's producer identity and collective solidarity, reflecting Türkiye's cultural narratives of camaraderie. Taglines like "unity" echo familial values but recast them as communal labor solidarity. Women's attire, accent-free Turkish, and sports facilities code them as urban, educated, middle class, while diverse socio-economic backgrounds remain visible. The ad positions female visibility in public and competitive fields as quietly subversive—symbolic transformation without overt political defiance.

Opet | Kadın dayanışması, umudun en güçlü temsilcisi oldu.

Sector: Energy

YouTube link: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=czS8GfUTiZs>

Auditory Transcript (Translated)

Büşra: I'm Büşra Tanır. I'm from Hatay, specifically from Antakya. My whole family lives here in Umutkent. After the earthquake, having such a job opportunity was truly a turning point in my life.

Şenay: When I came here, I realized how talented we actually are. I had no idea about my own talents. We're learning everything here.

Nisa: I feel so valued here. My ideas are taken seriously, and I also receive input. I'm improving myself here, I really love this place.

İkbal: They say, "Next week you'll do even better, İkbal. We believe in you." I find that strength within myself. I can pull myself together and get back into the rhythm.

Aybüğe: I learned to play volleyball in Umutkent. Thanks to this place, I'm achieving something.

Olçay: Living together in such a warm environment, and in a place with so many opportunities, is truly precious to us. For example, there's a kitchen where meals are cooked.

Hatice: I don't want this kitchen to ever close down. Whether I'm here or not, I hope it always exists. May it always smell like cake in here.

Eylem: Its name may be “Kitchen,” but it’s not just a kitchen. We come here and cry together, laugh together. Women’s power, it means we will succeed together and rise again, God willing.

Visual Transcript

Figure 37: Opet ad – Working with baby

Figure 38: Opet ad – Women chatting all together

The commercial opens with a young woman giving a statement inside a customer service center. She is wearing a black blouse, has makeup on, and her dyed and styled hair is down. The camera frames her in a portrait shot at eye level. Then, the scene shifts to a neighborhood setting where two conservatively dressed women are sitting on chairs placed outside a house. In the background are slippers, shoes, flower pots, and synthetic grass laid over wall-to-wall carpeting. One woman wears a headscarf and a printed skirt. The other wears glasses and has her natural loose hair. A street scene appears showing women and children of different ages, some with headscarves and some without, all gathered together. In the next scene, another woman giving a statement is wearing a brown shawl around her neck and a long-sleeved cream top. Her hair is straight and natural, and she wears optical glasses. She speaks indoors, in front of a garment workshop where three women in headscarves are working in the background. As she speaks, other women are seen sewing bags and working at sewing machines. The camera also focuses on objects and the work environment. Following this, a young girl with curly hair speaks with her hands clasped. She wears jeans and no makeup. The camera is positioned indoors in front of a wall decorated with colorful children’s posters. Then, a scene shows young girls and boys training on a field. In the next scene, two young girls are reading books in a library setting. Then, a young woman with curly hair, no makeup, and simple clothing gives a statement directly to the camera at eye level. In another scene, a woman wearing modest clothing is seen explaining something to children sitting around a table, pointing at a poster on the wall. Following this, children gathered around a larger table are seen clapping while looking at two women, one wearing a headscarf, the other with long, uncovered hair in a dress. In the next scene, girls are playing volleyball on a sports field. A girl in a red jersey gives a statement. Then, in an indoor setting with three women and a baby stroller, the women are seen working with papers. In successive scenes, women wearing both conservative and modern clothing are seen working at production machines and chatting over tea in the kitchen. Most of the women in this area are dressed conservatively. Next, a woman with black hair, wearing a black blouse, red lipstick, and jewelry gives

a statement. In the kitchen, a headscarfed woman hands a pan to an uncovered female chef standing beside her. The prepared meals and the other women in headscarves are then shown. In the next scene, cookies and tea are set on the kitchen table. Behind the table, a blonde woman with no makeup, dyed hair, and wearing a plain, long-sleeved cream blouse speaks to the camera. Wide shots show women chatting and working together in the kitchen. Throughout the commercial, all camera angles are at the subjects' eye level, no high or low angle is used to imply hierarchy. The commercial ends with the message appearing on screen: "Women's solidarity is the strongest symbol of hope." The commercial concludes with the brand's logo.

Analysis

Social Constructivism

The Opet commercial presents a powerful narrative that shows how gender is socially constructed through women's collective life practices. The advertisement brings women's social roles and solidarities to the forefront, highlighting how the identity of "womanhood" is shaped through communal living. Büşra's statement— "This job opportunity was a turning point in my life" —demonstrates how economic independence is not only transformative on an individual level but also within the context of community-based reconstruction. Scenes of kitchens, sewing workshops, and interactions with children, while referencing traditional female roles, are re-signified through new meanings. The line "It's not just a kitchen" points to how the spaces occupied by women also become sites of socio-emotional transformation. The visual representation of women from various ages, social classes, ethnic backgrounds, and clothing styles reveals that womanhood is not monolithic but rather a socially diverse and dynamic construction. Here, gender is not a fixed category but a socially shaped identity that gains strength through solidarity. The language used in the ad ("We will rise together") and the use of eye-level camera angles without any imposed hierarchy express that this construction is carried out collectively. In sum, the Opet commercial produces a representation of womanhood that is redefined not through individual success but through collective belonging and shared practices.

Gender Performativity

In the commercial, women embody abstract concepts such as strength, solidarity, and hope through the diverse roles they take on in everyday life. Sewing, teaching, producing in the kitchen, or playing volleyball—each of these repeated acts constitutes a performative expression of "womanhood." The women's recurring motivational support for one another reflects how performative identity is reproduced within the community. In a collective living space, women discovering their own potential proves that gender is not fixed, but transformable and performable. Aybüge's line, "I learned to play volleyball here," exemplifies how physical practice can evolve into a performative process of empowerment. Although the acts in the Opet commercial unfold in traditionally gendered spaces

(kitchen, sewing, childcare), the embedded difference lies in the layers of solidarity, hope, and subjectivity. Their diversity—with headscarves, styled, working—shows gender as socially produced, not essential. The presence of headscarved and non-headscarved women, manual laborers and professionals, renders empowerment a plural, performative act rather than a single model. In this context, the advertisement demonstrates that womanhood is not limited to fixed roles, but can be rewritten through collective performance.

Feminist Media Theory

Women are shown as holistic subjects: speaking, acting, teaching, working. Lighting is soft and realistic; no smooth filters idealize them. Throughout the Opet commercial, women are never eroticized; camera angles remain consistently at eye level, preventing the viewer from adopting a hierarchical or objectifying gaze. This allows women to be portrayed not as objects of spectacle but as active social subjects. Each woman is presented as a bearer of experience, labor, and collective memory. Women emerge as active agents, not passive subjects of empowerment. The narratives make emotional labor among women visible. This affective-political approach represents an amplified version of the emotional representation that feminist media theorists advocate. Furthermore, the diversity in the ad reflects a key feminist principle: representing women of different generations, ethnicities, and lifestyles without reducing them to a singular image. In this way, multiple female experiences are made visible, resisting reductive portrayals and contributing to a pluralistic vision of womanhood.

Türkiye Context

The commercial demonstrates how the representation of collective living spaces and civil initiatives stepping in where the state falls short can play a transformative role. The women featured in the advertisement are not confined to traditional “domestic roles”; they are also coded as active figures who produce, educate, and organize. While female representation in Türkiye is often shaped around the notions of motherhood, modesty, and loyalty, although motherhood in this ad is implicit via props, women are made visible through not only their socio-emotional labor but also their technical skills and organized communal practices. Scenes featuring both veiled and unveiled women reflect the religious, cultural, and class-based diversity of female identity in Türkiye, and suggest possible bridges feminism might build between secular and conservative groups. Therefore, the Opet commercial is not merely a brand narrative, but also contributes to a visual archive in which the female subject is redefined within Türkiye’s gender regime through collective strength and the capacity for healing.

Industrial & Agricultural Sectors Intra-Group Analysis

The Industrial & Agricultural Sectors group comprises three advertisements: Syngenta (Agricultural Science & Crop Protection), Cengiz Holding (Multi-sector Industrial & Services), and Opet (Energy).

The Industrial and Agricultural Sectors, as defined in this study, encompass industries characterized by high regulation, large-scale production, and technical specialization. The inclusion of Opet, Cengiz Holding, and Syngenta within this category reflects the structural and functional similarities of these sectors—each grounded in physical labor, engineering expertise, and systemic operations. This classification prioritizes the shared industrial logic that shapes how gender roles and empowerment are positioned within production-oriented fields. Each of the commercials centers on International Women’s Day but offers distinct portrayals of the “strong woman” across industrial, rural, and service-oriented contexts. Although diverse in scope and setting—from labs and courts to community kitchens in post-disaster zones—these ads share a common goal: to visualize women’s power not as innate, but as constructed, performed, and communal. This section seeks to uncover recurring themes and visual-symbolic codes across these sectoral portrayals, while also spotlighting their points of divergence. In doing so, it aims to evaluate how femvertising reshapes strength through lenses of labor, collectivity, and visibility in non-traditional advertising sectors.

Across all three ads, the notion of female strength is closely linked to visibility in public space and active labor. Whether through a woman steering a tractor (Syngenta), performing on a sports court (Cengiz Holding), or working in a communal place (Opet), each portrayal emphasizes women’s presence in spaces traditionally dominated by men or rendered invisible to the public gaze. These depictions resonate strongly with Judith Butler’s theory of gender performativity: strength is not essential or static, but rather enacted through repeated acts—physical, verbal, and symbolic—that challenge normative codes (Butler, 1990). In this context, even gestures like raising a fist or holding eye contact with the camera serve as performative assertions of agency. Moreover, the repeated use of collective framing—women standing shoulder to shoulder (Cengiz Holding), working and learning in groups (Opet), or narrated through plural pronouns such as “we” and “all of us” (Syngenta)—reflects Surrey’s (1991) “self-in-relation.” These women do not emerge as isolated heroines, but as part of a broader, unified force. The advertisements consistently employ eye-level or low-angle shots, reinforcing a narrative of equality and empowerment rather than objectification (Mulvey, 1975). There is also a notable absence of stylization filters or glamorization: natural lighting, minimal makeup, and functional clothing dominate the visual landscape, suggesting authenticity and labor-based strength.

Despite shared patterns, each advertisement carries sector-specific emphases and nuances. Syngenta’s campaign constructs strength as resistance to patriarchal disapproval, using confrontation-driven editing: angry male figures, pointed gestures, and direct camera engagement frame empowerment as defiance. Here, strength is framed as a fight—against taboos, hierarchy, and silence. Furthermore, the representation of a wide range of occupations (doctor, architect, scientist, boxer) establishes power through professionalism and intergenerational visibility, culminating in an older woman walking through the city with confidence. In contrast, Cengiz Holding’s advertisement locates strength in competitive sports and solidarity among women. The presence of a female uniformed athlete, and

collective celebrations on the court transforms traditional masculinity-coded sporting rituals into spaces of female affirmation. The sweat, physical exertion, and mutual support redefine femininity through embodied resilience and teamwork, offering a unique blend of physicality and sisterhood as the core of “women’s power.” Unlike Syngenta’s individualized voice-over narration, this ad relies heavily on gestures and non-verbal cues to transmit affect. Meanwhile, Opet’s advertisement is rooted in post-earthquake recovery, community rebuilding, and emotional resonance. Rather than professionals or athletes, it features women from diverse rural and urban backgrounds reflecting on learning, growth, and shared labor. Strength here is performative not through resistance or competition, but through care, continuity, and voice. Women speak directly to the camera, often in modest settings, revealing a quieter—but equally valid—form of strength rooted in relationality. The portrayal of both headscarved and uncovered women working together subtly destabilizes the binary between normatively defined modern and traditional, hinting at Türkiye’s socio-political complexities around gendered identity and female solidarity.

This sector group reveals how femvertising can be strategically adapted to male-dominated, industrial, and function-driven fields, challenging the assumption that empowerment narratives only belong to consumer-oriented or lifestyle sectors. While all three ads emphasize labor, collectivity, and non-sexualized empowerment, their sectoral tones diverge: Syngenta leans into defiance and visibility; Cengiz Holding celebrates physical performance and team cohesion; Opet centers emotional labor and post-crisis reconstruction. Collectively, they resist a singular definition of strength, instead constructing a polyphonic narrative of female power across class, region, and profession. This plurality also provides fertile ground for cross-sectoral comparisons—raising questions about whether femvertising can maintain its transformative edge as it enters fields marked by social conservatism, state narratives, or labor hierarchies.

CONCLUSION AND EVALUATION

INTERGROUP ANALYSIS ACROSS SECTORS

This section presents a final comparative analysis of the sector groups studied, aiming to uncover the underlying dynamics that shape how “strong women” are constructed across different commercial and cultural terrains in Türkiye. The advertisements analyzed span eight major sector groups—ranging from Beauty & Personal Care to Industrial & Agricultural fields—each reflecting distinct expectations, visual strategies, and ideological pressures.

According to Butler’s (1990) theory of gender performativity, repeated bodily actions—whether subtle gestures like flipping one’s hair or more forceful ones like throwing punches—function as performative acts that actively produce and express femininity, rather than being simple matters of appearance. Yet these performances diverge sharply depending on sectoral context. In Beauty & Personal Care, bodily control is equated with self-worth: smooth skin, voluminous hair, and yoga-toned bodies are framed as the currency of empowerment. By contrast, in Finance & Insurance, bodily visibility yields to vocal authority and institutional presence; women’s strength is articulated through public speech and historical legitimacy. From a social constructivist lens (Berger & Luckmann, 1966), each sector reproduces a culturally embedded notion of “appropriate” femininity. For instance, the Food and Home & Domestic Industries sectors reinforce care-based narratives, constructing strength through labor, community, and modest pride. The advertisements in these groups foreground repetition of domestic or productive gestures—kneading, designing, cooking, managing—as tools of gender socialization. However, while Lezita and Atia Interiors highlight women’s resilience in the face of material labor and social invisibility, ads from Yurtbay or Remove blend empowerment with a sanitized aesthetic, risking depoliticization by wrapping strength in sentimentality or perfectionism. Conversely, Automotive & Mobility and Technology & Telecommunications depict women as agents of performance, mobility, and innovation. Here, the female body is not fragmented but situated in motion—whether through sports, flight... These sectors resist objectification by using full-body framing and non-sexualized aesthetics, signaling a symbolic departure from traditional advertising tropes. Yet even within these progressive frames, traces of male mediation linger: male voice-overs, metaphorical narration, or legacy-based storytelling occasionally temper the portrayal of female autonomy. The Industrial & Agricultural Sectors offer the most radical recontextualization of femvertising. Here, strength is constructed not through glamour or speech but through collective labor, crisis response, and class-spanning solidarity. The presence of headscarved and non-headscarved women, manual laborers and professionals, renders empowerment a plural, performative act rather than a fixed ideal. This multiplicity exposes the tension between empowerment as a marketable image and empowerment as socio-political resistance. Ultimately, this

cross-sectoral evaluation reveals that femvertising in Türkiye operates within a spectrum: from commodified empowerment to culturally grounded agency. The meaning of “strong woman” is not fixed but fluctuates—shaped by sectoral ideologies, class positions, and media strategies. This pluralism, while occasionally contradictory, provides a critical mirror to the socio-economic structures that frame gender in Turkish advertising, and sets the stage for evaluating whether these portrayals resist, reproduce, or revise the symbolic order of power.

Cross-Sectoral Similarities in the Representation of the “Strong Woman”

Across sector groups as diverse as Beauty & Personal Care, Technology & Telecommunications, Home & Domestic Industries, and Finance & Insurance, a set of recurring visual, thematic, and discursive codes shape the portrayal of the “strong woman.” Despite differences in industry logic or target demographics, the commercials analyzed tend to converge around several motifs: bodily control, emotional resilience, multitasking, and symbolic labor. These commonalities not only reveal the diffusion of femvertising strategies across the Turkish advertising landscape but also illustrate the performative repetition of empowerment as a gendered expectation—what Judith Butler (1990) would define as the consolidation of gender norms through stylized acts. One of the most salient points of convergence lies in bodily performance as a marker of strength. In sector groups such as Beauty & Personal Care, Fashion, and Finance & Insurance, women are frequently depicted in command of their bodies—boxing, flipping hair, running, posing, or stretching. These physical gestures are consistently stylized through close-ups, low-angle shots, and slow-motion editing, reinforcing a hyper-visible form of bodily agency. Yet this visibility is not neutral. As Rosalind Gill (2007) argues, post-feminist media often aestheticizes empowerment, rendering strength palatable through visual beauty and composure. Even in commercials that aim to highlight agency, such as Pantene or AXA Sigorta, strength is consistently encoded through bodily discipline—nice skin, upright postures—suggesting that strength must be seen to be believed, and, more crucially, to be sold. Another recurring theme is emotional labor and resilience, especially visible in Home & Domestic Industries, Food, and Finance & Insurance sector groups. In the Beko, Domino’s, Yurtbay, and İş Bankası commercials, women are portrayed as carriers of emotional continuity—responsible not just for physical tasks but for holding families, teams, and even nations and the world together through care, perseverance, and grace. Emotional vocabulary such as “passion,” “dedication,” “strength from unity,” and “legacy” permeates these ads, framing the “strong woman” as someone who does not break under pressure but quietly absorbs and transforms it. Empowerment is cast not as defiance but as dignified endurance—maintaining composure and grace within the confines of traditional expectations. Multitasking and professional competence form another shared motif, cutting across Technology & Telecommunications, Finance & Insurance and Fashion sector groups. In Trendyol, Yandex, and AXA Sigorta advertisements, the female subject is portrayed as professionally competent, intellectually agile, and emotionally balanced—teaching, managing,

speaking, coding, or sewing with precision and poise. These performances of multitasking are often interlaced with visual symbols of productivity—laptops, design boards, whiteboards—suggesting that strength lies not in isolated acts but in the seamless integration of multiple roles. From a social constructivist perspective (Berger & Luckmann, 1966), these representations underscore how gendered expectations are institutionalized through the normalization of over-performance—women are shown not merely as capable, but as expected to excel in every domain. Moreover, maternal symbolism and intergenerational transmission of values appear across several sectors, particularly in Home & Domestic and Industrial & Agricultural groups. Commercials such as Beko, Opet, and Syngenta embed strength in relational dynamics—between mothers and daughters, teachers and learners, teammates and communities. These relationships function as cultural anchors that define women’s power through continuity and care rather than rupture or rebellion. In these sectors, strength is less about individual victory and more about communal legacy—a narrative strategy that both affirms and subtly confines women within relational roles.

In sum, while the ads span varied industries and aesthetics, they share a symbolic architecture that equates strength with visible competence, affective labor, and culturally approved ambition. Whether styled in a boxing gym or a ceramic factory, the “strong woman” is repeatedly cast as composed, competent, and caring. These convergences reveal a gendered patterning of empowerment that is at once progressive and conservative: progressive in its visibility and multiplicity, conservative in its reliance on recognizable, socially validated scripts. Such repetition not only stabilizes femininity as a consumable identity but also reifies the very norms it seeks to challenge—highlighting the limits and possibilities of femvertising as a transformative discourse.

Cross-Sectoral Differences in the Representation of the “Strong Woman”

While femvertising campaigns across sectors share thematic continuities, they also produce highly distinct articulations of female strength, shaped by each industry’s target audience, product type, and cultural positioning. These divergences result in varying symbolic constructions of empowerment—ranging from aestheticized individualism to collective labor, from emotional depth to rational credibility.

In the Beauty & Personal Care sector group, strength is largely rendered through aesthetic mastery and bodily control. Advertisements for brands like L’Oréal and Pantene equate female empowerment with visual transformation—hair becomes a metaphor for inner strength, and smooth skin a signifier of self-confidence. The use of close-up shots, soft lighting, and glamorized styling reinforces “empowered beauty”, where agency is articulated as self-care and visual perfection. Empowerment here is individual, emotional, and consumption-driven—rooted in the promise that the right product will unlock one’s inner power. The gaze remains active but curated, tailored to middle-class urban women negotiating between

career ambition and conventional femininity. In contrast, the Finance & Insurance sector group constructs strength through cognitive authority and historical continuity. Ads from Türkiye İş Bankası and AXA Sigorta emphasize public speaking and vision. Camera angles are often eye-level or low-angle, emphasizing respect and credibility rather than beauty. Clothing is minimal and professional—blazers, button-ups, neutral tones—visually aligning women with rationality, reliability, and public leadership. Here, strength is intellectual and symbolic, framed through narratives of national progress and legacy-building. Unlike beauty ads that focus on personal transformation, these commercials ground empowerment in structural access and civic contribution. The Industrial & Agricultural Sectors group offer a radically different paradigm: strength is rooted in manual labor, resilience, and collective identity. Ads like those from Syngenta and Opet depict women in fields, factories, and communal kitchens—using machinery, or rebuilding communities. Visual aesthetics are grounded in natural lighting, practical clothing, and unfiltered realism. Unlike the stylized empowerment of Fashion or the verbal authority of Finance & Insurance, these ads emphasize physicality and relational labor. Female strength emerges as communal and embodied, a product of teamwork, hardship, and visibility in male-coded industrial environments. In this way, empowerment resists commodification and aligns more with grassroots social transformation. In the Fashion sector group, the contrast between Nocturne’s aesthetic spectacle and Trendyol’s entrepreneurial documentary reflects a split vision of empowered femininity. Nocturne celebrates the woman as a curated visual subject—shot in dramatic lighting, high fashion, and solitary frames—where strength is synonymous with confidence, sensuality, and self-staging. This aligns with postfeminist values of “choice” and consumer agency (Gill, 2008). Trendyol, by contrast, highlights production, collaboration, and self-made success. Women are seen sketching designs, managing projects, and building businesses—framed in natural lighting, surrounded by tools, textiles, and partners. While both narratives commodify empowerment, they differ in emphasis: appearance versus action, spectacle versus structure. Technology & Telecommunications group ads blend symbolic authority and modern performativity. Vodafone showcases real athletes in dynamic, embodied motion—spiking, shouting, jumping—whereas Yandex constructs historical reverence through illustrated female professionals. The first offers contemporary strength through sweat, teamwork, and vulnerability; the latter through respectability, national duty, and elite status. These differences are visually encoded: Vodafone uses handheld shots, real-time emotions, and minimal stylization; Yandex relies on illustrations, vintage costumes, and muted color palettes. The former performs gender in motion, the latter as a commemorative ideal—each adapting femvertising to different cultural registers of strength. Lastly, Home & Domestic Industries—Beko, Atia Interiors, and Yurtbay Seramik—recode domestic labor as a site of empowerment. Beko’s intergenerational narrative constructs strength through temporal evolution, showing how gender roles are passed down, contested, and reimagined. Atia depicts physical labor—designing, lifting, building—as a radical reoccupation of masculine-coded work. Yurtbay, in contrast, offers a lyrical montage of female roles, often stylized and emotionally rich, yet risking depoliticization through universalized ideals. Technical contrasts are also notable: Atia’s gritty,

industrial framing contrasts with Yurtbay's soft light and poetic edits; Beko uses realism and narrative chronology to embed strength in socioeconomic transformation. In sum, the representation of strong women in Turkish femvertising varies substantially by sector. The distinctions are not merely aesthetic—they reflect deeper assumptions about gender, value, and power within each commercial ecosystem.

Dominant Patterns and Conceptual Synthesis

Despite the sectoral variety and surface-level pluralism, a set of dominant representational patterns emerges across the femvertising campaigns analyzed in this study. While each sector appears to tailor its depiction of the “strong woman” to its specific audience and industry context, these portrayals often coalesce into a hegemonic model of female empowerment—marketable, aestheticized, emotionally contained, and ultimately non-threatening to structural gender hierarchies.

Across sectors groups—from Beauty & Personal Care and Fashion to Technology & Telecommunications and Industrial & Agricultural Sectors—female empowerment is repeatedly tied to personal transformation, emotional resilience, and symbolic labor. Even when strength is framed through physicality (boxing, lifting, playing sports), it is often stylized and edited to avoid confronting deeply entrenched power structures. Aesthetic choices—such as soft lighting, close-ups of smiling faces, or postured defiance—render these depictions emotionally uplifting yet politically tame. This aligns with Banet-Weiser's (2018) critique of “empowerment feminism”, which celebrates visibility and voice while leaving systemic inequalities untouched. The underlying message becomes clear: women can be strong, as long as that strength remains palatable, aspirational, and brand-aligned. Indeed, a singular model of the “ideal strong woman” subtly dominates the advertising landscape: she is visibly composed, professionally competent, emotionally balanced, and socially respectable. Whether in high heels or work boots, she rarely expresses anger, contradiction, or dissent. Her power is narrated through success, harmony, and transformation—not struggle or confrontation. Even in commercials that feature headscarved women, working-class figures, or rural laborers, their presence is framed within stories of unity, service, and national pride, rather than critical resistance or subversion. This smoothing out of difference dilutes the potential of femvertising as a pluralistic or intersectional practice, reducing empowerment to a brand-friendly format that privileges elite, urban, and middle-class femininities. Furthermore, the strategic segmentation of strength by sector—aesthetic control in Beauty & Personal Care, rational trust in Finance & Insurance, community resilience in Industrial & Agricultural Sectors—suggests that femvertising is less about expanding the meaning of strength and more about adapting it to pre-existing marketing formulas. As McRobbie (2009) points out, postfeminist media culture uses feminist gains not to question patriarchy, but to revitalize capitalism. Similarly, in Türkiye, femvertising is at times shaped as a disciplinary discourse that presents female empowerment not as a right, but as a purchasable product. That said, certain exceptions challenge this pattern. Advertisements from Atia

Interiors, Mercedes-Benz, and Domino's, for instance, push the boundaries of traditional representations by emphasizing physical labor, historical authorship, and secular collectivism without relying on glamour or emotional spectacle. These moments suggest that counter-hegemonic portrayals are possible, particularly when strength is rooted in lived materiality rather than symbolic polish. However, such representations remain peripheral, often overshadowed by the dominant logic of individualized, apolitical empowerment.

In synthesis, the overarching narrative of femvertising in Türkiye does not suggest a radically transformative practice, but rather a carefully managed aesthetic of strength—designed to inspire without provoking, to empower without unsettling. While multiple versions of strong women appear across sectors, they are often tethered to a narrow range of affective, bodily, and ideological codes. Femvertising thus emerges as a highly adaptable yet ultimately conservative discourse, one that reflects the contradictions of neoliberal feminism: visibility without disruption, plurality without conflict, and power without politics.

Overall, the comparative findings underscore the sectoral nuances in defining and visualizing female strength, while also revealing the limitations of commercial empowerment discourses in challenging deep-rooted gender ideologies. While femvertising in Türkiye appears to embrace diversity—featuring women from different social classes, professions, and visual styles—it often converges around a narrow, market-friendly model of empowerment that privileges aesthetic control, emotional composure, and professional competence. Sectoral distinctions demonstrate that female strength is not a fixed ideal but a fluid construct shaped by industry logic and cultural coding. Yet, this fluidity does not always translate into transformative representation, most campaigns avoid confronting structural gender inequalities and instead offer a depoliticized vision of empowerment rooted in individual success and symbolic visibility. Despite some critical exceptions, the dominant narrative remains aligned with where strength is a performance to be consumed rather than a challenge to be posed.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following suggestions are designed to support advertisers, creative professionals, researchers, and media policymakers in fostering more inclusive, diverse, and socially responsible narratives of female empowerment. To avoid reinforcing existing class and beauty hierarchies, future femvertising campaigns should incorporate more diverse body types, socioeconomic backgrounds, and regional identities. Rural laborers, disabled women, elderly women, and those from marginalized ethnic communities remain largely invisible within current campaigns. Broadening this spectrum would not only enhance the authenticity of empowerment narratives but also reflect the plural realities of womanhood in Türkiye, where class and regional disparities remain deeply embedded in cultural representation. Turkish femvertising must also move beyond aestheticized confidence and individualized success stories to engage more directly with systemic gender inequalities—such as the gender pay gap, domestic violence, underrepresentation in STEM, and unpaid care labor. Campaigns can incorporate real policy goals, support women’s organizations, and include calls to action that extend beyond brand loyalty. This approach would re-anchor empowerment in collective progress rather than personal branding. Brands should consider adopting more documentary aesthetics, such as unscripted dialogue, handheld cameras, or less stylized lighting to portray women’s experiences with greater realism. Especially in Türkiye, where women’s everyday resilience often unfolds in less visible, more precarious environments, realism-based visual strategies could enable a more grounded form of storytelling. Rather than restricting empowerment to sector-specific tropes—beauty in cosmetics, intellect in finance, or labor in agriculture—brands should consider integrated narratives that reflect the complexity of modern womanhood. A campaign that simultaneously features a factory worker, an engineer, and a fashion designer could more effectively reflect the diverse modes of female strength. Such collaborations could also create opportunities for solidarity across class, region, and profession—transforming femvertising from segmented messaging into a shared cultural discourse.

Media regulators, advertising associations, and creative agencies should work together to develop gender-sensitive advertising guidelines—with clear criteria for avoiding tokenism, objectification, and essentialism. These guidelines could include requirements for balanced representation, inclusive casting practices, ethical storytelling, and stakeholder consultation. Additionally, brands should be encouraged to undergo gender impact assessments during the development phase of campaigns, involving gender experts, sociologists, and activists to ensure that representations align with real-world equity goals. Advertising agencies should not view gender representation merely as a creative or branding challenge, but as a core element of their institutional ethics and social responsibility. Femvertising cannot be reduced to a visual trend; it must be embedded in agency culture—from creative briefs to casting, voiceover selection, and editing processes. Agencies in Türkiye should actively seek to collaborate with women’s rights organizations and diverse communities, not just as “subjects” of campaigns, but as co-

creators of representational narratives. This would reposition advertising as a tool of social engagement, not just commercial persuasion. Universities, advertising agencies, and civil society actors can co-develop workshops, roundtables, and research-based briefs that help practitioners understand the ideological effects of their visual choices. In Türkiye, this alliance can also function as a mode of academic resistance and public education.

In conclusion, these recommendations emphasize that femvertising, if critically approached, has the potential to move beyond surface-level symbolism and contribute to meaningful social change. This requires a shift from representation as image to representation as intervention—a reframing of empowerment not as a marketable quality, but as a social, cultural, and last but not least, political process. Because the personal is political (Hanisch, 1970) when it is woman.

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